

Risk Management Practices of Commercial Banks of United Kingdom

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Abstract

Perhaps one of the greatest shocks from the economic meltdown of 2007-08 had been the global failure of risk management. Risk management failures at big financial and non-financial firms had captured the headlines for many years in international electronic and print media. The most common reasons for these collapses were facilitated by deficient risk management systems and corporate governance failures. Following the global financial meltdown, risk management has been of significant importance in the banking industry and many companies have started paying attention to risk management.

This study aims to explore the current practices of risk management followed by London banks with a particular focus on HSBC and LLOYDS and to evaluate the effectiveness of these practices. Convenience sampling has been used to conduct both interviews and survey questionnaires because staff selected for interviews has been chosen with respect to head office managers, managers of branches, and managers of risk management departments in banks. Mixed methods research design has been undertaken in which qualitative data has been analysed using thematic analysis and secondary data has been analyzed by conducting statistical analysis and descriptive analysis.

The current research has investigated the current practices of risk management followed by banks after comparing and corroborating the findings of thematic analysis, statistical analysis with the literature review and research questions of the study and have evaluated their effectiveness. The current research has contributed to the body of knowledge by recommending a stringent risk management framework to enhance the financial resilience of the banking industry and has determined the relationship between capital adequacy of banks and risk management. A somewhat positive significant relationship has been found between capital adequacy of banks and their risk-weighted assets. However, capital adequacy of banks not only depends on risk management but also on other factors such as risk profile of banks, risk preferences of shareholders, bondholders and risk managers, and capital regulatory requirements of regulators.

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I have no words to offer gratitude to my family for their patience, steadfastness and prayers who suffered a lot because of my studies. I hope and believe that this endeavour and work would lead to fruitful results.

Declaration

I declare that this work is my own work and it is being submitted for DBA (Doctor of Business Administration) at the University of the West of Scotland. This work has not submitted for any other examination and degree in another university.

Signature

Personal details withheld.

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Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Chapter one aims to provide an overview of the current study. It sheds light on the research questions, the background of the current research, research gap, rationale of the study, aim and objectives and conceptual framework of this research. An outline of the research methodology undertaken for each objective of the study has been discussed in this chapter. In the end, an outline of the structure of the thesis has been presented.

1.2 Background of the study

The UK is one of the largest economies in the world and it is the second largest economy in Europe after Germany. Its banking sector plays a leading role in boosting its economy and strengthening its financial sector. Its banking industry is the fourth largest banking sector in the world and many internationally established banks are working in the UK. Banks and financial institutions in the UK offer various financial products and services to customers including loans, investment banking, mortgage lending, residential lending and insurance.

Financial innovation, globalization, complex financial products and services have exposed banks to a wide range of risks. In addition, big corporate failures including Barings bank, Northern Rock, Lehman Brothers, and the recent economic meltdown has demonstrated that poor risk management systems adopted by banks have not only adverse impact on the performance of banks but also affect the wider economy and erode consumer confidence (Hubbard, 2009). Moreover, increased expansion in the banking industry of the UK has made it high leveraged and has made the banking industry more volatile and uncertain because of product innovation, financial diversification, financial market regulations and financial deregulations (Burki and Niazi, 2010).

Risk management is a cornerstone of the banking sector. In the current volatile business environment, the banking industry is facing various interrelated risks such as market risk, operational risk, liquidity risk, foreign exchange risk and credit risk. These risks are of paramount importance for banks as these risks may threaten their survival and performance and subsequently undermine consumer's confidence in the banking system. Furthermore, the latest financial meltdown and the collapse of big firms have emphasized the need for establishing a stringent risk management system in banks to absorb financial shocks (Al-Tamimi, 2002).

A robust risk management system assists banks in optimizing the value of banks and enables management to make informed decisions regarding their risk response strategies. Adoption of advance risk management techniques grants banks an opportunity to gain access to various means of credit sources which enhance their ability to reduce the volatility of earnings and associated losses (Drzik, 2005).

Therefore, in the current volatile business environment, an effective system of risk management is of paramount importance for banks because they cannot define their objectives effectively without risk management and they are more likely to be run undirected.

1.3 Importance and Rationale of the Research

After the global economic crisis, risk management has got significant importance in the banking sector. Eminently, in recent years there has been extensive growth in the field of risk management because financial firms and companies are exposed to a more unpredictable and volatile business environment where past certainties no longer hold (Bernstein, 1996). At the same time, more advance and sophisticated means of managing risks have been envisaged which have enhanced the risk understanding and improved the ability of firms to manage risks. Therefore, financial crisis and the collapse of big firms globally served as an awakening to bankers, investment firms, insurance industries and financial experts drawing their attention to the importance and urgent need of a sound system of risk management (Buckley, 2011).

As explained in section 1.2, the UK banking sector is the fourth biggest banking field in the world and many internationally established banks are operating in the UK. Its banking industry is playing a dominant role in national development and boosting the UK economy. Whereas, the success and continuity of banks depend on stringent systems of risk management and internal control which enables to absorb financial shocks and weather financial stress (Scarborough, 2011; Wilson, 2007; Kao et al. 2011).

There is limited research conducted on exploring risk management practices in the context of the UK commercial banks particularly after the financial crises of 2007-2008. Cross-segment mergers, acquisitions, financial diversification and product innovation have made banks in the UK more vulnerable to various risks. There is a considerable amount of literature on risk management in banks in various countries. Nevertheless, there is a little research undertaken on exploring risk management with a specific emphasis on commercial banks in the UK; this includes studies conducted by Abdou, English and Adewunmi (2014), Mahlkecht (2009) and Sundararajan (2007).

Moreover, previous studies on risk management highlight issues in electronic banking of the UK banks and they do not cover all aspects of risk management in the context of subprime crises and financial downturn (Abdou, English, and Adewunmi, 2014). In this regard, this study is distinct from earlier studies by offering recommendations to improve risk management function in banks that ultimately helps policymakers, management and investors in enhancing the financial resilience of the banking industry.

Therefore, this research has been undertaken to determine the risk management practices currently adopted by London banks within the context of HSBC and LLOYDS and to evaluate the effectiveness of these practices. This makes a contribution to the available literature on risk management in the context of the London banks by exploring the current practices of risk management and evaluating their effectiveness. This study helps in investigating whether the banks are following risk management guidelines recommended by the Bank of England and the Bank for International settlements (BIS). It contributes to the body of knowledge by exploring the role of risk management in deciding the capital adequacy of banks and determining their relationship.

Also, the current research can contribute to the existing literature on the usage of institutional theory by investigating the risk management guidelines of the Bank of England for UK banks. This study tests the uniformity assumption (homogeneity) of an institutional theory under which all banks operating in the UK need to build up and execute a sound system of risk management to meet the regulatory requirements of the Bank of England (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983).

1.4 Research Gap

Risk management is a backbone of the modern banking industry and plays a leading role in the stability and success of banks. Different studies have been undertaken to elucidate risk management in banks. However, a detailed review of literature on risk management has identified that most of the studies have been done in various countries including UAE, Germany, Malta and USA on different aspects of risk management but not with specific emphasis on commercial banks. One study has been done on risk management in electronic banking of the UK banks that includes all banks incorporated in the UK. Therefore, no study has yet been undertaken to explore risk management practices followed in the UK commercial banks and evaluate their effectiveness. In addition, it is still unknown how much capital adequacy of the UK commercial banks is affected by risk management and what is their relationship. Therefore, the current study has been undertaken to address the research

gap with regards to exploring the risk management practices followed in the London banks within the context of HSBC and LLOYDS and to evaluate their effectiveness.

1.5 Research Questions

Given the complexity of the research topic, the following research questions have been developed that this study has sought to be answered to meet the aim and objectives of the current study.

1.5.1 Research Question

How effective are the current practices of risk management followed by London banks within the context of LLOYDS and HSBC and what risk management framework can be recommended to enhance the financial resilience of the banking sector?

1.5.2 Sub Questions

Q1. What are the key risks faced by HSBC and LLOYDS?

Q2. What are the current practices of risk management followed by London banks (LLOYDS and HSBC) and what is the relationship between various aspects of risk management to manage risks, maximise opportunities and uphold economic stability?

Q3. Is there any relationship between risk management and the amount of capital banks hold?

Q4. How to evaluate the application of Basel III in London banks and to determine the impact of Basel III in managing risks?

Q5. What kind of risk management framework can be recommended to enhance the financial resilience of the banking sector?

1.6 Aim

To assess the effectiveness of current practices of risk management followed by London banks with a specific focus on LLOYDS and HSBC in order to develop a sound risk management framework to enhance the financial resilience of the banking sector.

1.7 Objectives

Following the identification of research questions; an attempt has been made to operationalise the research questions within the context of research objectives. Therefore, research objectives are outlined as:

1. To determine the key risks faced by HSBC and LLOYDS.

2. To ascertain the current practices of risk management followed by London banks and to explore the relationship between various aspects of risk management to manage risks, maximise opportunities and uphold economic stability
3. To investigate if there is any relationship between risk management and the amount of capital banks hold.
4. To evaluate the application of Basel III in London banks and to determine the impact of Basel III in managing risks.
5. To recommend a risk management framework to enhance the financial resilience of the banking sector.

1.8 Conceptual Framework

Pragmatism philosophy has been adopted in this study along with the deductive approach to answer the research questions. The mixed methodology has been used in which primary data has been collected through semi structured interviews with managers and risk managers of HSBC and LLOYDS across London and survey questionnaires have been sent to bank managers, and risk managers in London to get their opinions and perceptions on risk management. Secondary data has been obtained from the annual accounts of banks. Thematic analysis has been used to analyse qualitative data (interviews) whereas quantitative data have been analysed using descriptive and statistical analyses. Hypotheses are developed between independent and dependent variables that have been subject to rejection or acceptance based on the statistical analysis.

In the subsequent sections, a synopsis of methods to collect and analyse data for each objective has been discussed:

1. The first objective of this work is about determining the key risks faced by HSBC and LLOYDS in London. To achieve this objective, quantitative and qualitative data has been collected using the methodology of (Abdou, English and Adewunmi, 2014). Descriptive and statistical analyses undertaken on survey questionnaire have facilitated this research to find the mean and standard deviation which enable the current study to explore the main risks encountered by banks. Findings of thematic analysis and descriptive analysis have been compared and corroborated with the research questions and literature review to substantiate the findings to achieve this objective.
2. The second objective of the current research focuses on ascertaining the current practices of risk management followed by London banks. To meet this objective,

quantitative and qualitative data has been collected using the methodology of (Abdou, English and Adewunmi, 2014; Bezzina, Grima and Mamo, 2014). It has been dealt with the mixed research strategy based on interviews and survey questionnaire sent to banking professionals of the HSBC and LLOYDS. Thematic analysis has been used to record the responses of interviews and interpret its findings.

3. The third objective of this work is to explore if there is an association between risk management and the amount of capital banks hold. Secondary data has been collected online; risk-weighted assets have been used as proxies for assessing the risk portfolio of banks and it has been captured from financial statements of banks. Amount of capital banks hold has been collected from annual accounts of banks that represent their capital adequacy.

In order to achieve this objective, a hypothesis has been developed between study variables using multiple regression analysis.

Independent variable: risk-weighted assets

Dependent Variable: the amount of capital

4. The fourth objective aims to evaluate the application of Basel III in London banks and to determine its impact on managing risks. This objective has also been dealt with mixed methods research strategy. The findings of thematic analysis and descriptive statistics have been critically compared with the literature review and research questions to reach the overall conclusion about this objective.
5. Finally, the last objective of this study aims to suggest a risk management framework to enhance the financial resilience of the banking sector. This objective has been dealt with the qualitative research strategy in which primary qualitative data has been collected from banking professionals. For this purpose, interviews have been conducted with bank managers and risk managers in HSBC and LLOYDS and have obtained their opinions about risk management framework. Interview responses have been analysed using thematic analysis which have been compared and corroborated with the literature review and the research question to achieve this objective.

1.9 Composition of the Research Work

The current thesis has a total of six chapters. The overview of each chapter is discussed in the following sections.

Chapter one: This chapter provides background information and rationale for conducting this study. It explains the research gap, the research questions, the aim and objectives of the study. An outline of the research methodology and conceptual framework has also been explained in this chapter.

Chapter two: This chapter puts the spotlight on available literature on risk management in the banking sector. It explains risk management in banks, types of risks faced by the banking industry along with various risk management guidelines to cope with the risks. Basel accords have been critically reviewed in this chapter and various risk management frameworks used in various countries have also been presented in this chapter.

Chapter three: This chapter aims to explain the research methodologies undertaken in this research. The research philosophies, research strategy, research design, research approach, methods of data collection and analysis and ethical considerations have been discussed in this chapter.

Chapter four: Chapter four aims to presents the findings of data analysis undertaken for interviews conducted with banking professionals, survey questionnaire and secondary quantitative data. For this purpose, this chapter has been divided into five parts after taking into account the research objectives of the study.

Chapter five: Chapter five is the analysis and discussion chapter in which the findings of data analysis have been discussed in detail, corroborated and compared with the literature review, research questions and objectives of the study to substantiate the findings which assist the current research to achieve the overall aim of the study.

Chapter six: This is the concluding chapter which intends to present an overview of all previous five chapters. It also describes the reflection on research findings, the contribution of research, research limitations and recommendations for future research. Conclusion of the research findings has also been presented in this chapter.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The literature review chapter provides a critical discussion on existing literature on risk management in banks and evaluates the efficiency of risk management practices adopted by banks to manage the risks they face. Depending on the size, nature and complication of business operations of banks over the last two decades, the existing literature on banking industry has been subjugated by design, adoption and monitoring of various risk management frameworks (Stan-Maduka, 2010). Furthermore, the impact of adopting risk management frameworks on banking performance and their implications using different methodologies and their theoretical perspectives have been critically reviewed in the current literature.

This chapter comprises of three major sections and each section encompasses subsections to cover all aspects of risk management. In the first section, risk management has been explained in general, how it is evolving and previous empirical research has been discussed that has provided theoretical justification for risk management adopted by the UK banking industry. Moreover, the impact of the failure of risk management on the recent financial crisis of 2007-08 has been reviewed emphasising the need for establishing a stringent system of risk management in banks.

In section two, risk management has been discussed with a particular focus on financial firms and different risk management frameworks used by banking industries in USA, China, Europe and developing countries have also been discussed. Role of Basel accords has been critically reviewed in dealing with different risks. In the last section, risk management has been discussed within the context of the UK banking sector.

The following sections provide a detailed analysis of the above discussed key areas underpinning risk management in banks.

2.2 Banking Risk

The term risk holds no universal definition, rather banking risk has widely been used by different researchers in recent times (Ghosh, 2012). However, different commentators apply different approaches and definitions to define the scope of banking risk. Risk is a possibility of deviation from an anticipated outcome that is hoped for and expected. This possibility of risk is explained in terms of probability ranging from 0 to 100 per cent. However, the probability of risk is neither definite nor impossible. Therefore, this definition does not require probability to be quantified, rather it must exist (Gallati, 2003).

Schroeck (2002) and Bessis (2002) define banking risk as a source of uncertainty that brings undesirable impacts on the expected returns of banks. Likewise, Ghosh (2012) reinforces the above claims and argues that banking risk is a potential loss that arises due to multiple unpleasant economic events for instance financial meltdown, tumbling equity prices, adverse fluctuations in trade policy, and unfavourable changes in exchange rates and interest rates. Furthermore, the above claims make it evident that banking risk not only depends on the real-world situations but also on the external environment in which banking industry operates and it has a huge impact on the way risks are identified and managed.

The Bank of England (BoE) identifies seven key risks that are currently encountered by banks in the UK. These risks consist of liquidity risk, credit risk, risk of a cyber attack, market risk, operational risk, geopolitical risk and political risk. According to the Systemic Risk Survey (SRS) that is undertaken by the Bank of England every six months, political risk has been found the most significant risk faced by the UK banks in a current banking environment (BoE, 2020).

The reason for considering the political risk the most important risk is that over the past decade, the focus of big banks, building societies, hedge funds, pension funds and insurers in the UK has shifted from financial risks to political risks. HSBC is currently facing various risks depending on its operation and financial products and services. Interest rate risk, capital risk, operational risk, risk of cyber attack, market risk, liquidity risk, resilience risk, credit risk, regulatory compliance risk and insurance manufacturing operations risk are principal risks that are faced by HSBC (HSBC, 2019). By contrast, risks that are faced by LLOYDS are categorized into operational risk, operational resilience risk, capital and liquidity risk, people risk, credit risk, insurance underwriting risk, model risk and governance risk (LLOYDS, 2019).

There are four main categories of risk that are faced by banks. These include

- 2.2.1 Market risk
- 2.2.2 Operational risk
- 2.2.3 Enterprise risk
- 2.2.4 Financial risk

2.2.1 Market Risk

According to the Bank for International Settlement (BIS), market risk is a risk of potential losses in on and off-balance sheet positions of banks that arise due to fluctuations in market prices of their stocks (Gallati, 2003). The overall market risk is an aggregation of key risks

including interest rate, commodity, foreign exchange and equity risk. Gallati (2003) recommends conceptual frameworks to manage market risk. Investment diversification is a well established approach that can be adopted by firms to diversify away from their risks (Roy, 1952; Marschak, 1938; Hicks, 1962).

Moreover, the market risk is a systematic risk that emanates from a decline in the market value of investments as a result of adverse economic developments and other unfavourable events influencing the markets in which firms undertake trading (EIIB, 2010d). Schroeck (2002) reinforces above claims and argues that market risk is closely related to the market value of an asset and appears due to systematic factors including adverse movements in the market value of trading portfolios, equities and instruments.

2.2.2 Operational Risk

Operational risk is one of the most significant risks that are not only faced by the banking industry in current economic markets but also non-financial firms are also exposed to operational risk. The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS) published a consultative paper on operational risk in 1998; according to which operational risk is the risk of loss arising from inadequate and failed internal processes, systems, people and from external events (BCBS, 2006). Therefore, operational risk has become a significant component of a sound risk management framework in contemporary economic markets (Gallati, 2003).

Akkizidis and Khandelwal (2007) further add that technology, processes, external events, people and breakdown of internal control are key causes of operational risk. Lack of expertise, human error, fraud, non-compliance with laws and regulations are the main factors of people risk.

Unlike other risks, operational risks are not easy to determine and counter due to their interdependence on other risks and only appear once a big issue arises. Internal fraud (employee theft, intentional inappropriate of positions and insider trading), external fraud (forgery, computer hacking, robbery and cheque kiting) and employment practices and workplace safety (non-compliance with health and safety laws, workers inappropriate wages, insufficient working facilities and discrimination claims) are the main risks associated with operational risk (Lowe, 2010).

2.2.3 Enterprise Risk

Enterprise risks are risks that cause the capability of a business to function inappropriately and in jeopardy and ultimately incur significant losses. There are many kinds of enterprise risk. These comprise of operational risk, compliance risk, strategic and financial risk (CMA, 2018). These risks are not easy to identify. Enterprise risk management is

“A process, effected by an entity’s board of directors, management and other personnel, applied in strategy setting and across the enterprise, designed to identify potential events that may affect the entity, and manage risk to be within its risk appetite, to provide reasonable assurance regarding the achievement of entity objectives” (COSO, 2004)

It is a new risk management framework that assists firms in managing a portfolio of risks and helps policymakers equally in developing mechanisms to improve firm-wide risk management and corporate governance.

A well-established enterprise risk management function is a source of value creation and competitive advantage for a firm if all material risks are viewed and managed in a single integrated framework. ERM as a firm-wide business strategy assists an organisation in identifying, analysing, evaluating and overseeing risks. It helps the management to make a robust plan of action making available to shareholders, stakeholders and potential investors as a part of their annual reports (Nagaoka, 2007; Nocco and Stulz, 2006).

Unfortunately, ERM has serious flaws that may erode its credibility. It lacks the framework it touts because it has no defined process and consists of bits and pieces. Therefore, it lacks an ability to ensure total management of all risks. It focuses on obvious and sensational while overlooking routine and mundane. For example, Enron and WorldCom spent millions of dollars on establishing ERM but it failed to address the risks of financial reporting and accounting. ERM is a reactive paradigm instead of proactive because it fails to identify risks that yet have to be revealed and experienced by management and focuses only on easily observed risks (Grose, 2011).

2.2.4 Financial Risk

Financial risk is a risk that a company’s cash flows appear to be inadequate to fulfil its financial obligations and shareholders may bear losses if they invest their money in a company facing cash flow problems. Bondholders may lose money if a corporation or government is exposed to financial risk and is defaulting on its bonds. Several financial ratios are used by investors to measure the prospects of their investment. Debt to capital ratio

determines the proportion of debt used in the total capital structure of a company (ACCA, 2016).

Investment is considered to be risky if a company has more borrowing in the form of debt in its capital composition because of the preference of repayment to creditors over ordinary shareholders in case of insolvency. Another ratio is the capital expenditure ratio that measures the ratio of cash flow and operations by capital expenditures to find out how much money a firm holds to continue the business operations running after paying off its debt. Financial risk is mainly categorised into four types which include credit risk; currency risk, liquidity risk, and foreign exchange risk that are discussed briefly in the following sections.

According to the Bank for International Settlement (BIS), credit risk exposure refers to the risk that a counterparty will be unable to settle its financial obligations in full value when these are due to be repaid (Gellati, 2003; Bessis, 2002; Schroeck, 2002). Hempel and Simonson (1999) support above stances and argue that credit risk is a threat that a bank is unable to collect its principal amount and interest on securities and loans when promised. Dhakan (2006) further adds to the above claims and emphasises that in majority of banks; advances and loans are the principal sources of credit risk exposure that is worth eliminating through employing effective credit risk management models (Greuning and Bratanovic, 2009; Karim, 2006).

However, Gellati (2003) proposes conceptual frameworks for modelling credit risk. Every bank develops designs and implements its credit risk management model and culture concerning its requirements. Some banks implement systems that monitor credit risk exposure throughout the organisation whilst others monitor credit risk in individual business lines. Risk-based pricing, limiting exposures; evaluation of the risk-return profile of business lines, employing risk-adjusted return on capital (RAROC) and determination of economic capital calculation are widely used models by banks to monitor credit risk exposures.

Liquidity risk is one of the most important risks faced by banks. Financial liquidity is of paramount importance for the proper running of the financial system across the globe. In fact, since the financial downturn of August 2007-2008 stock markets in various countries have borne all the hallmarks of enhanced liquidity risk. It further reveals that how liquidity risk contaminates market liquidity and invites responses from central banks to address this risk (Nikolaou, 2009).

Liquidity risk is the incapability of banks to meet their liabilities when they are due to be repaid. Similarly, the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision defines liquidity risk as banks run the risk of liquid assets because of several reasons making them unable to unwind

their positions and settle their liabilities when they are due (BIS, 2008; IMF, 2008). These findings are reinforced by Matz and Neu, (2006) who consider liquidity risk as a momentous risk as it tends to raise more spikes in other financial risks.

On the other hand, market saturation, increased immediate intentions of depositors for funds withdrawal, and inappropriate market depth run the chances of liquidity risk (Santomero 1997; Saunders and Cornett, 2008; BCBS, 2008). They further point out that banks are exposed to liquidity insolvency as a result of inadequate liquidity that may erode the financial resilience of the whole banking industry thereby shattering the confidence of depositors and shareholders (Fayyaz, 2006).

However, systemic liquidity risk can be eliminated by adopting transparent liquidity management practices. Regulation and supervision are principal tools against systemic liquidity risk. By minimising moral hazard and asymmetric information; liquidity risk is more likely to be tackled through adequate monitoring mechanisms of the financial system. Furthermore, collection of required information necessary to address liquidity risk makes risk management mechanisms costly particularly for smaller companies (Nikolaou, 2009).

Foreign exchange risk emanates because of erratic transition in the foreign exchange rate that exerts adverse influence on the capability of banks to settle their obligations (Tahir, 2006). Ishfaq (2006) further rationalises that market speculation, political instability, public debt, current account deficit and inflation are the main driving factors that contribute to deteriorate the exchange rate. Foreign transactions undertaken with counterparties in foreign countries also carry this risk. Rate of return on foreign investments is likely to be eroded if the foreign exchange rate becomes more volatile and uncertain. This volatility in foreign exchange brings immense losses and tends to inhibit foreign investment.

However, foreign exchange risk can be addressed by adopting various risk management techniques. Financial derivatives including futures, forwards, and credit default swaps are widely used derivatives to counter this risk.

Equity risk is the erosion of profit and earnings of banks arising from unfavourable fluctuations in the market value of equity portfolios. Bessis (2002) rationalises equity risk in terms of negative movement in the market value of stocks and commodities held by banks and this risk tends to be systematic or unsystematic in banks' operations.

However, Norges Bank (2016) proposes equity risk premium (ERP) that is a measure of how much investors are compensated for investing in stocks, bonds and bearing equity risk. This measure outlines the potential of tremendous equity wealth building and plays a central role in making investment decisions.

By contrast, Stevenson (2014) illustrates in his article published in financial times that option-based products are used by banks to hedge portfolios against equity risk. Turbos, covered warrants and traded options are widely recommended structured products that have the potential to return from the markets and hedge portfolio risks.

From the foregoing, it can be argued that the banking sector is exposed to an array of risks in the global financial world that creates threats for their success and survival. Therefore, consideration and assessment of different risks emphasise the need for the banking institutions to comprehend the significance of risk management and implement its recommendations accordingly to counter various risks.

The subsequent section explains risk management with respect to its definitions and applications:

2.3 Risk Management in Banks

It is an integrated, strategic and active process aiming at the determination and management of risk with the overall goal of enhancing the market value of banks whilst reducing the risk of bankruptcy. Bessis (2002) rationalises a combination of various risk management models and processes assisting banks in identifying, analysing, assessing and managing risks they face. A risk management system consists of all tools and models necessary for overseeing and controlling various risks. Above arguments are supported by Bessis (2002) who illustrates that risk management is an achievement of various activities undertaken to lessen the undesirable impact of uncertainty and to minimise the risk of losses.

Effectiveness of a robust risk management framework depends on how efficiently different activities are undertaken by who charged with governance evaluate risk exposures, limit positions to tolerable levels, formulate policies and strategies to deal with risk exposures, and ultimately assist decision-makers to control risks for sake of achieving the aim and objectives of the banking industry (State Bank of Pakistan, 2003).

Engel (2010) underpins the above discussion and argues that banks are predominantly riskier businesses; they must bear risks in order to get higher returns. Once the money is taken out from banks' deposits, banks are subject to the whole array of risks. More significantly, the existence and survival of a bank depend on the extent to which it has the ability to foresee and deal with risks.

So, it can be argued that risk management is a multifaceted practice in banking institutions that starts with the development of a risk management function to discover, assess and investigate risks thereby implementing required measures to minimise and control potential

losses. Above stances are supported by (Oldfield and Santomero, 1997) who argue that for the efficient functioning of risk management models, it is imperative for risk managers to decide what approaches and framework to be used after considering risk appetite and risk tolerance of banks.

2.3.1 Background to Risk Management

Risk management is a developing notion that holds different definitions. Risk management as a scientific approach has evolved from corporate insurance management and its central point is the probability of potential losses to income and assets of organisations. It is a modern innovation but real exercise of risk management is as old as civilisation itself. First managers working in the insurance industry were engaged at the end of the 20th century by big companies such as steel manufacturers and the railroads (Gallati, 2003).

In addition, Gallati (2003) illustrates in his book “Risk Management and Capital Adequacy” that emergence of modern risk management signalled a revolutionary and drastic change in methodology and philosophy happening when attitudes towards insurance regimes started to shift. The current shift from insurance management to modern risk management appeared over a period of time and introduced risk management as a new academic discipline.

Furthermore, Markowitz was the first financial theorist who first time introduced risk in his discussion paper regarding portfolio and diversification. He developed a relationship between risk and return and combined these approaches in his modern portfolio theory and initiated risk-return discussion (Markowitz, 1959). Subsequently, option-pricing theory by Fischer Black and Black and Scholes’s theory in 1970 were main developments that became the foundation of the derivative industry and provided an impetus for the banking industry to manage risks.

Bessis (1999) supports the above considerations and points out that modern risk management has played a leading role in the development of the current financial system. Irving Fisher was the first economist in the 20th century who emphasised the need for the significance of risk management in the appropriate running of stock markets. Furthermore, Sharpe’s Capital Asset Pricing Model introduced the concepts of residual risk and systematic risk and facilitated the development of techniques for capital structuring such as efficient market hypothesis, and pecking order theory (Stremme, 2005).

Therefore, it can be concluded that risk management is a fairly new field that has gained significance in banking institutions over the last few decades. The extent and kinds of risks faced by the banking industry have changed due to drastic changes to banking businesses

including the complexity of operations, globalisation, competition, diversification, and threat of new technology led to the obsolescence of products. These factors have exposed the banking industry to various interlined risks that have made risk management a principal academic discipline. It has played a vital role in determining the economic strength and resilience of the banking industry against financial shocks.

Next section intends to discuss risk management in the context of the UK banking sector.

2.3.2 Risk management in UK banks

The UK banking sector has undergone extensive regulatory changes after the recent financial crisis. Most of these changes were about the deregulation of the financial industry that resulted in the creation of a new banking structure (Casuet et al, 2006). According to Casuet et al, (2006), exclusion of regulatory limitations on the financial sector over the last twenty years was to encourage free trade, produce financial wealth and encourage free-market completion in the UK. After taking into account last two financial crises of 2000 and 2007, all banks operating in the UK have been required by the Bank of England to execute a concrete risk management system to make them financially resilient. More than a decade since the global economic meltdown, the Bank of England in the UK approached towards full implementation of post-crisis reforms for UK banks. For example, in 2013, the BoE formed the Prudential Regulation Authority, the UK's prudential regulator of investment firms, banks and an insurer (PRA, 2018).

2.3.3 Risk Management Procedures

The Prudential Regulation Authority in the UK has recognised the fact that banks in the UK are exposed to diverse kinds of risks in this dynamic and volatile business environment. Consequently, it has enforced risk management guidelines on banks depending on the various types of risks because inappropriate risk management may exert a financially unpleasant effect on the survival and continuity of banks in the UK (Burki and Niazi, 2010).

Risk management guidelines cover key aspects of a robust risk management framework such as understanding, identification, assessment, analysis, monitoring, controlling of risks, and management of credit, market, liquidity and operational risks. These aspects have considerable liaison with risk management practices. For examples; if the banks have an appropriate understanding of risks and have the capability to identify and evaluate risks; they are in an improved position to build up a stringent risk management function. All banks in the UK have been directed by the BoE to comply with basic fundamental principles of risk management regardless of their management structure and size (PRA, 2018).

According to the risk management principles discussed above, the overall responsibility for risk management in banks lies on the shoulders of the board of directors. They are required to design and develop strategies after taking into consideration various aspects of the operations of banks (Fatemi and Fooladi, 2006). Top management in banks has explicit responsibility for developing procedures, plans and risk management strategies for managing and controlling risks that are ultimately got permitted by the board. A brief overview of risk management guidelines with regards to key risks are summarised below:

According to risk management guidelines on market risk, top management of banks and board of directors set up a stringent framework for market risk management for the sake of coping with potential losses because of adverse movements in foreign exchange rates, equity prices and interest rates (PRA, 2018). Besides this, the Prudential Regulation Authority (PRA) has embedded the Senior Managers Regime for banks and insurance firms in the UK; assigning them accountability has become a dominant tool through which the PRA is delivering its supervisory approach towards enforcing risk management practices on the UK banks. These guidelines require banks to classify, appraise, evaluate and investigate market risks intrinsic in operations of banks and report risk exposures to top management.

The board is responsible for designing, implementing and overseeing policies for recognition and management of credit risk which depends on the overall business strategy of banks. Top management of banks is required to not only develop systems, procedures and policies on risk management but also directed to evaluate, approve and monitor those policies (Sokolov, 2007).

Similarly, guidance on liquidity risk emphasises the need for developing an instrument to recognize, evaluate and manage liquidity risks and top management and the board are accountable for developing and overseeing such policies. It is further directed that the upper management of banks to establish a sound organisational structure to oversee the liquidity position of banks in a timely fashion. There are important prerequisites of an effective liquidity risk management consisting of competent risk specialists, well-informed board and experienced staff with sound knowledge of system, tools and risk management (Richard et al, 2008).

All banks are directed to develop a resourceful framework for overseeing liquidity risk in the light of general and separate liquidity exposures based on various types of depositors and account holders. For that reason, banks need to evaluate future liquidity shortfalls and forecast a regular cash flow analysis under various scenarios and market forces. Therefore, risk limits, contingency planning to support liquidity and management information systems

have been suggested as key aspects of an effective liquidity management process under these guidelines.

The operational risk management strategies require banks to enhance their understanding of causes of potential operational risks which may adversely affect the banking operations and erode consumer confidence in the banking sector. Guidance on operational risk management directs the board to make sure that top management of banks has established appropriate policies, controls and models for all key aspects of operations (Anderson, 2010). Therefore, all banks in the UK irrespective of their size and scope of operations need to comply with the fundamental principles of risk management. Furthermore, senior management of banks is required to communicate risk management guidelines and policies to all employees and take necessary steps to provide essential training to relevant staff in banks. To offer a consistent arrangement for evaluating operational risk effectiveness, banks are required to ensure the disclosure of relevant information on a timely basis (Rosman, 2009).

Finally, the above discussion of risk management and relevant guidelines point out that it is imperative for banks in the UK to contemplate the risks effectively and then to develop various risk management strategies to manage risks for their success and survival.

The next section sheds a light on a theoretical approach to risk management:

2.4 A Theoretical Approach to Risk Management

Different models and tools have been reviewed by various theorists and researchers in the existing literature that provides a theoretical justification to the adaptation of the risk management framework by the banking industry (Santomero, 1995). These theories are explained in the subsequent sections:

2.4.1. Structuration Theory

2.4.2. The Financial Model (Economics)

2.4.3. Institutional Theory

2.4.4. Agency Theory

2.4.1 Structuration Theory

This theory determines the relationship between agents working on behalf of organisations and structures of organisations. According to this theory, humans act as agents in an organisation; they are influenced and shaped by the organisational structure that determines the values and operating policies of organisations (Giddens, 1984). Lamsal (2012) points out

that structuration theory is about the structures surrounding humans that are determined for them and volunteerism.

Furthermore, this theory is of the view that humans have a free choice to create their lived environment after taking into account their desires and needs. And, this environment seeks out the relationship between human agency with structures and institutions. Craib (1992) adds to the above discussion and explains that structuration identifies the relationship between social forces and individuals that tends to act upon them. This theory illustrates that individuals have restricted knowledge and they do not have the ultimate preference of their actions. Nonetheless, they are actors that produce social change and regenerate social structure (Craib, 1992 and Cloke, 1991).

On the other hand, structuration theory has some limitations that may undermine its usefulness. As this theory pinpoints problems in the context of social research therefore it can be applied in context with limitations to the broader application. This merit makes it useful to be applied in social research. However, this theory is less applied outside of social perspective. Giddens (1984) exerts focus on the definition of social that embarks human actions, experiences and their interactions with society. The social term helps in understanding human behaviours in institutions. Therefore, different definitions of the term social by different researchers have eroded the credibility of this theory (Boland, 1993 and Callon, 1981).

It is summarised from the foregoing discussion that structures comprising moral codes, institutions, traditions and expectations are steady. However, they are likely to be modified as a result of the inadvertent consequences of an action. For instance; when individuals give no consideration to the social norms; they can surrogate and recreate in their way. Scapens and McIntosh (1996) support above stances and rationalise that humans develop social reality by interacting with organisational structures as they act as free agents on behalf of shareholders. Also, Scapens and McIntosh (1996) consider institutions as a creation of duality of an arrangement in which communal structures play a major role in their formation and are instituted by agents.

In terms of the banking industry, structuration theory considers risk specialists more well-informed and experienced that formulate policies and strategies regarding risk management. Nonetheless, risk managers as agents carry out their activities independently outside of their beliefs; norms and values thereby assisting management in developing risk management systems.

2.4.2 The Financial Model (Economics)

This model is based on the work of Modigliani Miller that suggests the circumstances for irrelevance (Miller and Modigliani, 1958). Stulz (1984) identified feasible economic reasons to determine why managers play their role in forecasting profit and determining the variability around their values. Based on irrelevance conditions, Stulz (1984) rationalised the need for risk management in firms (Oldfield and Santomero (1997).

Santomero (1995) presents different reasons for adopting risk management in his book “Financial Risk Management: The Whys and Hows. Main reasons for risk management in firms are capital market imperfections, tax impacts, cost of financial stress and securing internal financing meaning managers of a firm have limited resources that in turn affect their capability to diversify investment because of limited capital. It promotes aversion to risk and a priority for robustness in businesses”.

Oldfield and Santomero (1997) advocate above stances and point out that anyone of the above-discussed points is enough to require management to be concerned with risks and motivate them to develop and demonstrate risk management policies to manage risks associated with financial products. Effective risk management is a value-boosting strategy and its goal is to maximise shareholder’s value.

2.4.3 Institutional Theory

According to the institutional theory, economic outcome is a complex set of various interrelated variables such as social norms, individuals, state and the organization. This theory views power relationships among these variables as a source of illustrating institutional and organizational phenomenon (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). According to Greenwood et al (2012), institutional theory aims at comprehending the organizational and institutional outcomes by macroeconomic integration of society, firm and the state. In the context of risk management in banking; institutional theory views risk decisions as an occurrence that is undertaken by macro variables including technology, competition and regulation. Risk process simply tends to be an avenue in which complex individual motivations and actions legitimize risk decisions. Therefore, human behaviour, motivation and reckoning are not straightforward actions and are not easily comprehended and explained in an institutional context.

By contrast, this theory has been criticized for not defining the responsibility of humans in determining economic and institutional decisions because risk managers specifically in banking sector play a central role in accepting or rejecting a particular loan. Therefore, an

agent's role in modern financial markets cannot be overlooked. However, new institutional theory has been proposed by various researchers (Cruz et al, 2009; Lawrence et al, 2002 and Sahlim, 1996) to define the role of humans in the institutional context.

Cruz et al (2009) propose a new institutional theory that emphasizes the need for agents in developing the social environment of the organization and shaping the institutional outcome. Thus, risk decisions in banking institutions are explained on the basis of a combination of agents (processes and human interactions) and organizational structures. Lawrence et al (2002) reinforce new institutional theory and argue that an organization can be developed by establishing and implementing new policies, procedures, systems and interaction among them. Sahlim (1996) advocates new institutional theory and development of institutions occurs when old dated policies and systems are changed, substituted and adjusted over time to meet the current organizational needs and old practices appear in the form of modern practices with adequate organizational value.

2.4.4 Agency theory

In an attempt to present a theoretical rationalization for risk management in firms; different commentators have undertaken agency theory in their research to offer an academic base. Agency theory explains the social phenomenon in the context of a principal-agent relationship (Fatemi and Luft, 2002). Agency theory explains that an organisation is represented by two parties; principals (owners and shareholders) and agents (directors and management). According to the agency theory, managers as agents do not discharge their duties in the interest of their owners and instead attempt to pursue their vested interests (Watts and Zimmerman, 1983).

Jensen and Meckling (1976) support above arguments and illustrate that agency theory is an agreement under which principals (owners) engage agents (directors and managers) to run businesses on their behalf and this gives them authority to make decisions in the best interest of their principals. In the context of risk management in banks, agency theory assumes that risk manager does not watch the interest of the customers (depositors). In addition, risk managers make and transact decisions to pursue their interests by using clients' information available to them not because of higher returns than investment but an expectation of higher remuneration inducing them to overlook investment opportunities. Agency theory requires managers a duty of prudence and integrity they owe to their shareholders and customers (Chua, 1986).

Smith et al (1985) used agency theory in business risk management and evaluated the attitude of risk managers towards risk-taking and hedging. Additionally, Tufano (1998) rationalised risk management in banks on the basis of this theory and points out that risk managers use hedging techniques without looking at the interests of shareholders. The main rationale for the attitude is the variation between risk aversion of shareholders and managers. As managers have more knowledge about the company's affairs and risk exposures than shareholders; this makes the risk aversion of managers highly sophisticated than risk aversion of shareholders. On the contrary, proponents of agency theory claim that risk management increases agency problems along with agency cost and wealth of shareholders tend to be transferred to managers because of widespread hedging and introducing unfavourable risk practices (Tufano, 1998).

2.4.5 Theory used in this research: justification for using institutional theory

After reviewing the above four theories in detail; institutional theory has been used in this research to provide a justification for risk management in the London banks. Reason for using institutional theory is that it mainly concentrates on regulations, policies and guidelines which are enforced by regulatory bodies and governments on the institutions and require them to comply with those rules and regulations (DiMaggio and Powell 1983; Scott 1995). Several research studies on risk management have used institutional theory in order to elucidate the phenomenon of risk management in banks for instance Collier and Woods (2011) & Hudin and Hamid (2014). Both researchers believe that institutionalisation prevails when risk management activities undertaken by banks become largely homogeneous.

This homogeneity is achieved by the coercive isomorphic mechanism through which legal and regulatory pressures are exerted on the firms in the form of persuasion, invitation and direction. For example, in the context of the UK banks particularly HSBC and LLOYDS, all banks operating in the UK are directed by the Bank of England to build up and execute a sound risk management system. Bearing into mind the homogeneity supposition of institutional theory, the basic principles of risk management are applied to all banking institutions no matter what their size, nature and complexity of banking operations are.

In the following section; background to financial crises of 2007-2008 and risk management is discussed briefly;

2.5 Background to the financial meltdown and risk management

The current financial meltdown has an extensive impact on the global financial system and has caused many commentators to compare this financial catastrophe with the Great Depression of the 1920s with dire economic consequences. According to Turner (2009), the calculated cost of this crisis was undoubtedly into trillions of dollars that shattered the whole global financial system specifically the banking industry.

According to Walker (2009) and COP (2009), socio-technical challenges are the main reasons of financial crisis such as inadequate risk appetite frameworks, managerial risk perceptions, inappropriate risk culture and governance structures and inflexible corporate structures that hinder risk management and risk reporting. Also besides, the US Congressional Oversight Panel (COP 2009) pinpoints failures in risk management by regulators and firms as key reasons for the current financial meltdown.

Likewise, the House of Commons Treasury Committee of the UK Parliament stressed that banks adopted complex banking systems and overlooked time-honoured principles of prudent lending that eroded their ability to manage their funding needs efficiently. This committee concluded dire weaknesses in structures, models and procedures for risk management in banks. Market forces, greedy senior management and executive directors and insufficient market discipline are the main reasons for failures in risk management as they turn blind eye to excessive risk-taking (Walker, 2009 and Turner, 2009).

The financial meltdown made global regulators, financial institutions and governments to seek out the reasons why the financial crisis occurred specifically when macroeconomic volatility was perceived to be overcome in developed countries. Moreover, in developed countries, sophisticated systems of risk management and financial regulation were adopted by firms and the risk of the financial crisis was considered to be minimal.

From the above discussion, it is highly recommended that the banking institutions may modernize the risk management regimes within the context of their risk appetite and promote a robust risk culture. It should be embedded in their corporate strategy. Banks through adopting various risk management frameworks can manage their risks efficiently and ultimately aid them in absorbing financial shocks at the time of the financial stress.

The next section explains the effect of the financial meltdown on the UK banks.

2.6 Impact of the economic meltdown on the UK banks

Recent financial meltdown changed the economic and commercial landscape of UK firms particularly the UK banking sector suffered a lot. As with other markets in different

countries; the financial crisis also brought unfavourable consequences for UK firms. The productivity of firms in the UK fell sharply as a result of the financial meltdown of 2007-08 and banking performance also affected due to the global crisis (NIESR, 2017).

Big banks in the UK were adversely affected due to the huge financial blow. Royal Bank of Scotland was nationalised in late 2008 and took its 58% stake and in 2009 its ownership rose to 84% because RBS was struggling due to cash flow problems. Moreover, Bingley Building Society and Bradford bank in the UK were nationalised in the same year in 2008 and ultimately was sold to Spanish Grupo Santander Bank.

Halifax Bank of Scotland (HBOS) was the largest mortgage lender in the UK and was in dire financial trouble and ultimately the UK government took a 45% stake in combined HBOS and LLOYDS TSB. Though HSBC and Barclays were not nationalised, Bank of England (BoE) required both banks to preserve their capital ratio through raising capital by issuing shares (Press Association, 2012).

Above discussion summarises that the current financial meltdown and the collapse of big banks in the UK including RBS, HBOS, Barings and Northern rock, Societe Generale in France, and Iceland banking industry have hit UK economy specifically its banking sector. Above discussion not only highlights failure in risk management but also inadequate risk culture in the UK banks. Moreover, it has been argued by commentators that since the beginning of a recession, customer trust in the banking sector is low since then with extensive banking scandal exposing corruption and mismanagement in the UK banks.

The following section underlines the description of how the UK banks deal with risks with a particular focus on the commercial banks

2.7 How do the UK banks deal with risks?

Over a period of time, risk management in the UK banks has transformed in the wake of the current economic crisis. A wave of change in risk functions of banks has been triggered because of the economic meltdown and fines levied on the banks due to their failures in risk management. These transformations include detailed and increased capital, funding, liquidity and high leverage requirements and increased requirements for robust risk reporting (Mckinsey, 2017).

Banks functioning in the UK are required to adopt a sound system of risk management underpinned by the board and its committees. According to the British Business Bank (2017), the board is overall answerable and accountable for risk management in the banks and banks need to establish a risk management framework that aligns with the size, complexity and

scale of banks. The board gives authority to the chief financial officer, chief risk officer and CEO for maintaining an internal control system and risk management in the banks. The soundness of risk management depends on clear responsibilities, adequate risk management policies, strong risk culture, robust corporate governance, and computer-based training. Financial Conduct Authority is a regulator for financial markets and financial institutions in the UK that is mandated to ensure consumer protection from market failures, maintain market integrity and to ensure competition in the markets. These initiatives are taken in response to the recent banking crisis and technology-led financial innovation. FCA requires all banks operating in the UK to comply with its guidelines and recommendations to enhance consumer confidence and encourage competition (Chiu, 2015).

Credit default swaps (CDS) are widely used financial instruments by banks to transfer risks (Greenspan, 2004). CDS contracts enable banks to transfer the credit risk from protection buyers to protection sellers and these financial innovations aid financial institutions to manage their risk portfolios. Parlour and Winton (2013) and Duffee and Zhou (2001) are in favour of using credit default swaps and rationalise that the financial derivatives assist banks in hedging risks of high-quality borrowers and are appropriate to use when monitoring costs are low. Furthermore, Allen and Carletti (2006) support the above arguments and claim that banks can use financial derivatives when they are exposed to liquidity and capital constraints. On the contrary, many commentators regard CDS as weapons of mass destruction. Following the recent financial meltdown, use of CDS is considered to be the main reasons for the collapse of JPMorgan Chase and insurance giant American International Group (Buffet, 2002). Risk management framework used by Islamic banks in Brunei Darussalam has been investigated by Hassan (2009) and it concluded that operational, foreign exchange and credit risks were the main risks encountered by Islamic banks. Hassan (2009) used a survey questionnaire technique to get a feel of how banks in Brunei Darussalam understand, analyse, monitor and manage risks. On the other hand, Al-Tamimi (2007) draws a comparison between risk management adopted by national and foreign banks of UAE and concludes that credit and foreign exchange risks are key risks encountered by UAE banks and UAE banks are in a position to manage these risks efficiently.

From the foregoing discussion, it is evident that banks operating in different countries face various risks and extent of their impact on banking performance depends on the nature, structure and complexity of banking operations, local regulations and banking standards enforced by individual countries. Therefore, the above discussion emphasises the need for

robust risk management system required of banks to manage risks they face. Next section provides case studies underpinning the reasons of failure of banks:

2.8 Failure of banks (case studies)

Banks are financial intermediaries that play a leading role in boosting the world economy. They adopt two ways of making money. Firstly: they take deposits from the public and lend it back in the form of loans and earn interest income from loans. Secondly, banks facilitate financial transactions and sell financial products and services for which they charge brokerage fee (as brokers). As loans are a typically illiquid source of funds for banks that expose them to various liquidity challenges. This solvency risk makes depositors and creditors realise that banks' assets are falling in value and they start withdrawing money from banks simultaneously thus deteriorating the banks' liquidity position (Nolt, 2016). Following case studies reflect the reasons why banks fail in light of the above discussion.

However, according to the Comptroller of the Currency Administrator of National Banks (1988), banks can recover from the challenges they face by taking various key steps. These steps include changes in management, improving economic conditions, overhauling current risk management practices, reviewing banking philosophy and ultimately holding enough buffer capital may assist banks to stay healthy to absorb financial shocks.

2.8.1 Northern Rock

Northern Rock was one of the biggest mortgage providers in the UK that was offering finance to households. In 1990, it was the first finance lender in the UK that adopted securitisations; a process by which mortgages are pooled as bonds and subsequently sold to investors in the stock markets (The Telegraph, 2007). In August 2007, the UK experienced its first bank run in 140 years that was Northern Rock and because of fear of a systematic run on bank deposits; Northern rock was nationalised by the UK government.

The Bank of England (BoE) issued early warnings that might hit adversely going concern status of Northern Rock. These warnings included sharp asset growth, emerging trends in markets, systemic under-pricing of risk and more specifically financial derivatives responsible for risk-shifting including credit default swaps and collateralised debt obligations were not as watertight as it might be. Furthermore, the Bank of England highlighted the following weaknesses in the risk management regime and strategic decision making of the bank:

- Failure of risk management in identifying and managing liquidity risks
- No established bankruptcy system for bank

- An underlying problem in a deposit protection scheme
- Lack of a robust internal control system to highlight deficiencies in corporate governance
- Fundamental flaws in the UK's institutional arrangements for handling stressed banks (Bruni and Llewellyn, 2009)

2.8.2 Barings Bank

Barings bank before its collapse in 1995 was the oldest merchant bank in the UK. This bank was collapsed by a single-handedly rogue employee named Nick Leeson who was a derivatives trader. Nick Leeson was appointed as derivatives operation manager in Baring Securities Singapore and after one year in 1993, he was promoted to general manager and assistant director of Baring Futures Singapore (BFS). In a short period of time, he not only took the charge of the front office of BFS but also took over the back office that was processing paperwork. This unauthorized access simultaneously to both offices enabled him to undertake unauthorized futures trading and hide losses using an 88888 account.

Not only this, but he also started dealing in Japanese government bonds in 1994 and dabbled in Nikkei 225 futures and options. As a result of internal audit of BFS, the estimated loss of Baring bank due to unauthorised trading by Nick Leeson was \$373.9 million by the end of December 1994 (National library board Singapore, 2018).

The above two case studies conclude that the failure of risk management and weaknesses in corporate governance are key reasons for their collapses. Banks within the context of financial meltdown and collapse of other banks including Societe Generale, RBS, Iceland banking industry and other banks across the globe can ensure their survival by establishing a robust risk management system and appropriate supervision by regulators and central banks as lenders of last resort in individual countries.

2.9 Effect of risk management on banking performance

Economic crisis management across the globe has recognized the reality that effective risk management frameworks are indispensable for organisations that tend to enhance shareholder and customer patronage. The collapse of big firms across the world including Enron, WorldCom, Barongs, Tyco, Dawa bank debacle, and recently injected fund by the Governor Central Bank of Nigeria Sanusi Lamido into the Nigerian banking industry to protect the economy and ailing banks; it is argued the effectiveness of risk management in banks cannot be compromised at any cost (Olamide et al. 2014).

Risk management has a central role in the current financial world and has gained significant importance in recent times in the light of the financial downturn of 2007-08 and major corporate collapses. It is a major driving force behind enhancing the market value of firms and increasing consumer confidence in banks. Investors tend to invest in those firms that establish a stringent risk management system. Risk management plays a leading part in protecting the interests of shareholders and other stakeholders and safeguarding the assets of banks. A robust risk management system brings following advantages for banks (1) it increases profitability and efficiency of banks (2) by improving the reputation of being more resilient to risks; banks enjoy the chance to pull more clients thereby enhancing their portfolio of funding means (3) enhanced compliance with regulatory and statutory requirements increases capital market confidence into banks (Oluwafemi et al. 2013).

Furthermore, banks that incorporate highly developed techniques in their risk management framework have better access to different sources of credit thus increasing their profits as well as productivity (Cebenoyan and Strahan, 2004). Stulz (1996) supports the above arguments and argues that risk management assists banks in not only reducing taxes but also minimising insolvency costs. Advanced techniques used in risk management regimes have helped banks in the USA to reduce profit variations and achieve higher returns. Essinger and Rosen (1991) further add to the above discussion and point out that risk management is an effective tool in optimising returns in unfavourable circumstances and reducing adverse effects of risks banks encounter.

Tandelilin (2007) determined the association between bank performance, risk management and corporate governance in the Indonesian banking industry. This study primarily emphasises the need for optimising the understanding of the corporate governance adopted in Indonesian banks and seeks the ways that are used by banks in implementing effective corporate governance aligned with the banks' performance. This research concludes a robust bond between risk management and banking performance of Indonesian banks.

Similarly, the relationship between bank performance and risk management in banks of Nigeria has been explored by Oluwafemi et al. (2013). This work summarises a considerable affiliation between risk management and banking performance. However, the cost of doubtful and bad loans has an inverse relationship with the financial achievement of Nigerian banks. Return on assets and return on equity have been used in this research to measure the financial achievement of banks and capital to asset ratio tends to have a positive momentous relationship with banking performance.

Pastor (1999) has evaluated the effectiveness of Spanish banks with respect to credit risk. He divided credit loan amount into two parts: external (changing environment) and internal (managerial control). Loan losses were used to measure credit risk in banks. Pastor (1999) concludes that the effectiveness of risk management in Spanish banks has improved considerably over a period of 1985-92. He further argues that the single market program of the European Community has introduced deregulation that has a negative impact on banking risks.

From the foregoing discussion, it is summarised that risk management plays a key part in enhancing the financial resilience of banks when exposed to economic stress. It helps banks in identifying, assessing, evaluating and managing risks by applying guidance and principles introduced by an integrated risk management system.

In the subsequent parts, the affiliation between risk management and capital adequacy of banks is illustrated in detail with a particular focus on Basel accords.

2.10 Capital adequacy and risk management

It is an established fact that the recent global financial meltdown and big corporate giants have required banks to maintain enough (buffer) capital in order to maintain their going concern status and sustain the smooth running of their business operations. Large waves of failures striking banking industry in the USA, UK, Germany, France, China and other countries had significantly raised importance and apprehension about holding an extreme risk-taking behaviour by USA banks at a time when similar banking institutions seem as overly risk averse (Chakroun and Abid, 2016).

This concern emanates because market and credit risks tend to proliferate instantly with funding resources dissipating that further the concerns capital adequacy realisation and asset valuation. These issues emphasise the need for demonstrating a specific relationship between capital adequacy of banks and risk management involving the questions of how much capital banks is required to absorb financial shocks (Chakroun and Abid, 2016).

However, there are two underlying questions that are faced by banks: first is the determination of how much capital is required for banks to cover their level of risk-taking and other is the extent of supervision and regulation that influence risk management and capital adequacy of banks. For example, regulatory capital has an impact on banks' lending balance sheet activities (Leland, 1994).

Berger et al. (1995) explain reasons for why markets require banks to hold capital and encourage banks to maintain capital ratios in the absence of regulatory needs. According to

Berger et al, (1995), market capital requirement of banks is the ratio that facilitates banks in optimising the value of banks in the absence of regulatory capital needs. However, in the presence of regulatory structure, it safeguards the soundness and safety of banks from financial stress and helps them in honouring their financial commitments when due to be repaid.

Basel accords were introduced by the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS) that helped banks in resolving the above-discussed issues faced by banks in the light of economic debacles and corporate collapses. In addition, Basel accords have also improved prudential regulation of the banking industry and have introduced capital ratios that require banks to hold buffer capital to enhance their financial resilience. These accords seek to maximise banking industry ability in improving risk management, strengthening banks' transparency, and ultimately managing economic and financial pressures.

Basel accords are discussed briefly in the following sections along with their applications and limitations:

2.10.1 Basel Accords

The most important role of capital with regards to the banking industry is to function as a buffer to absorb financial shocks and to protect depositors from potential losses whereby mounting the trust of rating agencies and shareholders in the banking sector. Furthermore, buffer capital is the minimum level of capital required of banks to hold in accordance with the rules established by prudential regulators and the goal of maintaining capital is to guarantee the viability and stability of the banking organization (Ciurlau, L., 2016).

In response to maximising profits through extensive use of own funds and exposure to risks; supervisory authorities impose certain restrictions on banking institutions in the form of prudential rules facilitating the suitability of the share capital of banks. In this regard in 1988, an agreement of the Basel Convention was drawn by the Committee under the name of COOKE Committee that incorporates the recommendations of the Bank for International Settlements in relation to the adequacy of capital (Ciurlau, L., 2016).

The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision is the principal international standard setter that provides prudential regulation of financial institutions and the insurance industry. It offers a platform for mutual collaboration and regular understanding of supervisory matters relating to banking institutions. This committee is composed of 45 members comprising bank supervisors and central banks from 28 jurisdictions (BIS, 2018).

There are three Basel accords that are introduced by the BCBS and are discussed in the following sections:

2.10.2 Basel I

2.10.3 Basel II

2.10.4 Basel III

2.10.2 Basel I

It was introduced in December 1987 and it primarily deals with the credit risk by defining the capital requirements of banks as a function of banks' on and off-balance sheet positions.

There are two underlying goals of this Basel:

- To reinforce the viability, stability and financial resilience of banks
- To eliminate the current sources of aggressive disparity among global banks (Balthazar, 2006).

The main principle of Basel 1 is to allocate to both on and off-balance sheet things a weight that is a function of their estimated risk level. In addition, it calls for banks to maintain capital equivalent to 8% of risk weighted assets (Jorion and Khoury, 1996). Basel committee defined two types of capital with regards to the function of its quality: Tier 1 & Tier 2.

Tier 1 capital consists of paid-up capital and disclosed reserves comprising of retained earnings and legal reserves. Whereas, Tier 2 capital is composed of asset revaluation reserves, hybrid instruments, and undisclosed reserves. Therefore, total banking capital is a sum of Tier 1 capital and Tier 2 capital after deducting tier 1 goodwill and investments in unconsolidated subsidiaries (Balthazar, 2006).

Tier 2 capital is restricted to 100 % of tier 1 capital and goodwill is deducted from tier 1 capital because it is invariably considered as an item whose valuation is subjective, fluctuating and is very likely that it reflects the small value in case of insolvency of a business.

Furthermore, the Basel Committee has recognised five factors (risk-weighted assets) which give weightings to the balance sheet figures of banks to mirror their risk level. Zero percent weighting is assigned to balance sheet items such as cash, claims on central governments of OECD countries. Twenty percent weighting is attributed to claims on multilateral development banks, OECD public sector institutions and banks. Twenty percent weighting is

also applied to other entities outside OECD if their residual maturity is less than one year. On the contrary, fifty percent weighting is assigned to mortgage loans whereas one hundred percent weighting is associated with corporate claims, fixed assets and claims on banks outside OECD with a maturity of more than one year (Balthazar, 2006).

In the beginning, Basel 1 was functional in globally active banks operated in a group of ten countries. Sooner, it became an established standard which highlighted solvency of banks and subsequently was supposed to be applied in more than hundred countries (KPMG, 2007).

Regulatory deficiencies

Since the introduction of Basel 1 in December 1987, significant changes have taken place in the world financial system. A considerable amount of innovation has occurred that has made financial markets more volatile and exposed to various interrelated risks. The recent financial crisis of 2007-08 and recent advancements in technology, risk management and banking institutions, globalisation and complex financial products and services have made Basel 1 less meaningful as it focuses only on credit risk. It does not consider counterparty risks and fails to distinguish between degrees of creditworthiness among borrowers (KPMG, 2007).

Research on credit risk management since 1990 has revolutionised the way banks manage risks. Quantification models have facilitated banks to create a precise and reliable estimate of their in-house economic capital requirements. In contrast to regulatory capital, the economic capital is required by regulators and supports banks' risk-taking activities and is determined by the bank (Balthazar, 2006).

2.10.3 Basel II

The Basel II that replaced the 1988 Basel 1 framework was launched in June 2004. It is the outcome of more than six years of the effort of regulators and vigorous dialogue with banking industry leaders. The explicit purpose of regulatory bodies was to make sure that the international level of capital held by banks remained approximate to the current level by taking into account their respective risk levels (Balthazar, 2006). Since 2007, the new capital adequacy directive was applied to all firms, with the highly developed techniques being practicable from 2008. However, in the USA, Basel II was applied to a few numbers of big firms while some other banking firms were subject to a new edition of Basel I.

Basel II has required banks to hold minimum capital requirements and it grants incentives to use sophisticated risk-sensitive techniques of the improved model. It incorporates supervisory review and market discipline and combines them with minimum capital requirements to promote improvements in risk management. Besides this, this Basel deals with all risks which

were not previously dealt with Basel 1. These include concentration risk, country risk, reputational risk, and legal risk. Basel II makes changes from transaction based supervision to risk based supervision (KPMG, 2007).

There are three main objectives of this Basel:

- To maximise the stability and quality of the global banking structure
- To promote the acceptance of rigorous risk management guidelines
- To provide and retain a level playing field for internationally vigorous banks (Balthazar, 2006).

Basel II opened a new era of mutual cooperation between internationally active banks and it ensured the harmonisation of standards, practices of capital adequacy and surveillance activities of global banking (Ciurlau, 2016).

Structure of Basel II

Basel II is structured into three main pillars that underpin the global objectives of sound risk management practices and financial stability. Key characteristics of each pillar are highlighted in the following sections:

Table 2.1

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure is the three pillars of Basel II. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

(Balthazar, 2006).

Pillar 1

Capital Requirements

Risk-weighted assets (RWAs) are considered as a key control ratio because capital is the principal buffer against losses when profits are volatile and become negative. Capital requirements are closely aligned with the internal economic capital estimates; internal models adopted by banks aid them in estimating their capital needs concerning their risk-weighted assets.

According to Pillar1, minimum capital requirements (capital adequacy ratio) required of banks are equal to 8 % of risk-weighted assets whereas risk weighted assets are based on the market, credit and operational risks (Danila, 2012).

Minimum capital requirements = 8% * risk-weighted assets (RWAs consist of operational risk, market risk & credit risk). However, the following formula is used by banks to estimate their capital requirements:

Capital adequacy ratio = total capital/ sum of operational risk, market risk & credit risk

Basel Committee on Banking Supervision has anticipated numerous options to evaluate the market risk, operational risk and credit risk (BIS, 2006):

1. Credit risk approaches

- Standardised Approach
- Advanced Internal Rating Approach (A-IRB)
- Internal Rating Approach (IRB)

2. Operational risk approaches

- Basic Indicator Approach
- Advanced Measurement Approach
- Standardised Approach

3. Market risk approaches

- Basic Indicator Approach
- Standardised Approach
- Advanced Measurement Approach

1. Credit risk approaches

Standardised Approach:

In this model, different risk weights determined by worldwide rating agencies like Moody are assigned to different kinds of companies, banks, governments, central banks, and central or local public sector organisations.

Internal Rating Approach (IRB):

According to IRB, certain standards are set by regulators and supervisory authorities that assist banks in identifying additional risk factors including Exposure at Default (EAD) and Loss given default (LGD). Banks undertake their predictions on the probability of default (PD) relating to every customer. Banks are required to comply with standards set by regulators.

Advanced Internal Rating Approach (A-IRB):

This approach applies to banks that tend to estimate their risk exposures internally and those banks that wish to adhere to strict standards set by supervisory authorities. Credit derivatives and collateral quality methods are employed to manage credit risks.

Smaller banks are using a standardised approach due to its compatibility with Basel 1. However, more banks are using IRB and AIRB underpinning a more rigorous risk assessment.

2. Operational Risk Approaches

Basic indicator approach

In this approach, a basic indicator for example revenue is selected and specific % is applied to this indicator that is determined by supervisory authorities.

Standardised Approach

Business activity of banks is separated into various business sections; for each section, an underlying indicator is selected with a specific % determined by regulators is allocated.

Advanced measurement approach

Internal risk prediction models validated by supervisory authorities are used to manage operational risks. However, with regards to operational risk measurement banks may face challenges in developing a reliable and complete database necessary to deal with operational losses incurred in each business segment.

Market risk approach

In this approach, models validated by the Basel 1996 amendment are used to manage market risk. Most frequently used models are value at Risk (VAR) and standardised approach based on supervisory standards (Danila, 2012).

In all above discussed approaches; required capital is equal to 8% of risk-weighted requirements concerning operational, market and credit risks:

Table 2.2

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table is of market risk approaches. Please contact the thesis author for further information.

(Balthazar, 2006)

Pillar 2

Supervisory review and internal assessment

Pillar 2 requires banks to establish a stringent internal control system and supervisory review to determine their capital needs along with the regulatory framework and integrate the risk profile of banks accordingly. It also requires banks to integrate all risks whether fully or partially covered by Basel II including credit risk, strategic risk, interest rate risk and reputation risk in the banking book.

In this pillar, regulatory bodies regularly review that capital needs of pillar 1 are appreciated and assess the soundness of internal control systems developed by banks. If banks do not hold buffer capital to absorb financial shocks, regulators require them to increase their capital base and restrict the novel credits that are approved. It requires banks to function under capital greater than 8% because pillar 2 captures additional risks that are not covered in Basel 1 and Basel II (Balthazar, 2006).

Pillar 3

Market discipline

This pillar concerns market discipline and appropriate and timely disclosures to market participants. Banking institutions are asked to prepare reports on the robustness of their internal control and risk management systems and shed light on how the Basel II is implemented and overseen. Reports need to be publically disclosed at least twice a year. Main elements that need to be disclosed in the reports are risk management policies and objectives, collateral management policies, risk grading, and internal loss experiences (Balthazar, 2006).

Limitations of Basel II

The recognition of double default: this means that banks have to incur double default if they lose money and it is a sign of protection against counterparty risks. Basel II fails to recognise double default and thus it provides fragile incentives for financial firms to hedge their risks from a perspective of regulatory capital utilization. The definition of eligible capital: capital required of banks to hold is still defined under 1988 Basel 1 accord but further work is expected to be undertaken to define Tier 1 capital.

The scaling factor: as the most important purpose of Basel II is to maintain global level of capital in the banking industry, therefore, regulators are facing challenges in scaling factor of capital requirements which are based on the unforeseen loss fraction of a credit portfolio. Current scaling used by regulators for comparison is 1.06. Accounting issues are other challenges that are faced by regulators because of distortion emanating from the adoption of the same rules and recommendations under different accounting regimes. However, this issue is worth resolving as the global trend is towards international standardization by applying International Accounting Standards (IAS).

Bearing in mind all considerations and relevant challenges raised in Basel 1 and Basel II; Basel Committee on Banking Supervision introduced Basel III that is currently adopted by banks and is helping them in enhancing their financial resilience (Balthazar, 2006).

2.10.4 Basel III

This Basel is a globally established set of guidelines and instruments introduced by the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision in reaction to the financial meltdown of 2008. These are minimum requirements that are applied to all globally dynamic banks. Furthermore, all members are required to implement and apply provisions contained in Basel III in their countries within the established time frame.

Its main objectives are:

- To make stronger the administration, regulation and risk management of financial institutions (BIS, 2018)
- To make stronger the global equity and capital rules with the aim to develop a more durable banking industry
- To enhance the ability of banks to absorb financial shocks emanating from the economic and financial meltdown

- To decrease systemic risk by minimising the risk of spill over from the financial industry to real economy (BCBS, 2017).

In an attempt to address the market failures revealed as a result of the financial meltdown, Basel III has introduced underlying reforms to the global regulatory structure. These reforms make stronger micro prudential and bank level regulation which assists individual banking institutions to increase their financial resilience. Moreover, having a macro prudential approach; these recommendations deal with system wide risks building across the banking sector and address the procyclical amplification of risks over time.

Under Basel III, BCBS has introduced the following reforms to deal with capital requirements of banks and ensure the financial resilience of banking institutions:

- It is optimising the financial resilience of the banking industry by underpinning the regulatory capital structure that is based on three pillars of Basel II. These reforms enhance the quantity and quality of the capital base and boost the risk exposure of banks underpinned by a leverage ratio serving as a backstop to risk based measures.
- It increases transparency, consistency and the quality of the capital base.
- In response to these deficiencies, BCBS brought about changes to Basel II in 2009 and therefore, raised capital requirements for complex securitisation and trading book exposures; underlying sources of capital losses for banks. In addition, BCBS introduced a stressed value-at-risk (VaR) capital requirements based for 12 months of financial stress.
- In an attempt to counter systemic risk emanating from the interconnectedness of banks and other financial firms by derivative markets; BCBS has introduced reforms for financial market infrastructures and central counterparties.
- Banks are exposed to a capital charge in case of mark to market losses connected with worsening in the creditworthiness of counterparties.
- Committee has emphasised the importance of strengthening the measures for initial margining and collateral management. To determine the regulatory capital needs, banks need to apply longer margining periods if banks are exposed to illiquid and large derivative exposures to the counterparty (BCBS, 2017).

Detailed analysis of Basel accords has made it evident that a resilient and strong banking system is central in maintaining the sustained economic growth because banks act as intermediaries between investors and savers. Banks are exposed to various interrelated risks discussed above due to different factors including globalisation, financial innovation,

technology and complexity of structured products and services. Banks can enhance their financial resilience and absorb financial shocks by implementing relevant recommendations introduced under Basel accords and ensure their effectiveness.

2.11 Risk management guidelines

In the following sections, risk management guidelines underpinning key aspects of risk management are discussed.

2.11.1 Risk management guidelines introduced by the Bank of England

2.11.2 Risk management guidelines recommended by OECD

2.11.3 Risk management guidelines issued by IMF

2.11.1 Risk management guidelines introduced by the Bank of England (BoE)

As the Bank of England acts as a lender of last resort and is a fundamental regulator regulating activities of banking organisations in the UK and plays a crucial role in balancing and managing the UK economy. Its role in the UK is diversified and it issues guidelines covering all firms in the UK therefore it is not possible to discuss all risk management guidelines introduced by the BoE. Thus, to answer the research questions of this study, only fundamental guidelines introduced by the BoE underpinning risk management in the UK banks are discussed:

The BoE has issued the Capital Requirements Directive (CRD 1V) that is responsible for implementing Basel III and ensuring its effectiveness in the UK banks. The BoE under CRD 1V require UK banks:

- To maintain buffer capital to absorb financial shocks and to put in place appropriate risk controls
- To enhance the quantity and quality of capital
- To establish appropriate policies for leverage and liquidity requirements
- To implement and supervise the application of standards covering capital buffers and a countercyclical capital buffer for banking institutions

Furthermore, CRD 1V has made changes in corporate governance in banks including remuneration and has introduced standardised EU regulatory reporting such as FINREP and

COREP. These reporting guidelines require UK banks to report specified information relating to financial information, large exposures and their funds (Bank of England, 2018).

The Prudential Regulatory Authority (PRA) is answerable for prudential regulation of investment firms, building societies, banks and insurance industries in the UK and BoE requires all banks in the UK to provide regulatory returns to PRA from 1 December 2017.

Stress testing is one of the most important and underlying measures introduced by the Bank of England that has addressed the capital adequacy requirements in case of financial stress and deficiencies in risk management in banks.

In response to the economic meltdown of 2007-08 and big corporate collapses that deteriorated the global economic system and undermined consumers trust in the banking system; the BoE has introduced stress testing requiring banks and insurers to determine their capital adequacy. Stress testing assists banks in assessing their financial resilience and making sure that banks have buffer capital to withstand financial difficulties and to support the economy if stress testing materialises.

There are two main kinds of stress testing introduced by BoE:

BoE runs an annual stress test of the biggest banks and building societies in the UK. Results interpreted by the Prudential Regulation Authority (PRA) and the Financial Policy Committee of BoE help the management of banks in determining their capital adequacy and identifying loopholes in risk management and subsequently recommend corrective actions to rectify any deficiencies.

Banks not part of the annual stress test are required to run their own stress testing. For the convenience of banks; a scenario is published every six months by the PRA that helps banks to build their scenarios to ensure they have adequate planned capital to remain solvent (Bank of England, 2018).

The PRA has recommended the following measures for effective risk management framework and stress testing:

- Banks need to establish and implement robust governance frameworks, procedures, policies and controls underpinning risk management to manage their model risk.
- Banks must undertake independent review activities and appropriate model validation for better understanding of model uncertainties and ensure robust banking performance.
- Banks have a sound knowledge of risk management models used and ensure adequate resources for effective implementation.

- Banks have potential and capability to use models appropriately and take steps for further improvement and development in risk management models including stress testing and Basel accords (Bank of England; Prudential Regulation Authority, 2017).

2.11.2 Risk management guidelines recommended by OECD

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) founded in 1961 is an intergovernmental organisation with 37 member countries which aims to address common problems of member countries, compare policy experiences, coordinate global and domestic policies and identify good practices of member states aiming to strengthen democracy and market economy. OECD provides guidance and best practice guidelines on different areas including risk management, corporate governance, development, economy, corruption, education, health, public governance, employment and so on. The following sections shed the spotlight on key recommendations of OECD on risk management to get a feel of what are the best practice guidelines on risk management that can be used by the UK banks to deal with risk exposures. Following guidelines underpinning corporate risk management and corporate governance framework are recommended by OECD on the basis of OECD's sixth peer review conducted in three countries including Switzerland, Singapore and Norway.

Big corporate collapses and recent financial meltdown have created a sense of realisation in companies paying additional attention to risk management. However, it rarely resulted in transformations to prescribed measures apart from the economic sector and businesses that have experienced deficiencies in their risk management in recent times. Many firms consider that line managers are responsible for risk management.

Underneath are the principal guidelines of OECD on risk management that need to be followed by companies in their jurisdictions:

General perspective

Risk management is not about a mere reducing risk-taking; rather, it is an essential driving factor in entrepreneurship and business. Both financial and non-financial firms need to strengthen their risk management function after careful consideration of risks they encounter and their capability to deal with those risks. According to Mckinsey report in 2011, the board must regularly endorse and re-evaluate risk management strategies and spend enough time on business risk management and enhance their understanding of risks businesses come across.

Risk management standards and codes

OECD requires banks and other institutions to comply with internally established standards and codes underpinning risk management to guarantee effective corporate governance and risk management. For example, the UK's combined code, New York Stock Exchange listing rules (NYSE) and the French AFEP-MEDEF code. In 2004, the Committee of Sponsoring Organisations of the Treadway Commission (COSO) introduced an enterprise-wide risk management system that helps firms in taking an overall view of their businesses when deciding risk management strategy. Furthermore, in 2009, the International Organisation for Standardisation introduced its process-oriented standard "ISO 31000" that provides guidance and generic principles on risk management that leads to achieving convergence from various methodologies, procedures and standards that differ between countries, subject matters and industries.

Risk appetite and incentives

Boards are responsible for establishing risk appetite and risk tolerance of a company. Boards need to set risk targets, identify and assess various types of risks businesses are exposed to and ultimately aggregate all risk into one number after applying various models bearing in mind the risk appetite of firms. OECD further requires the boards to extend their process of defining risk strategy and risk appetite for establishing and supervising enterprise-wide risk management systems. There should be compatibility between risk strategy, risk appetite and risk management (OECD, 2014).

Chief Risk Officer (CRO)

In many countries, listing rules require listed companies to appoint a chief risk officer responsible for establishing and supervising the effectiveness of risk management and internal control functions for example in Singapore, India and Argentina. In the large corporations and financial industry, risk management function tends to be separated from profit centres and CRO reports directly to the board of directors and to non-executive directors. However, there is no guarantee that the appointment of a CRO can deter a risk management function in a firm from failing (Taleb, 2004).

However, CRO must be independent, knowledgeable, better sourced, and competent and be involved in decision making. According to the Financial Stability Board (2013), it is a best practice for a sound risk management function to have access to subsidiaries, affiliates and relevant risk information and should be part of overall risk governance framework.

Qualification Requirements

In many countries, the board members and its committees are requested to have appropriate qualifications and expertise, especially in the financial institutions in order to discharge their duties effectively. For example, Statutory Audit Directive (2006/43/EC) states that a person is granted approval to undertake statutory audit after holding a university degree, attaining practical guidance and must pass an exam of qualified competence.

Board Committees

Board committee (audit committee) in many jurisdictions is responsible for maintaining and overseeing risk management and corporate governance systems. The EU's Statutory Audit Directive calls for audit committees to oversee the fruitfulness of risk management function, internal control and similar standards around the globe. For instance, the New York Stock Exchange (NYSE) listed rules require audit committees to shed light on risk assessment and risk management systems. The Financial Stability Board consider it as a sound risk governance practice in which financial firms have separate risk committee distinct from audit committee chaired by an independent director and tends to avoid dual hatting with board chairman and other committees.

Yearly re-evaluation by the board

The board is required to undertake a yearly assessment of the internal control system and risk areas covering all factors incorporated in reports to the board of directors together with all the information related to the company's internal control. A review should cover the quality and extent of how management oversees risk management, work of internal audit function and internal control system. In addition, frequency and extent of results of management reporting to the board should be reviewed and get a feel whether the risk reporting is sound enough to facilitate management in the evaluation of internal controls and how risks are identified and managed.

2.11.3 Risk management guidelines issued by IMF

John Lipsky deputy managing director of IMF outlines the importance of risk management and argues that financial crisis reminds us that banks have to take risks in order to earn returns that tend to be excessive from the public point of view and subsequently deteriorate economy. He is of view that this is due to incentives incorporated in compensation practices of directors and inadequate monitoring by shareholders. Right risk management policies adopted by banks may assist them in reducing the risky behaviour of banks. However, the

International Monetary Fund has proposed the following risk management guidelines within the context of the global financial meltdown.

- According to IMF, Barack Obama, former president of USA required regulators to seek ways to deter banks from excessive risk-taking across the financial system and establish appropriate capital standards and compensation rules aligning directors' performance with risk management.
- In order to hold management responsible and accountable for risk management; banks should align their compensation practices with risks banks face. By offering risk managers long term bank bonds; banks may incorporate compensation with overall banks' financial performance. This measure may help banks prevent potential shareholders and risk managers to go for risky bets when banks are financially weak and less resilient to absorb financial stress.
- In an attempt to ensure effective risk management and sound internal control functions, there must be a different risk committee responsible for establishing and overseeing risk management and the board of directors should be independent of management.
- Those who are charged with governance in banks must ensure that the board not only looks after the shareholder interests but also interests of the creditors of banks. For example, granting board representation to a certain class of bondholders may encourage creditors to oversee bank managers effectively.
- IMF has required banks to grasp enough capital to make the financial system safe and resilient and it can help banks in reducing risk up to 5 percent.
- Banks can manage risks by improving their compensation and governance practices and capital requirements and should ensure their effective implementation and monitoring.
- Establishing an appropriate risk culture is also a driving factor that can create a sense of realisation that everyone working in banks is responsible for risk management and must play his/her part in this regard (IMF, 2018).

2.12 Risk Management Framework

There are various risk management systems used in various jurisdictions depending on corporate structure and complexity of business operations in those jurisdictions. The paramount risk management guidelines are those that promote an integrated approach to risk covering of both social positions of investors and capital structures. Basel II and Basel III

reinforce an integrated approach to risk management and show greater support for COSO's framework for risk management. However, three globally recognised risk management frameworks are discussed in light of how UK commercial banks can use them to enhance their financial resilience:

2.12.1 COSO framework

2.12.2 Enterprise-Wide Risk management (ERM)

2.12.3 Sarbanes Oxley Act

2.12.1 COSO framework

In early 1990 in the USA, big corporate failures and collapse of the banking industry created a wakeup call and early warning for regulators and investors emphasising the need for establishing and improving risk management practices. According to Borghesi and Gaudenzi (2012), it is unlikely that firms can eliminate risks completely but they can manage to deal with risks. Various regulators and standard-setting bodies took initiatives to refine compliance rules, corporate governance, financial reporting, internal control and risk management (Khan, 2016).

Incorporation of risk management practices and taking a holistic view of risks are better explained by a term enterprise risk management (Sax and Torp, 2015). It is a framework that integrates all risks faced by the organisation and takes a portfolio view of overseeing those risks (Grace et al., 2015).

In this regard, the Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission (COSO) published internal control-integrated framework a decade ago. It helps businesses to evaluate and improve their risk management systems. Since its launching, this framework has been incorporated into regulation, rule, and policy and is adopted by firms in different countries better controlling their activities and facilitating the achievement of their objectives. An underlying theme of COSO's framework is that firms exist to offer value to its stakeholders. Value is optimised when bank management sets targets and standards to seek the best possible equilibrium between return, risks and growth. It assists businesses in allocating resources efficiently in the pursuit of objectives.

COSO's framework is composed of eight interconnected segments. These components are implied from the way management operates businesses and incorporated with business processes.

1. Internal Environment

Internal environment in an entity sets the tone of the organisation and seeks the ways risk is considered and addressed by firms' employees. It includes risk appetite, risk management philosophy, moral principles, integrity and the business environment in which firms carry out their business operations.

2. Objective Setting

Objectives setting should be the foremost priority before management identifies key events impacting their accomplishment. Management must have systems in place to set objectives and objectives must be consistent with risk appetite and support and align mission statements of entities (COSO, 2004).

3. Event Identification

Firms must identify risk and associated opportunities and establish procedures to seek out internal and external events influencing the accomplishment of organisations' goals. Management should take opportunities constructively to improve business processes and risk management functions after taking into account management strategy and objective setting for dealing with risks.

4. Risk Assessment

For sound management of risks, management must ensure a sound risk analysis along with getting a feel of their likelihood of occurring and their impact on business performance. Residual and inherent basis can be employed by firms for effective assessment of risks (COSO, 2004).

5. Risk Response

Various risk response options should be used to deal with risks. These options are avoiding, reducing, transferring, sharing and accepting risks. The decision for choosing appropriate risk response must be associated with risk appetite and risk tolerance of an entity.

6. Control Activities

Risk responses are adequately implemented and monitored by establishing sound processes and procedures of risk assessment and analysis.

7. Information and Communication

Pertinent and reliable information must be recognized, gathered and reported in a timely fashion thereby enabling the employees in the entity to carry out their jobs efficiently. Management must ensure effective communication from top to bottom at all levels of business operations in a broader sense.

8. Monitoring

Procedures should be in place to ensure sound monitoring of risk management function established by firms and evaluate its effectiveness. Modifications in the way risk management procedures are practised can be made when needed. Monitoring can be carried out by separate evaluations and management activities. COSO's framework also helps firms in establishing their objectives, setting the organisational strategy and aligning objectives with strategy within the context of their vision and mission (COSO, 2004).

Limitations

In addition to the benefits that COSO's risk management framework offers; limitations exist in this framework that undermines its usefulness. Human judgement in decision making can be faulty because judgement is required in identifying, analysing and responding to risks. Judgement is also required to consider cost and benefit analysis of establishing a system of risk management. Human error, human failure and collusion of two or more people can obstruct the functioning of risk management function in banks. Therefore, management and the board of directors should obtain absolute assurance to achieve banks' objectives.

2.12.2 Enterprise Wide Risk management (ERM)

According to the Financial Services Group (2013), risk management is an organisational competence rather than an operational function. Basel III and strict regulatory requirements have changed the banking landscape requiring banks to assess and review their risk frameworks. Defining strategic proposition is considered to be a major component of risk management change. According to the enterprise wide risk management framework, firms need to determine their management culture and ensure that how this culture is incorporated in strategic decision making for a sound assessment and management of risks.

Enterprise risk management requires firms to incorporate a firm wide risk appetite and allocate risk ownership in a less tangible operating environment incorporating quantitative and qualitative risks. In order to carry out a sound risk assessment; categorising and communicating intangible risks to those responsible for risk management and determining their impact of organisational performance should be the foremost priority of those charged with governance (Financial Services Group, 2013).

Furthermore, banks should establish risk related controls in routine business processes and procedures for the effective management of risks. Evaluation of risk-reward of firms'

strategic decision on day to day business activities supports the management of firms in analysing how their actions are reinforcing in managing risks.

2.12.3 Sarbanes Oxley Act (SOX)

It is a United States federal law introduced in July 30, 2002. This act was enacted in response to major accounting scandals and corporate collapses in the USA and across the globe including those affecting Enron, Adelphia, WorldCom, Tyco International, and Peregrine Systems. These corporate collapses not only cost investors and banking industry billions of dollars when stock values of companies plummeted considerably: but also it undermined the consumer confidence in global stock markets (Sarbanes Oxley Act, 2002).

Moreover, banking failures and economic meltdown in the USA caused policymakers and regulators (Security Exchange Commission) in the USA to develop a sound system of internal control, risk management, and corporate governance. Therefore, the Sarbanes Oxley Act was enacted that has introduced new and robust standards in the form of guidelines for all US public company boards, public and management accounting firms (Sarbanes Oxley Act, 2002).

This act requires the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) to ensure the implementation of SOX requirements by all listed companies and consists of 11 components ranging from additional corporate responsibilities of the board, internal control, and risk management to criminal penalties.

In addition, SOX has created a Public Company Accounting Oversight Board responsible for managing, disciplining, evaluating, regulating and monitoring accounting organisations in their functions of auditing financial statements of public companies. This act also sets guidelines underpinning key areas such as corporate governance, risk management, internal control appraisal, financial reporting and improved financial disclosure (Sarbanes Oxley Act, 2002).

SOX has been proved to be very useful for companies over a period of time and it has played a very important part in strengthening the corporate accounting controls and restoring consumer confidence in banking and financial industries not only in the USA but also across the globe.

The new legislation covers 11 underlying titles or elements of SOX that are outlined in the following sections (Kenton, 2020):

- Public Company Accounting Oversight Board
- Independence of the Auditor

- Responsibility for Corporate Businesses
- Increased Disclosures for Financial Matters
- Conflicts of Interest with regards to Financial Analysts
- Allocation of Resources and Autonomy
- Reports and Communications
- Accountability for Criminal and Business Fraud
- Penalty Enrichment for White Collar Crimes
- Tax Returns for Listed Businesses
- Accountability for Corporate Fraud

1. Public Company Accounting Oversight Board

PCAOB is responsible for providing sovereign supervision to public accounting firms conducting audit and other assurance engagements. In addition, a central oversight board has been established which helps firms in defining precise processes and measures for compliance audits, registering auditors, ensuring compliance with the defined provisions of SOX and ultimately policing and inspecting conduct and quality control in assurance engagements.

2. Independence of the Auditor

This title comprises of nine sections addressing issues with regards to the independence of an auditor to restrict the conflicts of interest. In addition, it sets standards regarding the approval requirements of an auditor, auditor rotation and issues pertaining to financial reporting. Audit firms are restricted from offering non audit services (consulting) for the existing clients.

3. Responsibility for Corporate Businesses

When it comes to corporate responsibility, leading executives are individually responsible for completeness and accuracy of business financial reports. Roles and responsibilities of auditors and audit committees are defined along with specifying responsibilities of corporate officers to ensure the validity and accuracy of financial reporting. Behaviours of management of firms are overseen with offering rewards for management appropriately discharging their roles in risk management and corporate governance. Civil penalties are introduced for non-compliance with laws and applicable financial reporting framework. For example; section 302 of SOX requires the chief financial officer and chief executive officer of listed companies to approve and certify the accuracy of their firms' financial reports quarterly.

4. Increased Disclosures for Financial Matters

This section gives financial reporting guidelines for financial transactions, pro forma figures, off-balance sheet transactions and stock transactions of corporate officers. It requires companies to establish a stringent system of risk management and internal control for ensuring the accuracy of financial reports, disclosures and mandates both audit and report on these controls.

5. Conflicts of Interest with regards to Financial Analysts

Aim of this section is to enhance the trust of investors in reporting of a securities analyst. It also offers codes of conduct for securities experts and asks firms to ensure the disclosure of conflicts of interest.

6. Allocation of Resources and Autonomy

This section is related to the definition of authority of the Securities Exchange Commission to restrict securities specialists from practice and has underlined conditions under which an individual is stopped from acting as a dealer or broker.

7. Reports and Communications

Comprising of five sections, this title requires Securities Exchange Commission and the Comptroller General in the USA to undertake studies on risk management and internal control to increase the financial robustness of the listed companies and then to report and document their findings. In addition, companies must include in their reports the consequences of the consolidation of communal accounting firms, securities violations and enforcement actions, the function of credit rating agencies in the business of stock markets and eventually to investigate whether investment banks in the USA helped Enron, Global Crossing and other firms to manoeuvre profits and complicate true financial conditions.

8. Accountability for Criminal and Business Fraud

The corporate and criminal fraud accountability act of 2002 specifies criminal penalties for material inconsistencies in companies including manipulation, alteration and destruction of financial accounts and another intrusion with investigations and provides definite safeguards for whistleblowers.

9. Penalty Enrichment for White Collar Crimes

Like the corporate and criminal fraud accountability act of 2002; the white collar crime penalty enhancement act of 2002 tightens the penalties for white collar crimes and conspiracies. It introduces stringent sentencing rules required of companies to be followed to develop corporate governance and increase the effectiveness of their risk management function.

10. Tax Returns for Listed Businesses

Section 1001 of SOX outlines that only Chief Executive Officer (CEO) of a company can sign tax returns filed in SEC annually.

11. Accountability for Corporate Fraud

Consisting of seven parts; section 111 of SOX regards record tampering and corporate fraud as criminal offences and ultimately recommends certain penalties for these offences. Also, this title requires the Security Exchange Commission in the USA to resort to temporarily payments and transactions that are perceived to be large and unusual.

Factors contributing to the adoption of SOX

In 2000 and 2002, a series of conditions and events occurred that caused a significant number of corporate fraud and collapses to be occurred that unfavourably affected the international economic system and specifically the banking industry. For example; extensively publicised frauds at WorldCom, Enron and Tyco reflected significant deficiencies in their risk management functions and corporate governance with incentive compensation schemes and conflicts of interest.

Banking Practices

Appropriate banking practice is one of the most significant factors that have led to the adoption of the Sarbanes Oxley Act. In the case of Enron, the main banks offered bulky loans to Enron without considering and ignoring the risk of a company to be a going concern. Ultimately, clients and investors of these banks were devastated by such bad loans resulting in huge settlement payments by banks. Adopting inadequate internal control and risk management framework by Enron resulted in a collapse of Enron that undermined the confidence of investors as well.

Internet Bubble

In 2000, investors had stung because of sharp declines in technology stocks and declines in the overall market to a lesser extent. Moreover, certain mutual fund managers were perceived to have encouraged the purchase of technology stocks while selling the confidentially on the other hand. Resultant losses incurred as a shock of anger among potential investors.

Boardroom Failures

Board of directors and their audit committees were alleged to establish oversight mechanisms on behalf of investors for financial reporting in the US firms. These events identified

discrepancies in a way firms were running because the board members were not exercising their responsibilities properly and a few of them did not have the knowledge to realize the complexities of banks. Moreover, in many firms, members of audits committees were dependent on the management of banks.

Executive Compensation

Inappropriate executive compensation schemes offered by big corporations caused top management to ignore opportunities in the long term and just pursue profitable opportunities short term to show a higher profit in the pursuit of their bonuses. For example; in many firms, bonus practices and stock options combined with unpredictability in stock values for even small earnings resulted in pressure on management to deal with earnings and manipulate profit figures to maximise their bonuses and perks for fraudulent financial reporting and missing opportunities to invest in profitable projects.

Advantages of SOX

SOX act of 2002 was passed by Congress to enhance the control environment, refine the consistency of financial reporting, combat fraud, uphold a concrete system of internal control and risk management and to restore the investor confidence.

Effective implementation of SOX may help organisations in strengthening their control environment. Firms with stringent governance system in place provide discipline and structure, foster ethical norms in employees and train them to follow appropriate procedures which may enable them to operate business operations effectively. SOX assists the management of firms in establishing a sound system of internal control encompassing control procedures and control environment and it helps executives and directors of firms in recognising the importance of transparency and openness in creation and execution of the company's procedures and policies.

Improved documentation is obtained by implementing guidelines provided by SOX and it assists firms in maintaining unnecessary documentation and paperwork. It requires companies to update operations manuals; record controls processes and revise personnel policies. For example; according to Paul Audet, former CFO of Blackrock an investment firm having more than \$450 billion in assets undertook an extensive inventory of its written procedures and policies. In the course of this exercise, Paul noticed that most of the jobs required revision and updating. Also, SOX ensures active involvement of audit committees in the audit process and ensures their engagement in maintaining and defining the scope and issues relating to external audit and maintaining external auditors' independence (Wagner

and Dittmar, 2016). Sarbanes Oxley Act assists firms in achieving standardised processes by adopting a consistent approach to risk management and corporate governance.

Sarbanes Oxley Act has also limitations that undermine its usefulness. These limitations are explained as follows:

Limitations of the Sarbanes Oxley Act

This law was approved in 2002 to stop companies from engaging in fraudulent financial reporting and accounting fraud that was perpetrated by WorldCom and Enron. Sarbanes Oxley Act enhanced the accuracy and transparency of financial information and rebuilt the confidence of investors and securities markets. However, SOX has some challenges and issues for firms while trying to abide by the SOX guidelines.

This act requires firms to establish a stringent system of risk management and internal control to secure financial information of companies. Establishing an internal control system proves to be costly for small and start-up companies and it requires resources to establish an in-house internal control system. All employees are required to ensure the completeness of paper works and authorisation by supervisors. Extensive number and functions of internal control may slow down the finishing period for each accounting period and it results in delaying the preparations of financial statements.

Segregation of accounting duties is one of the key functions of SOX guidelines. It requires that no single individual can handle all accounting functions from beginning to end because it may raise the options of embezzlement and deception. Under the SOX guidelines, all listed companies are required to undertake at least once a year audit by another accounting firm. Increased number of audits by accounting firms may affect the company's profits and shareholder dividends due to additional audit fees and costs.

After the collapse of Enron and World Com, the Sarbanes Oxley Act provided increased oversight in the accounting industry. Furthermore, in the light of SOX guidelines, many jurisdictions across the globe have posed extra financial burden in terms of compliance with more regulations thereby increasing the costs of carrying out business operations.

Sarbanes Oxley Act of 2002 has introduced strict penalties for accounting embezzlement and fraud. Unfortunately, some penalties are enacted for small contraventions such as not signing annual accounts and not issuing financial accounts to the intended users after approval by the executive management of the bank. These harsh penalties on inconsequential violations restrict the executive talent pool if management staff in future does not want to be held accountable for such activities and penalties (Vitez, 2009).

2.13 Evaluation of the application and the impact of Basel III in managing risks

The global financial meltdown of 2007-08 identified a large number of fault lines in regulatory frameworks then used by the banking industry, for instance, excessive leverage, inadequate levels of good quality capital, and a lack of global standards for liquidity risk and insufficient consideration of macro-prudential risks. In 2010, the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision introduced various regulatory measures that helped banks in addressing these shortcomings (Santos et al, 2020). Vallascas & Hagedorff (2013) endorse above arguments and claim that the economic meltdown that happened in 2007 highlights that over last two decades despite new developments and refinements; capital adequacy of banks has failed to make sure that regulatory capital needs are compatible with the riskiness of banks assets. Since the beginning of the economic meltdown, banks maintaining inadequate capital created uncertainties over the going concern status of banks thereby undermining the proper functioning of interbank markets. According to Hellwig (2010), Basel Committee (2011) & Acharya and Richardson (2009), the key reason why banks did not hold enough capital was their capital requirements that were not adjusted to the riskiness of banks assets.

Banks in the UK are following various regulatory measures introduced by Basel III to enhance their financial resilience. HSBC in the UK is supervised by the Prudential Regulation Authority (PRA) which seeks information regarding capital requirements and its capital sufficiency under the Basel III capital requirements. In December 2017, Basel III was revised and introduced changes to the risk weighted assets (RWA) regime that require all banks to hold buffer capital after taking into account their risk weighted assets (RWA) (HSBC, 2018).

The Basel III: International framework for liquidity risk measurement, standards and monitoring is assisting the banking industry to strengthen liquidity rules and global capital in an attempt to endorse a more durable banking industry. With the development of various regulatory measures such as liquidity ratio, net stable funding ratio and capital ratio, it is enhancing the ability of banks to absorb shocks emanating from the economic and financial stress irrespective of their source. Thus, it reduces the risk of spill over from the financial sector to the real economy (BCBS, 2017).

Basel III refers to increasing the capital adequacy of banks which enables them to manage the risks they face. The preamble of the new CRD IV/CRR regulatory structure under Basel III has assisted the EU banking industry in strengthening their capital position (Ciurlau, 2016). Basel III has integrated best risk modelling practices into the regulatory framework which in

turn has enhanced the potential of banks to develop; implement and monitor best performing risk management policies (Balthazar, 2006).

Walter (2011) suggests three main reasons for the recent financial crisis of 2007-08:

- Excessive leverage
- Excess liquidity chasing yields
- Under pricing of risk
- Too much credit and weak underwriting standards

Walter (2011) further argues that Basel III has enhanced the financial resilience and capability of banks to absorb financial shocks in the following ways.

It has introduced a leverage ratio that serves as a backstop to the risk-based framework. It has enhanced risk coverage focusing on those areas that perceived to be key reasons for the financial crisis such as securitisation activities, counterparty credit risk and trading book exposures. Short term and long term liquidity mismatches have been coped with new international liquidity standards set by Basel III. Refining the definition of capital with a specific spotlight on common equity has improved the capital adequacy of banks. Under Basel III, total banking capital now comprises of common equity tier 1 capital (retained earnings) and tier 2 capital.

The credibility of the risk weighted asset (RWA) framework was eroded during the onset of the financial crisis. Various studies have been undertaken by academics, BCBS and analysts to evaluate the extent of unpredictability in risk weights predicted by the internal models of banks (Santos et al, 2020). The excessive degree of variability in RWAs brings significant implications for banks. Two banks with the same risk tolerances and balance sheets may report remarkably varied estimates of their regulatory capital ratios. Consequently, this RWA variability can undermine the effectiveness of risk weighted capital framework as a risk responsive measure of solvency of banks (BCBS, 2011).

To that end, Basel III has introduced initiatives to reduce excessive RWA variability (BCBS, 2017). These initiatives include (1) limiting the use of internally modelled approaches (2) increasing the soundness and risk sensitivity of the standardised approaches (3) establishing an output floor to in house modelled RWAs. The output floor requires that the level of risk weighted assets of a bank is not lower than 72.5% of risk weighted assets had the bank estimated capital needs with the help of standardised models (BCBS, 2017).

According to the Financial Stability Board (2020), consistent and timely application of Basel III is critical to a robust and proper running of the banking system which enhances the

potential of banks to enhance the economic growth and recovery on a sustainable basis. Timely application and consistent application of Basel III offer a level playing field for globally vigorous banks. Regulatory acceptance of different core Basel III elements has been applied and implemented consistently since 2012. Basel III risk-based capital and liquidity have been applied in all 24 FSB jurisdictions. Moreover, Basel III guidelines about the higher loss absorbency requirement for global systemically important banks (G-SIBs) are enforced effectively in all countries. However, rules with regards to appraisal strategy and higher loss absorbency needs for domestic systemically important banks (D-SIBs) are consistently applied in 23 jurisdictions (Financial Stability Board, 2020).

2.14 Summary

The literature review chapter has shed light on key aspects of risk management and has reviewed risk management in detail explaining why it is vital for banking institutions to ensure their financial resilience and stability. Various themes underpinning risk management including failures and benefits of risk management, empirical and theoretical underpinnings, the association between risk management and capital adequacy of banks, risk management practices and framework have been critically reviewed that has helped the current research in identifying the literature gap. Therefore, it can be argued that risk management plays a crucial part in ensuring the going concern status of banks and facilitating them in managing risks effectively.

Chapter Three: Methodology Chapter

3.1 Introduction

In the preceding chapter; detailed literature has been reviewed on risk management with a particular focus on the London banks. Literature review chapter has helped the current research in identifying the gap in the published literature on risk management which in turn has enabled the current research to perform an enthusiastic study in the field of banking risk management specifically London banks with a particular focus on HSBC and LLOYDS.

The research methodology has been developed on the basis of investigation of relevant studies on risk management and the literature review discussed in chapter two. The aim of the methodology chapter is to shed light on the research methods, research strategies, sampling, data collection and analysis strategies that are undertaken to carry out the empirical part of the study. The last part of this chapter explains a synopsis of the methodology chapter.

3.2 Research Question

How effective are the current practices of risk management followed by London banks within the context of LLOYDS and HSBC and what risk management framework can be recommended to enhance the financial resilience of the banking sector?

3.2.1 Research objectives

As discussed in chapter one (section 1.4), the current work aims to evaluate the effectiveness of current practices of risk management followed by London banks with a specific focus on LLOYDS and HSBC and to develop a sound risk management framework which may enhance the financial resilience of the banking industry. At the heart of this study is the question of determination of risk management practices followed by the London banks and the evaluation of the effectiveness of risk management practices in enhancing the financial resilience of the banking industry.

A review of available literature on risk management does not give a comprehensive answer to the above research question which is anticipated to be answered by the collection of primary and secondary data through semi structured interviews conducted with bank managers and risk managers and survey questionnaire sent to bank managers, risk managers and banking professionals to get their feedback on risk management.

In the following sections, the aim and objectives of the current research are reproduced in order to assist this study in choosing appropriate research methodologies.

3.2.2 Aim

To assess the effectiveness of current practices of risk management followed by London banks with a specific focus on LLOYDS and HSBC and to develop a sound risk management framework in order to enhance the financial resilience of the banking sector.

3.2.3 Objectives

1. To determine the key risks faced by HSBC and LLOYDS.
2. To ascertain the current practices of risk management followed by London banks and to explore the relationship between various aspects of risk management in order to manage risks, maximise opportunities and uphold economic stability.
3. To investigate if there is any relationship between risk management and the amount of capital banks hold.
4. To evaluate the application of Basel III in London banks and to determine the impact of Basel III in managing risks.
5. To recommend a risk management framework in order to enhance the financial resilience of the banking sector.

The following section sheds light on various research philosophies with a detailed debate on the research philosophy chosen for this study and its justification.

3.3 Research Philosophy

It is about the evolution of knowledge as a result of conducting research on specific issues and the nature of knowledge developed in a specific area (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). At every stage during the course of conducting research; the researchers develop assumptions. Bryman and Bell (2011) reinforce the above argument and highlight that research studies conducted on the basis of assumptions assume that how this world is seen and comprehended by researchers in a systematic way.

The assumptions about individual knowledge and the essence of realities that the researchers come across during the research process help them in understanding the research questions, methods of data collection and the way findings are interpreted (Crotty, 1998). Moreover, the assumptions reinforce research strategies and methods to collect data as a key component of the research plan.

Johnson and Clark (2006) are of the view that management and business researchers must take into account philosophical commitments when developing research strategies because these philosophical commitments not only have an impact on what researchers do but also impact on what they are investigating.

There are different ways of looking at the research philosophy which mainly depends on the research questions; epistemology and ontology. Both philosophical considerations identify differences in the way the research process is conducted. Moreover, both choices enable the researchers to be well equipped to elucidate and rationalize their methodical choice, research design, research strategy and methods of data collection and analysis.

Following sections shed the spotlight on both philosophical considerations in detail.

3.3.1 Epistemology

This philosophy concerns with the attainment of knowledge in a field of study. It addresses the question of what is considered as an acceptable knowledge in a specific field. According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012), epistemology refers to the way how a researcher obtains the acceptable awareness of a specific area of research. The contentions about knowledge, reality and achievement of knowledge have not only absorbed philosophers, researchers and theorists of different fields but also are limited to management and business research.

Epistemology is of two types: positivism and interpretivism. These are discussed in underneath sections:

Positivism is one of the most important types of epistemology that encourages the use of methods of natural sciences underpinning the examination of social reality. Positivists argue that reality is the function of five senses i.e. smell, taste, touch, sound and sight that help social researchers in obtaining acceptable knowledge. Unlike philosophical conjecture, an inquiry should be empirical and needs to be based on scientific research (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

Gill and Johnson (2010) support above stances and argue that positivism takes a view of natural scientist that encourages the researcher to gather data about a visible reality and identify underlying associations and regularities in data thereby enabling them to deduce law-like generalisations similar to those created by scientists. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) add to the earlier claims and state that positivists use existing theory to develop hypotheses.

On the other hand, interpretivism explains that it is imperative for the researcher to perceive the differences between humans acting as social actors. This stance reinforces the need for understanding the way the research is conducting on individuals rather than items. A thread of interpretivism emanates from two academic traditions; symbolic interactionism and phenomenology. In symbolic interactionism, the researchers as social actors are in a frequent

progression of interpreting the social world around them in the same way they analyse the actions of others they interact with. This interpretation results in the adjustment of their actions and meanings. On the contrary, phenomenology is about the way in which the researcher as human beings makes sense of the world around them (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

Gray (2009) advocates the above arguments and states that interpretivism is about the reality that is socially constructed and social sciences and natural science require different methods of research and interpretation of findings. In order to induce theory and laws, individual actions play a leading role in business and management research. Unlike positivism, a strategy is required to help the researcher in understanding the difference between objects of natural sciences and people.

3.3.2 Pragmatism

Pragmatism refers to the view that concepts are only pertinent in the research study when they reinforce actions. This means that research questions of the study are the most significant determinant of researcher position on each area of the continuum i.e. on position to answer the research questions tend to be more appropriate than the other position in an attempt to meet the aim and objectives of the study. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) take the same position as Kelemen and Rumens (2008) take on pragmatism and argue that multiple research methods are highly appropriate research methods when adopting pragmatism philosophy within one study. They further state that there are various methods of interpreting the world and conducting research and there are multiple realities of underpinning the research. For instance, a single stance can ever give a full picture of an observable phenomenon. Researchers can take advantages of adopting pragmatism philosophy including assisting in answering various research questions, offering them various methods of research investigation, encouraging collaboration among researchers and adopting diverse philosophical orientations.

Having discussed epistemological philosophical considerations in the above sections; it is summarised that epistemology entails paramount significant in a business and management research that is inevitably pertinent to ontological considerations in business research (Cunliffe, 2011 and Grix, 2004).

3.3.3 Ontology

Ontology is about the nature of reality. It escalates the concerns about the assumptions the researchers have about the way the world operates and determination to the specific stances

underpinning business and management research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). There are two main ontological considerations that are worth mentioning in this research. These considerations are objectivism and subjectivism. Both aspects of ontology are perceived to be accepted philosophical orientations of valid knowledge by many researchers (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

Objectivism confesses that social entities in real position are independent of social actors and are external to them. According to Bryman and Bell, (2011) under objectivism, a firm is an intangible thing that has to be complied with certain laws and regulations to get things done. Standardised procedures are followed to continue its operations and are separate from individuals who manage it.

On the contrary, subjectivism or social constructionism asserts that consequent actions and perceptions of social actors create a social phenomenon. Because social connections between social actors are a frequent process therefore social process is a continual process of revision. It reinforces the need for studying the details of a situation to contemplate what is happening and the reasons for the occurrence in social perspective. Crotty (1998) and Bryman and Bell (2011) support the above claims and argue that social actors are key drivers in continually accomplishing social phenomena and their meanings. Constructionism asserts that it is vital for researchers to review the details of a particular situation to increase the knowhow of the impetus of occurrence and reasons behind the occurrence of specific situations.

3.3.4 Research philosophy undertaken for this work

Bearing into mind the research questions and research gap of the research; pragmatic philosophical position is adopted to answer the research questions and to achieve the overall aim of the study. The goal of undertaking this work is to assess the effectiveness of current practices of risk management in the London banks with a specific focus on LLOYDS and HSBC to develop a sound risk management framework to enhance the financial resilience of the banking sector. Therefore, this research has laid down emphasis on gaining a profound understanding and awareness of risk management in the banks and evaluating its effectiveness.

Moreover, the current research is taken as a holistic attempt and entails a positive approach to mixed methods research designs (Onwuegbuize and Leech, 2005). In this study, a mixed methodology is used in which qualitative and quantitative data is obtained through semi structured interviews and survey questionnaires are sent to banking professionals in the HSBC and LLOYDS to seek their opinions and perceptions on risk management.

From the above discussion, it is summarised that pragmatism is the most appropriate research philosophy for this research within the context of the research questions because from section 3.3.2, it is evident that pragmatists employ mixed methods research design as data collection techniques and highly structured and large samples are used in case of pragmatism that is also the spirit of conducting this research.

3.4 Research Approach

The theory is used in very research when the researcher intends to answer certain research questions of the project. In the design of the research theory that can be or cannot be made explicit as it tends to be made explicit when presenting the results and conclusions of the study (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). The degree to which the researcher is convinced about the theory to be employed at the start of the research study takes up an important question pertaining to the plan of the research study.

According to Ketokivi and Mantere (2010), two research approaches can be used by the researcher based on the reasoning they adopt; deductive approach and inductive approach. Both approaches are discussed briefly in the next sections.

3.4.1 Deductive Approach

This approach refers to the development of a theory that is tested for acceptance or rejection in the course of various propositions. Furthermore, it is a widely used approach in the natural sciences where laws are the main drivers of rationalization, anticipate their occurrence, allow the anticipation of phenomena and predominantly allow them to be controlled and monitored (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Gill and Johnson (2010) support above arguments and state that on the basis of a specific theory deductive approach facilitates to test a hypothesis which is subject to acceptance or rejection depending on the findings of statistical analysis.

Blaikie (2010) lists six steps to understand the progress of the deductive approach.

1. A theory is developed by putting forward a tentative premise and different hypotheses to test the propositions about the affiliation between variables and concepts.
2. Existing literature on the subject matter is reviewed to test several propositions and deduce hypotheses.
3. This step involves examining the logic and the premises of the argument that generate them and comparing the current theories with the arguments to review if it demonstrates any progress in its understanding; if it shows any advancement then it is subject to continuation.

4. Premises are tested by collected relevant statistics to determine the variables and analyse them.
5. If the above discussed tests fail i.e. if findings of tests are inconsistent with the premises; the theory is considered to be false and ultimately abandoned/ amended and research procedure is restarted.

3.4.2 Inductive Approach

This approach is concerned with the context in which social events take place. Therefore, unlike deductive approach small sample size is used in inductive approach bearing into mind the research questions of the study (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Qualitative data is used and establishing various views of phenomena requires the researchers to use different strategies for collecting and analysing data.

Bryman and Bell (2011) argue that inductive approach is a reverse process of deductive approach that starts with the empirical observations and findings and these findings are more likely to be a source of development of new theories. Gill and Johnson (2010) emphasise the need for understanding research approaches thereby enabling investigators to choose the most appropriate to their research studies.

3.4.3 Research approach undertaken for this research

The deductive approach is used in the current research owing to the empirical nature of the study. According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012), development of hypothesis is the main theme of the deductive approach to evaluate propositions therefore the deductive approach is the most suitable approach for this research work. Considering the research questions of this study, hypotheses are developed to determine the relationship between dependant variables (capital adequacy of banks) and independent variables (risk weighted assets). Statistical analysis is conducted to approve or decline the hypotheses.

3.5 Research Design

Research design is the generic plan of how the researchers attempt to respond to the research questions. This plan involves the derivation of research objectives from research questions specifying the sources of data collection. Moreover, how to collect and analyse data, consideration of ethical issues underpinning data collection and restraints the researchers inevitably encounter during the research process are discussed in research design. According to Hussey and Hussey (1997), research design provides a bridge between research activities such as data collection, analysis and research objectives of the study. Selection of a particular

research design involves different overarching factors such as the procedures for inquiry and the purpose of the study (Robson, 2011; Creswell, 2003).

Three research designs are used by researchers depending on the research questions of the research project. These include the quantitative method, qualitative method and multiple methods research design.

Quantitative research design is linked with the positivism research philosophy specifically when highly structured and prearranged data gathering strategies are used. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) further argue that a distinction must be drawn about the characteristics of the businesses, people and other things and data based on feedbacks and perceptions as these are often referred to qualitative numbers. However, quantitative research design may also be used within pragmatism and interpretivism research philosophies depending on the research questions of the research project.

In addition, quantitative research is allied with the deductive approach where the researcher focuses on pertinent data to investigate the theory. In case of where data is collected to develop a theory; quantitative research design incorporates inductive approach. Probability sampling is preferably used in this research design to ensure the generalisability and it determines the relationship between variables which are investigated and assessed by using statistical techniques.

On the other hand, the qualitative research design is related to the interpretive research philosophy because the researcher is required to develop a sense of socially constructed and subjective meanings expressing the phenomenon being studied. This research is also perceived to be naturalistic as the researcher tends to operate within a natural setting in an attempt to develop participation, trust, access to in-depth understanding and meanings. Similar to quantitative research; qualitative research design can be used in the context of pragmatist and realist philosophies e.g. multiple methods research design.

The inductive approach is associated with qualitative research where an emergent and naturalist research design is undertaken to formulate an extensive theoretical perspective that already exists in the literature. However, bearing into mind the research questions of the study, qualitative research begins with the deductive approach in an attempt to test the current theory by using qualitative research (Yin, 2009).

Besides the above two discussed research designs; mixed methodology consists of both qualitative and quantitative research design (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Pragmatism philosophy is widely used in multiple methods research design. Pragmatists are not wedded to either interpretivism or positivism which is considered to be a theory of opposing concepts or

dualism (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012; Tashakhori and Teddie, 2010). Research context, research consequences and research questions tend to be the most important driving factors behind establishing the most appropriate methodical choice for pragmatists. Pragmatists give equal importance to both quantitative and qualitative research paradigms and the exact methodical choice is contingent on the nature and context of the research project (Nastasi et al. 2010).

Multiple methods research design can use either deductive or inductive approach and is more likely to use both which depends on the research objectives of the study. Both research designs can be used by the researcher to test theoretical premises followed by further quantitative and qualitative research designs to develop the richer theoretical propositions (Tashakhori and Teddie, 2010).

3.5.1 Research design used in this research

Mixed methods research design is used in this research work to meet the research objectives of the study. This research is aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of current practices of risk management followed in the London banks with a particular focus on LLOYDS and HSBC to develop a stringent risk management framework to enhance the financial resilience of the banking sector. It is evident from the above mentioned aim that this study is attempting to probe two things; firstly, gaining a deeper understanding and holistic overview of risk management in HSBC and LLOYDS and evaluation of their effectiveness that is only achievable by seeking and developing explanations from bank managers and risk managers working in HSBC and LLOYDS across London.

Secondly, this study aims to recommend a robust risk management system for the banking industry to be adopted in order to enhance the financial resilience to absorb financial shocks in case of financial stress. This question is also likely to be answered by seeking opinions and perceptions of banking and finance professionals by conducting interviews with risk managers and distributing survey questionnaires to banking and finance professionals. Furthermore, this research seeks to find out what is the impact of risk management on the capital banks hold that is an entirely quantitative research that is likely to be answered by using quantitative research and hypotheses is developed to investigate the relationship between risk weighted assets as an independent variable and the amount of capital as a dependent variable.

From the above discussion, it is quite clear that the nature of the research questions of this work involves the collection of both narrative and numeric data because a mono method is

unlikely to answer the research questions. Therefore, multiple methods research design is supposed to be suitable for the current research in which qualitative and quantitative research strategies are utilised to gather and investigate both numerical and qualitative data.

Furthermore, this research study is undertaken in three stages to answer the research questions of the study. Quantitative data is a major part that is collected through the distribution of survey questionnaires and from financial statements of banks whereas primary qualitative data is collected by conducting interviews with managers and risk managers of HSBC and LLOYDS in London.

Next section puts the spotlight on the different research strategies with detailed discussion on research strategy to be used for this study.

3.6 Research Strategies

Various combinations of mixed methods research characteristics result in different research strategies after bearing into mind the research questions and the aim and objectives of the research. The overarching mixed methods research strategies are concurrent triangulation design, sequential explanatory design, concurrent embedded design, sequential exploratory design and sequential multiphase design (Creswell, 2009; Creswell Plano Clark, 2007). Bryman and Bell (2011) explain two principal types of the research plan that are recognised as qualitative and quantitative.

However, Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) emphasise the need for considering the research questions of the project when developing an appropriate research strategy to answer the research questions. The way study questions are asked by the researcher involves explanatory, descriptive and exploratory research strategies. Throughout conducting research; research objectives may also be changed over time that requires the researcher to consider all key aspects of research to meet the research goals of the study.

In the following sections, the above mentioned three research strategies are discussed briefly that has helped the researcher to choose the appropriate strategy with regards to the nature of the research project.

3.6.1 Exploratory Studies

Exploratory studies are a useful mean of asking open questions to get valuable insights about a particular field of interest and determine the reasons for their occurrence. It is a widely used study when getting a deeper understanding of a specific problem specifically when the researcher is uncertain about the exact reason of the research issue.

There are different ways to conduct exploratory research. These include conducting focus group interviews, conducting in depth individual interviews, research of literature and interviewing the experts in specific fields. Because of the exploratory nature of the study, interviews are most likely to be unstructured in the format and success of the interviews depends on the quality of contributions from those who play their part in guiding the subsequent stage of conducting the research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

The overarching benefit of an exploratory study is its flexibility and adaptability to change. The exploratory research can change its approach and direction in case of new data that appears and new insights that the researcher comes across. However, the research becomes narrower as the research progresses and commences with a broader focus (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

3.6.2 Explanatory Studies

These studies aim to determine the underlying relationship between variables with a particular focus on investigating a problem to put a spotlight on the association between variables. Different data collection techniques and statistical tools are used in the research to get a clear view of the relationship and interpret the findings after testing the hypotheses (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

3.6.3 Descriptive Studies

Descriptive research is about gaining accurate details of persons, events and situations. It may be the extension of either exploratory research or explanatory research. For this purpose, the researcher needs to have an unambiguous depiction of the observable fact on which the researcher wants to gather data. Descriptive studies have an overriding role in business and management research.

3.6.4 Research Strategy for this Study

As research strategy is an arrangement of how the researcher answers his/her research questions; therefore it offers a methodical connection between research philosophy and consequent choice of strategies to gather and investigate data (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005).

Critical analysis of literature review, development of the research questions and considering the various research philosophies, approaches, and research designs; this study is adopting mixed methods research as this research tends to offer comprehensive results not only to meet the research objectives but also to respond to the research questions accordingly.

Moreover, in this triangulation strategy semi structured interviews are conducted to collect qualitative data whereas survey questionnaires are sent to banking and finance professionals

in London to collect quantitative data. According to Bryan (2006), combining both qualitative and quantitative research strategies facilitates the researcher to triangulate the findings, help in the interpretation of findings, and allow generalisability and complementarities.

According to Bryman and Bell (2011), mixed methods research is a widely used research strategy in social science and business research. Mixed methods have been adopted by different researchers in their research studies over a period of time that has increased its acceptance and usefulness in meeting the research objectives (Molina-Azorin and Cameron, 2010). Bryman (2008) reinforces above claims and argues that from 1993 to 2004 there has been a threefold increase in the exercise of mixed methodology in the management and business fields. The mixed methodology has gained credibility and acceptance and it is adopted as a distinctive research strategy in various business studies on a fairly regular basis.

3.7 Time Horizon

An overriding question that is extensively asked when planning research is that whether research undertaken is a snapshot at a particular time or the research is a sequence of snapshots and presentations of actions over a specific period. Certainly, it is based on the research questions of the study. Selecting a time horizon is considered under cross sectional and longitudinal studies that are discussed in the following sections (Cooper and Schindler, 2011).

3.7.1 Cross Sectional Studies

This study refers to the examination of a specific phenomenon at a particular time because most research projects for academic purposes are time constrained. Survey strategies are often used in cross sectional studies that assist the researcher in explaining the occurrence of a phenomenon and determining the relationship between variables in testing the hypotheses (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

3.7.2 Longitudinal Studies

The dominant feature of a longitudinal study is its potential to study development and change. It provides the researcher with a measure of control over variables being investigated. Moreover, data with regards to the dependent variables is obtained in a certain period of time in the longitudinal studies (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). In contrast to the cross sectional studies; extra effort and more costs are incurred by the researcher in undertaking longitudinal studies.

Cross sectional study has been undertaken for this thesis due to time constraints of three years and data has been collected only one time for this research. Moreover, multiple methods

research design is used in this work where narrative data is gathered by conducting interviews with managers of banks in the UK and survey questionnaires have been distributed to banking and finance professionals in the UK to seek their opinions and views on risk management. Multiple methods research strategy is a key attribute of a cross sectional study therefore it is perceived to be more suitable for this research.

On the contrary, a longitudinal study is difficult to use or is inappropriate to require for this study due to different factors such as time constraints, limited financial aid and limited access to the UK banks.

The next sections put the spotlight on the sampling undertaken in this research.

3.8 Sampling

Appropriate sampling technique is used in this research study due to different issues associated with data collection and analysis because it impossible to study the whole population of samples and then test the whole population. According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, (2012), it is not possible for the researcher to collect and analyse all the potential data because of restrictions of money, access and time. Sekaran and Bougie (2013) reinforce the above claims and argue that logistics, time and money constraints are the key drivers of the sampling process. They are of the view that for efficient research; selection of a right sample from the whole population plays an overriding part in seeking the generalisation of results from the sample of the whole population.

Next section outlines the population, various sampling techniques with a particular focus on the sampling technique used in this study and its justification:

3.8.1 Research Population

The research population is the universe of units from which the research sample is chosen for investigation and analysis. The population of this study contains two banks namely HSBC and LLOYDS across London including their associated branches in all 32 London boroughs. These banks have been chosen for conducting interviews with risk managers and managers of various branches of HSBC and LLOYDS. Furthermore, these banks and their associated branches in London have also been chosen for a survey questionnaire. Questionnaires have been distributed to managers and risk managers in London to seek their opinions on risk management.

3.8.2 Sampling Procedures

In an attempt to seek answers to the research questions; it is impracticable for a researcher to obtain data from the whole population. For research purposes, the researcher needs to choose

a sample that is a true representative of the whole population (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). A sample refers to the selected portion of a population for investigative purposes. It is also known as sub group of the entire population that is used by academics and researchers to collect data on a specific research subject and then to analyse and deduce findings after using appropriate data analysis techniques (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). Selection of an appropriate sample is equally significant whether the researcher wishes to make use of interviews, observation, questionnaires or another data collection strategy. Barnett (2002) argues that using an appropriate sample ensures a higher accuracy of adopting and using appropriate research strategies which facilitates the researcher to answer the research questions depending on the aim and objectives of the study.

3.8.3 Sampling Techniques

The sampling techniques are divided into various categories that can be used for research purposes:

- Probability Sampling
- Non-Probability Sampling (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012)

Probability Sampling

With the probability sampling, the probability of selecting a sample from the entire population is known and this probability is equal for all cases. In addition, each unit is randomly selected from the entire population and each item has an equal chance of being chosen as a true representative. Probability sampling facilitates in achieving the objectives of the study and answering the research questions requiring them to determine the features of the population from the sample. It is usually linked with experiment and survey strategies (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

Probability sampling is illustrated in four steps:

1. Identifying an appropriate sample frame depending on the aim, objectives and the research questions of the study.
2. Selecting a suitable sample size.
3. Assisting researchers in selecting the most suitable sample and using pertinent sampling techniques.
4. Determining whether the sample is a true representative of the entire population.

All four stages are used in turn. However, Henry (1990) argues against the use of probability sampling. Henry (1990) argues that the researchers should accumulate data from the whole

population as the influence of a single extreme case as subsequent statistical analyses are more well-defined for large sample sizes.

Non-Probability Sampling

With non-probability sampling, the probability of selecting each sample from the entire population is not known to the researcher. A non-probability sampling technique makes it impracticable for the researcher to answer the research questions and achieve objectives of the research that requires them to develop statistical inferences about the features of the population. Also, the researcher needs to generalise about the population from non-probability samples rather than on statistical grounds (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Furthermore, for non probability sampling, the researcher may select units from the entire population without taking into account the random selection technique enhancing more probabilities of units being chosen as a subject than other (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

An element of subjective judgement is included in the majority of non-probability sampling techniques. In the exploratory studies such as pilot survey, non-probability sample is widely used sampling technique depending on the choice of research strategies, research questions and the aim and objectives of the research.

Therefore, the decision to use pertinent sampling technique depends on the sensibility and feasibility of collecting data to achieve the research objectives and answer the research questions from the entire population. A sampling frame is developed in probability sampling making it more time consuming than non-probability sampling (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

3.8.4 Sampling Technique used in this Study

The current study has used a convenience sampling technique that is one of the subcategories of non probability sampling technique. Convenience sampling involves choosing the cases haphazardly because they are easily accessible and most suitable for the researcher to acquire a sample. With convenient sampling, samples are chosen due to their proximity and convenience to the researcher.

Reason for using convenience sampling is that the researcher needs to conduct interviews with bank managers in London and distribute survey questionnaires to risk managers and top managers belonging to HSBC and LLOYDS across London. Research participants from HSBC and LLOYDS across London are conveniently available and prepared to partake in this research. In addition, convenience sampling has assisted the researcher in getting participants for interviews and survey questionnaire wherever he finds them and wherever is

convenient for him to have access to research participants. Furthermore, as one of the objectives of this work is to assess the effectiveness of how bank managers in London perceive, analyse, manage and control risks, convenience sampling assists the researcher in collecting initial primary data regarding perceptions and opinions of banks managers in HSBC and LLOYDS about how they perceive, analyse, manage and control risks.

Although convenience sampling is undertaken extensively, it is subject to influences, selection bias and sampling error not in the control of the researcher that may erode its reliability. Saunders (2012) argues that samples supposedly selected for convenience meet purpose sample selection criteria that are pertinent to the aim and objectives of the research study. It may be that banking organisation that the researcher intends to use for the research is convenient because the researcher may use his existing contacts to negotiate access to reach participants thereby enabling the researcher to overcome the above-discussed sampling deficiencies and thus it can improve research generalisation and enhance its credibility.

3.8.5 Sample Size

As discussed earlier in section 3.8.4, convenience sampling is used in this study that is the subcategory of non-probability sampling. According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012), for all non-probability sampling technique, there are no proper rules for sample size and the issue of sample size is ambiguous. Rather, Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) emphasise the need for developing a logical relationship between the aim and objectives of the research and pertinent sample selection strategy. Patton (2002) reinforces above arguments and argues that for non-probability sampling techniques, sample size depends on the objectives and research questions of the study. This is particularly useful where the researcher intends to gather qualitative data using semi structured interviews. However, Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) have given guidance on minimum non-probability sample size in his book “Research Methods for Business Students”. These guidelines are illustrated in table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Minimum Non Probability Sample Size

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found in Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A., 2012. *Research methods for business students*. 5th Ed. Essex, England: Pearson Education Limited.

Source: Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012)

It is evident from the research questions and objectives of this study (section 3.2.1), the researcher intends to collect qualitative data from semi structured interviews with bank managers and the survey questionnaire. Bearing into mind the above discussed arguments by Patton (2002), the researcher has conducted sufficient interviews and has distributed a significant number of survey questionnaires to risk managers and bank managers in HSBC and LLOYDS across London. Total 25 interviews were conducted with risk managers and bank managers and 300 survey questionnaires were circulated to bank managers and risk managers in HSBC and LLOYDS across London.

3.9 The UK Banking Industry

The UK banking industry is subjugated by a few large banks such as HSBC, Barclays, LLOYDS and the Royal Bank of Scotland. The UK banking market is oligopolistic (the market is highly concentrated by a few big firms) in term of market share for all categories of business. The UK banking sector has gone through a process of consolidation in response to the economic meltdown of 2007. In January 2009, a single major banking group, the LLOYDS group has been created as a result of the consolidation of LLOYDS TBS and the Halifax Bank of Scotland (HBOS).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at:
EconomicsOnline.,2019.*BankingSector*. [online]. Available from: https://www.economicsonline.co.uk/Business_economics/Banks.html.

Fig 3.4, Source: Economics Online (2019)

The banking industry in the UK increased its level of concentration after the economic crisis of 2007. The banking index H-H increased from 1401 in 2007 to 1736 in 2010. H-H index illustrates how much concentrated the market is. Like the EU and USA banks, UK banks are now more regulated after the latest financial meltdown and the collapse of big corporate firms across the globe. Financial stability in the UK is balanced by regulators requiring banks to pass stress tests to guarantee the competitiveness of financial markets and financial stability in the UK. The Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) is answerable for maintaining financial stability in the UK (Economics Online, 2019).

3.10 Banks Selected for this Study

Two large banks such as HSBC and LLOYDS have been selected for this study. Bearing into mind the time constraints, resources and accessibility to the research participants for data collection; the current research aims to assess the usefulness of risk management practices in HSBC and LLOYDS across London instead of the whole UK. It is impracticable and financially not possible to have access to all banks across the whole UK and time constraints to finish research study in the prescribed time frame do not allow the researcher to choose banks across the whole UK. Therefore, this study has focused only on two large banks; HSBC and LLOYDS across London including head offices and various branches of HSBC and LLOYDS in 32 London boroughs in order to make research comprehensive and achieve the aim and objectives of this study.

Though the market share (in fig 3.4, section 3.9) of HSBC is less than the other banks but the main reason for choosing HSBC and LLOYDS is the lack and availability of data from other banks. HSBC and LLOYDS are more open with regards to data collection for academic purposes. During the preliminary visits and contacts to HSBC, Barclays, LLOYDS, Santander, RBS, Nationwide and other banks across London with a request to collect data from their managers, and risk managers, HSBC and LLOYDS were more open and willing to interact with the researcher which allowed the researcher to conduct interviews and distribute questionnaires to bank managers and risk managers in their network branches across London. On the contrary, other banks did not allow the researcher to collect data from them. Some banks had a complex and lengthy process of allowing access and prior permission to collect data for research purposes and some of the banks straight away refused to allow the researcher to conduct interviews with their managers.

Moreover, LLOYDS (893 branches across the UK) and HSBC (1100 branches across the UK) have the largest branch networks across London after Barclays (1058 branches across

the UK) making it convenient for the researcher to have access to a significant number of branches of both banks which enabled the researcher to conduct a significant number of interviews and questionnaires that are necessary for statistical analysis.

In addition, one of the most important factors that is common between HSBC and LLOYDS is a diversified portfolio of products and services that both banks offer to the customers. Both HSBC and LLOYDS are dealing in commercial banking, investment banking, wealth management, retail banking and global private banking. These diversified portfolios of financial products differentiate HSBC and LLOYDS from other banks because the aim of this research is to focus on commercial banks of the UK (section 1.6) which is common in both banks.

Furthermore, though the market share (fig 3.4) of HSBC is smaller than other active banks, HSBC and LLOYDS have a global footprint; HSBC is the largest bank in the UK in terms of market capitalisation, total assets, revenue and risk-weighted assets. For the year 2019, HSBC has a market capitalisation of £131 bn, LLOYDS with £40 bn, NatWest with £26.2, Barclays £25 and Santander with £ 24.2 bn.

Risk-weighted assets that are one of the key determinants of capital adequacy of banks under Basel III; extensive information regarding RWAs and risk management frameworks is available with regards to both banks that caused the researcher to choose both HSBC and LLOYDS for this study.

As both banks are the largest banks in the UK in terms of market capitalisation, total assets and revenue; therefore, both banks have been chosen for this study because both banks are big banks that have led them to be exposed to different kind of risks because of product innovation, technological developments, enhanced regulation, customer centricity and globalisation. Being the largest banks in the UK, both banks are exposed to top and emerging risks that differentiate them from other banks.

The above-discussed reasons have led this study to choose HSBC and LLOYDS to evaluate the effectiveness of their risk management practices which may help banks to prevent the risks from materialising and limit their effect.

As discussed in the conceptual framework (chapter 1, section 1.8), the mixed-method strategy is undertaken in this research after reviewing the literature review and developing the respective research questions of the study. Thus, this research can benefit from both qualitative and quantitative research methods. According to Creswell and Clark (2007) “The mixed methods research provides more comprehensive evidence for studying a research problem than either qualitative or quantitative research alone. The researchers are given

permission to use all of the tools of data collection available rather than being restricted to the types of data collection typically associated with qualitative research or quantitative research. Mixed methods help the researcher in answering the research questions that cannot be answered by qualitative or quantitative approaches alone”.

Moreover, qualitative research in the current research is in the form of semi-structured interviews. On the contrary, quantitative study is based on self-administered questionnaires and secondary data (risk-weighted assets and amount of capital banks hold) is collected from annual reports (financial statements). Therefore, the different sample size for qualitative and quantitative data is used in this research depending on the research objectives of the work.

This study has chosen the bank managers and risk managers from each selected bank across London and risk managers in HSBC and LLOYDS head offices in London to conduct interviews. The reasons for obtaining the qualitative data from the bank managers is based on the fact that responsibility for risk management is not just confined to the staff of risk management department in banks, rather, everyone working for the bank is responsible for risk management.

Similarly, survey questionnaires were distributed to bank managers, risk managers across all branch networks located in 32 London boroughs to explore their opinions about risk management and to appraise the risk perceptions of research participants in order to increase an enhanced understanding of risk management practices in the UK banking industry. Methods for data collection and analysis are outlined in the next sections:

3.11 Research Methods

As discussed earlier (section 3.10); the two most important methods for collecting data are interviews and survey questionnaires. Both interviews and survey questionnaires help the researcher in collecting primary data as this study intends to collect both primary and secondary data (as illustrated in the conceptual framework: chapter 1, section 1.8) to answer the research questions. Primary data is collected when the secondary data is unavailable and unsuitable. However, for this study secondary data is in the form of risk weighted assets and the amount of capital the banks maintain to withstand financial stress that are collected from annual reports of banks. The following sections shed light on the key features of both data collection strategies.

3.11.1 Interviews

An interview is a purposeful discussion between two or more than two participants enabling the interviewer to demonstrate the relationship, to ask unambiguous and concise questions to

which the respondent intends to react and to listen carefully. Moreover, an interview is a widely used method to collect primary qualitative data in which specific information with regards to a particular issue is sought through conversation with respondents. The use of interviews assists the researcher in gathering consistent and suitable data that is pertinent to the research objectives of the study. In addition, when the researcher faces challenges in formulating the research questions and objectives; use of interviews can help in refining research ideas that tend to be consistent with the research questions of the study (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

Depending on the purpose and nature of interactions between research participants; interviews are classified into three types (Robson, 2011).

3.11.2 Structured Interviews

3.11.3 Semi-structured Interviews

3.11.4 Unstructured Interviews

3.11.2 Structured Interviews

These interviews are also known as interviewer administered questionnaires because structured interviews use questionnaires on the basis of a standardised and a predetermined set of questions. The interviewer says each question before the interviewee and then records the responses with pre-coded answers on a standardised schedule. Having a social contact between the interviewer and the respondent; introductory explanations are provided by the interviewer to the respondents thereby enabling the interviewer to read out questions as exactly as reproduced and in the same voice leaving no indication of any bias (Robson, 2011).

3.11.3 Semi Structured Interviews

These interviews are known as qualitative research interviews and are non-standardised as compared to structured or standardised interviews (King, 2004). In these interviews, the researcher contains key questions and a list of themes to be covered in a specific organisational context with regards to the research questions of the study. The flow of conversation between the interviewer and the respondents determine the order of research questions undertaking during the interview. Furthermore, in an attempt to explore the research objectives and research questions; additional questions can be formulated given the nature of the particular research topic. In addition, the interview schedule can also be used for semi-structured interviews apart from including the list of questions and themes to be covered. This interview schedule contains some comments and prompts that help research

participants to open discussion and to further and promote discussion and a few remarks to close up the conversation (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

3.11.4 Unstructured Interviews

These interviews are unceremonious and often referred to as in-depth interviews. No prearranged listing of questions is required in semi-structured interviews. However, the researcher needs to have a clear idea about the events he intends to explore. In this situation, the respondent is given the opportunity to speak clearly about behaviour, beliefs and events with regards to a specific research topic. Thus, this kind of interaction is termed as non-directive and non-informant interview as it is the perceptions of the interviewee that direct the behaviour of interview (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012; Robson, 2011; Rubin and Rubin, 2011; Bryman and Bell, 2011; King, 2004).

3.11.5 Operationalisation of Interviews

This study has conducted exploratory interviews to capture primary qualitative data from bank managers and risk managers across London banks. An exploratory interview is essentially heuristic that helps the researcher in developing research hypotheses and research ideas rather than just to seek statistics and facts (Oppenheim, 2001). While conducting the interview, the researcher puts himself in the situation of the respondent and tries to realize the viewpoints of the respondent. Furthermore, the researcher gives specific consideration to the respondents and listens to them attentively to comprehend the significance of what is being said and how the respondents develop opinions in response to specific research questions (Bryman, 2008; De Vaus, 2002).

In addition, adoption of semi-structured interviews brings the following advantages for this research study: these advantages include

- Giving extra information about the research topic by the researcher assists the respondents in understanding research questions and context of the research area to be explored.
- Facilitating the researcher to get extra information about the research study to improve the research design and develop corresponding research objectives to attain the overall goal of the study.
- Assisting the researcher to gain access to a number of respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS across all 32 London boroughs.

All interviews undertaken for this research study are presented in the next chapter 4.

3.11.6 Survey Questionnaires

A survey questionnaire is an effective technique of collecting data which enables the researcher to determine what data is necessary, what data source to be utilised to capture data and how the specific variables to be developed and computed (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013). According to De Vaus (2002), a survey questionnaire is an efficient research instrument comprising of a series of prompts and research questions to seek information from research participants. Furthermore, a properly designed and fairly implemented survey questionnaire is an extensively used instrument to obtain accurate and pertinent data in a systematic way (Cooper and Schindler, 2011). When designing a questionnaire; it is important to bear into mind the research questions and the aim and objectives of the study in order to develop a comprehensive questionnaire covering key research themes underpinning research questions. According to De Vaus (2002), survey questionnaires are rigorous, accurate and efficient means of seeking pertinent information about a given population if they are properly developed and implemented. Depending on the research methodology chosen and the sample size, results can be drawn relatively quickly and accurately to a large extent.

Taking into account the following key considerations considered by various researchers; the survey questionnaire is adopted in this work to pull together primary quantitative data for quantitative analysis.

- Survey questionnaire plays a dominant role in conducting the research as banks and financial firms make public less information about risk management in their financial statements.
- The questionnaire offers enough time to respondents and allows them sufficient time to respond to questions with their comfort and ease.
- It appears to be the most effective and efficient mean of data collection from the respondents in the UK banking sector by keeping in mind that this is the more convenient and likely to contact respondents across the UK through sending them questionnaires via email, by post and by hand.

There are different ways of primary data collection by employing a questionnaire. A questionnaire can be self administered, electronically sent and can be distributed by post and by hand. Each method of survey distribution has definite characteristics which should be considered when choosing an appropriate method of distributing a survey questionnaire.

According to Bryman and Bell (2011) and Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012), self-administered or self-completed questionnaires are concluded and responded straight away by

the respondents. Different means of distribution are used to send the questionnaires. Internet and Ethernet are employed to forward and gather web based questionnaires. By contrast, postal questionnaires are sent and received by post. Self-delivery and self-collection of questionnaires is a widely used self-administered questionnaire in business research. The researcher sends questionnaires in person to the research participants and seeks to collect them afterwards.

In this study, questionnaires have been distributed and sought responses by hand and by email as they offer the following advantages.

- It facilitates the respondents to give unbiased answers to the research questions.
- Required information can be obtained within a limited time span by distributing questionnaires
- It allows more time to the participants to think and answer the questions when questionnaires are distributed to them personally and research theme is explained them appropriately.
- It helps in improving the response rate.
- It assists the researcher to promptly address the queries of bank managers regarding the research questions handed over to them.

3.11.7 Structure of Survey Questionnaire

Design and layout of a questionnaire play a considerable part in the reliability, validity and response rate of collected data. Inappropriately designed and ambiguous questionnaire can lead to miss interpretation of a research theme by respondents that may create hurdles in meeting the research objectives of the research. Oppenheim (1992) requires the researchers to follow the following steps when conducting a survey questionnaire to develop the soundness, reliability and enhance the response rate of respondents.

- Conducting a pilot study can be a valuable contribution to determine the appropriateness of the questionnaire with regards to the specific research questions.
- To make a clear and unambiguous illustration of the rationale of the survey study and appealing draft of the instrument.

- Requiring the researcher to have a full grasp of the research theme, what type of information required, its aim and objectives and what type of respondents e.g. bank staff, bank managers and risk managers.
- Use of simple language in developing questionnaire without grammatical errors can assist in conveying the clear message of conducting research to potential respondents thereby facilitating them in responding to research questions.
- Planned and organised execution of survey distribution and its return is a key to getting a significant response rate.

By bearing into mind the above discussed points; the current study has taken into consideration the following key points in order to incorporate different matters contained within questionnaire of the research work.

- Concise, clear and purposeful closed-ended questions are used in developing the questionnaire for collecting relevant data and maximising response rate.
- Confidentiality and the privacy of respondents and responses of each respondent are ensured by using a locked safe and files containing their responses and details are password protected.
- To create and uphold the interest of research participants in a subject matter; all the questions are coherent, transparent and clearly illustrated.

By keeping the above discussed arguments proposed by Bryman and Bell (2011) in view; the questions included in the survey questionnaire have been developed from the current literature on risk management. The existing literature of various commentators on risk management has been reviewed to develop research questions including the work of Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi (2012), Al-Tamimi (2002) and Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei (2007).

Survey questionnaire of this research comprises of three sections; the format of which is reproduced in appendix 3.

Part 1. The first part of questionnaire sheds light on the demographic characteristics of research participants including their name, bank name, demography, position and work experience.

Part 2. The second part of the survey questionnaire aims to determine the main study variables underpinning the research questions. This section comprises of sixty two closed-ended questions. Majority of the questions are evaluated by a Likert scale (five-point)

illustrating as strongly disagree =1 to strongly agree=5. All research respondents were requested to choose a specific option pertaining to risk management practices currently adopted in their banks. However, all respondents were requested to add additional requirements at the end of each question if they wished to provide extra information.

Part 3. This part refers to seeking information from respondents about various risks banks encounter, risk management methods and models employed by banks to identify, assess, and respond to assessed risks and to manage risks. The ordinal scale is used in most of the questions to get responses of participants within the context of YES or No options. Part three aims to seek details about various fundamentals of risk management framework adopted in banks including identification of risk, assessment and analysis of risk, monitoring of risk, and controlling of risk.

Q57 to Q59 consists of questions in which respondents are offered a list of responses/options requiring them to choose one of the best options after considering all possible scenarios according to their understanding and grasp on the subject matter. These questions underpin Basel III, market risk, operational risk and capital requirements of banks.

Table 3.2. A Snapshot of Likert Scale Used in Questionnaire

Values	Explanation
1	Strongly Disagree: It illustrates that the specific statement under consideration is inconsequential, inappropriate and the respondent strongly opposes and completely disagrees with the risk management guidelines followed by the bank where the respondent works which is based on his or her experience and knowledge.
2	Disagree: This scale explains that the research participant holds a different opinion on what the specific question is asked by the researcher on risk management. Research participant’s understanding of risk management framework utilised in the bank and his/her expertise causes him to conclude that the specific assertion is not preferred, insignificant and inappropriate.
3	Neutral: In a neutral scale, a participant is not willing to take any position on subject matter information and tries to be unbiased and shows the impartial attitude towards what is requested to respond to.

4	Agree: Agree scale explains the reasonableness, appropriateness and significance of specific question on risk management framework used by banks to identify and deal with risks. The respondent wishes to take a specific stance and tends to agree with a particular statement on the subject matter.
5	Strongly Agree: Strongly agree means the respondent expressly endorses the specific statement on risk management and advocates the appropriateness and reasonableness of what the research questions tend to illustrate and explain. A sound understanding/knowledge of the respondent on risk management and his/her expertise in specific filed causes him/her to conclude the authenticity and reasonableness of specific research question.

3.11.8 Levels and Characteristics of Measurement

A variable can be measured by one of the four different levels of measurement. Understanding of measurement scales assists the researcher in phrasing the research questions and determining what statistical analysis is appropriate in analysing data. De Vaus (2002) proposes four stages of measurement including nominal scale, ordinal scale, interval scale and ratio scale. Interval and Ratio scales are also called as a continuous scale. These measurement scales are illustrated as

Nominal Scale: Nominal scales are also called labels that are used for labelling variables without any quantitative value. Qualitative variables are measured by using a nominal scale that creates frequency data that tends to be subject to non parametric test.

Ordinal Scale: With the ordinal scale; the order of the values is illustrated by what is important and what is significant, but the difference and significant is not known. With ordinal scale, it cannot be quantified the difference between each one.

Interval Scale: Interval scale is a quantitative measurement scale created by units of equal size. With the interval scale; there is an order between values and the difference between two values is significant.

Ratio Scale: It is a measurement scale that tells about order and exact values between units. This scale has an absolute zero allowing for a wide range of inferential and descriptive statistics to be applied to variables.

3.11.9 Operationalisation of Questionnaires

Operationalisation is vital to capture data with the help of a survey questionnaire (Bryman and Bell, 2011; Davis and Cosenza, 1993). The questionnaire is largely formed by the researcher which depends on the findings deduced from the available literature on risk

management, published articles on the banking industry, books on risk management, and surveys on risk management. Survey question by Khan and Ahmed (2001) assisted the researcher in designing the research questions of this study. Furthermore, the prior knowledge of the researcher on risk management has facilitated in developing a survey questionnaire.

The survey questionnaire (see appendix) comprises of total sixty questions, most of the questions have varied sub statements to augment the knowledge of the researcher and respondents on the subject matter information. The questionnaire is constituted by closed-ended questions in a way that enables respondents to answer all questions easily with a box ticking responses required of participants.

Operational definitions of all variables utilised in this research are illustrated in the following table. All variables for this research have been derived from the work of Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei (2007) & Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi (2012).

Table 3.3. Operationalisation of the Research Variables

Variables	Explanation
Understanding of risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a common comprehension of risk management in the bank. • The bank maintains an adequate structure for recognising different risks. • Responsibility for understanding risk and risk management is evidently defined across the bank. • Accountability for understanding risk and risk management is clearly defined and set out across the bank.
Identification of risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The bank conducts a systematic and detailed classification of risks it faces pertinent to the research questions of the study. • The bank faces difficulties in prioritising risks. • The bank has envisaged and established techniques for methodical recognition of opportunities. • It is very important for banks to implement largely accepted models for identifying risks.
Assessment and Analysis of Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The bank evaluates the probability of risks happening.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The bank uses quantitative methods of risk analysis. • Qualitative analysis methods are also used by the bank to assess risks. • Assessment of bank to analyse risks includes cost benefit analysis of coping with risks.
Monitoring and Controlling of Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overseeing the potency of risk management is a key component of the reporting process of management. • The bank has established an appropriate system of internal control depending on the extent of risks it encounters. • A robust system of reporting on risk management is in place covering the whole hierarchy of management from bottom to top • The risk response strategies of the banks consist of an assessment of the usefulness of the current controls and evaluation of its risk management systems.
Managing Market Risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The strategy for managing the market risk is envisaged by the board of directors that is implemented by top management in the banks in the form of guidelines and policies. • The risk exposures with regards to the market risk are retained at sensible levels and are in accordance with the capital bank holds. • There is a robust system for managing the market risk in the form of policies, infrastructure and processes for managing market risk.
Managing Credit Risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The credit risk strategy is envisaged by the board of directors that is implemented by top management in the banks in the form of policies. • The bank adopts a credit risk system to assess the creditworthiness of clients across all its credit activities. • The bank has a sound system of risk management in the form of policies,

	<p>infrastructure and processes for managing credit risk.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Credit portfolio is monitored by the bank regularly and takes action in case of any unpleasant credit event. • A periodic report of credit risk is prepared by bank regularly.
Managing Operational Risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bank adopts a comprehensive set of policies, guidelines and policies for dealing with operational risk. • All categories of operational risk are defined and contemplated by executive management and the board. • The bank ensures business continuity planning in case of any business disruption in order to minimise losses and operate as a going concern. • A periodic report of operational risk is prepared by bank regularly.
Managing Liquidity Risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bank adopts a comprehensive set of policies, guidelines and policies for dealing with the liquidity risk. • The bank has a sound system of risk management recognized by the board in the form of policies, infrastructure and processes for managing market risk.
Risk Management Practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executive management of the bank frequently appraises the performance of its operations with regards to overseeing its system of dealing with risks. • The bank has a stringent system of receiving views on its strategies on risk management. • Risk management processes and strategies are documented and appropriate training is provided to staff responsible for risk management. • Bearing into mind the recent financial crisis of 2007-08, banks hold enough capital to absorb financial shocks if capital ratio to risk

	weighted assets (RWA) is equal to capital adequacy ratio set by Bank of England.
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Before developing the main questionnaire to capture data, a pilot study has been conducted to establish the appropriateness of the survey questionnaire. The pilot study is outlined in the following section.

3.11.10 Pilot Study

It is a small study before conducting the main research to determine the practicability and to refine the research methodology. Therefore, it is advertently appropriate to conduct a pilot study before undertaking a survey questionnaire with the target population (De Vaus, 2002). According to various research scholars including (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013; Oppenheim, 1992), a pilot study assists the researcher in the following ways:

- It facilitates the researcher in evaluating the validity and reliability of research questions before sending a questionnaire to respondents for data collection.
- It helps in improving and refining a format and contents of a questionnaire to seek a significant number of responses.
- A pilot study is vital in business research to determine the uniformity of interpretation of all respondents and demonstrating whether the research participants are answering the questions accurately bearing into mind the research objectives of the research.
- A pilot study is used to measure the sufficiency of the stream of questions in the questionnaire and determine any room for refinement.
- In case of any confusion and misunderstanding towards any research question on the respondents' end, pilot testing helps in removing the confusion and misunderstanding as early as possible enabling the researcher to determine the reasonableness, clarity and overall presentation in terms of depth of information sought and the length of the research questions.

Bearing into mind all useful points illustrated above, a pilot study of the survey questionnaire is also undertaken in this research and its findings are taken into consideration before distributing the survey questionnaires to various respondents across London.

The initial draft of the survey questionnaire for this research study was reviewed and approved by the researcher's Lead Supervisor (DoS). The first section of the pilot study questionnaire referred to discussing the demographic features of the research participants. The second part of this questionnaire shed light on explaining nine key variables derived from the current literature on risk management and reviewing other research work (journal

articles, PhD thesis, books) in the banking industry. The third part was about underlining different key risks encountered by HSBC and LLOYDS including different models and frameworks utilised by banks to cope with risks. In addition to these three parts, two open ended questions were set out on a different page along with the main questionnaire requesting respondents to give feedback on format and design of questions included in the questionnaire. Their feedback and suggestions helped the researcher in improving the questionnaire that was ultimately distributed to 300 bank managers and risk managers belonging to HSBC and Barclays in London.

Prior consent was sought from twenty-five bank managers and risk managers working in HSBC and LLOYDS to participate in a pilot study for this research who confirmed their participation for pilot testing. Subsequently, the questionnaire was distributed to them via email, by post and by hand. Twenty one out of twenty five respondents from different branches of HSBC and Barclays in various locations in London responded. The response rate was 84% that was reasonable and acceptable in business research according to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012).

Cronbach's alpha was used to evaluate the reliability and internal consistency of different variables underpinning risk management. It is widely used and most efficient statistical tool used by researchers to test the reliability of various variables (Selltiz et al, 1976). Its values range from 0.5 to 0.7. If the value of Cronbach alpha is more than 0.7 then data is considered to be reliable and consistent (Nunnally, 1978). In addition to using Cronbach's alpha; correlation analysis was also used to determine the relationship between variables of this research study.

Table 3.4. Reliability Table of Different Variables based on the Pilot Study

Serial No	Variables	Coefficients:Cronbach alpha
1	Understanding of risks	0.76
2	Identification of risks	0.72
3	Assessment and analysis of risks	0.79
4	Monitoring and controlling of risks	0.71
5	Managing market risk	0.73
6	Managing credit risk	0.73
7	Managing operational risk	0.71
8	Managing liquidity risk	0.75
9	Risk management practices	0.72

It is evident from pilot study results illustrated in table 3.4 that Cronbach's alpha for each variable is greater than 0.7 which reflects the internal consistency and reliability of all variables underlined in the above table.

Following the reliability investigation of the pilot study, it demonstrated the trust in formulating a final version of the collection instrument (questionnaire). Data used for the pilot study was not included in the findings of the questionnaire.

Based on the results of the pilot study and feedback from banking professionals; the current research concluded that the final research questionnaire was appropriate and reasonable in responding to the research questions. Ultimately, before going for main data collection the final questionnaire was revisited, discussed and agreed by the researcher's Lead supervisor (DoS).

3.11.11 Data Collection thorough Survey Questionnaire

As discussed earlier in section 3.11.10, 300 hundred managers and risk managers from HSBC and LLOYDS working in 32 locations across London and corresponding head offices have been chosen to seek their responses on the survey questionnaire. Questionnaire responses have been received by email and self-collection method of the questionnaire has also been adopted in this study.

A reference letter (for HSBC and LLOYDS) for data collection has been obtained from the researcher's Lead Supervisor that has facilitated the researcher in maintaining the legitimacy of this study and assisted in getting access to respondents (see appendix). A covering letter (see appendix) had been sent to research participants along with the main questionnaire to encourage their voluntary participation to investigate into matter or any sensitive information that the respondents might not willing or reluctant to respond to because of the sensitivity of matter under investigation. A pilot study had been conducted to guarantee the usefulness and reliability of the questionnaire and is discussed in the last section 3.11.10.

Before distributing the survey questionnaire, a database of chosen banks i.e. HSBC and LLOYDS and their corresponding branches across London have been developed. Preliminary details about the surveyed banks have been obtained from their websites. All chosen banks were contacted by the researcher during February 2019 and April 2019 to get their consent for research participation and to book an appointment with them at their convenience for collecting data. After seeking all details including contact details, date and time of appointment, the survey questionnaire has been undertaken during April 2019 and July 2019.

3.11.12 Response Rate

As expounded in section 3.11.10, the current research has used self delivery and self collection method of distributing and receiving questionnaire responses to maximise the response rate. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) point out that self administered questionnaires have fewer problems with regards to the response rate. However, after distributing three hundred questionnaires for this study; two hundred and sixty five survey responses have been received back out of which fifteen questionnaires received are incomplete and thus are excluded when analysing survey responses. Therefore, after excluding incomplete fifteen responses; two hundred and fifty questionnaires are found appropriate, reasonable, and adequate and show a good response rate of 83 %.

Distributed	Received	Not Valid	Valid	Response Rate
300	265	15	250	83 %

According to Babbie (2010), a response rate of 70% or greater than 70% in survey study sounds good and reasonable to draw an acceptable conclusion on the subject matter. Moreover, the higher response rate has been received in this study than other studies undertaken on risk management by Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi (2012); Hassan (2011) and Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei (2007).

Next section sets out various data analysis techniques for the survey data:

3.12 Statistical Techniques used for Survey Questionnaire in this Study

Various statistical techniques have been undertaken in this research to examine the survey questionnaire. Descriptive statistics have been employed to express the questionnaire data. Afterwards, various statistical tools including multiple regression analysis, Pearson correlation, and descriptive statistics have been used to analyse survey questionnaire with the SPSS 25.0 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences).

3.12.1 Descriptive Statistics

These statistics assist the researcher in comparing and describing variables numerically. Research questions, the aim and objectives of the research facilitate the choice of statistics to be used to analyse data. Two aspects of variables need to be focussed while describing data:

- the central tendency
- the dispersion

With describing the central tendency; it is a generic practice of describing values in terms of common, middle and average. Central tendency is measured in three ways:

- Mode: the value that appears most repeatedly
- Median: middle value or midpoint after data is ranked
- Mean: Average value that comprises of all data values in its calculation

Describing the dispersion is equally important as describing the central tendency of numerical and categorical data. Two frequently used methods to describe the dispersion are

- Inter-quartile range: that is the variation within the middle 50% of values
- Standard Deviation (SD): Standard deviation illustrates the degree to which values fluctuate from the mean (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012; Groebner et al. (2005).

Both standard deviation and mean are frequently used models in descriptive statistics to characterise the underlying features of variables in business research (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Dancey and Reidy, 2004). A large value of standard deviation indicates that observations in data are extensively scattered from the mean. On the other hand, a small standard deviation illustrates the proximity of observations in data to the mean. Both higher and smaller values of SD enable the researcher to reach conclusions about the data (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Pallant, 2001).

Descriptive analysis has been undertaken to calculate standard deviation and mean for independent and dependent variables developed in this research work. The variability of variables has been determined by SD whereas mean values have helped in measuring the average response.

3.12.2 Reliability and Internal Consistency of Variables

Validity is about whether the questionnaire and interview measure what they are supposed to measure irrespective of what method is employed to collect data. Oppenheim (2001) proposes three key components of reliability such as explicability, precision and consistency of results. According to Bryman and Bell (2011, p.158), “Reliability refers to the consistency of a measure or a concept”. Cooper and Schindler (2011) are of the view that the determination of reliability refers to reducing the likelihood of prejudiced findings. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) advocate above claims arguing that internal consistency is about measuring the consistency of research responses either across all questions from the questionnaire or a group of research questions. Internal consistency tends to correlate

responses to research questions (scale items) with one another in a questionnaire. Reliability of data is determined by using a statistic tool e.g. Cronbach's alpha test (Gujarati and Porter, 2009; Pallant, 2001).

As discussed earlier in section 3.11.10; Cronbach's alpha is a widely used model to determine the reliability and internal consistency of various variables. Its alpha values range from 0 to 1 demonstrating the extent of how reliable and consistent are the research variables of the study (Selltiz, Wrightsman and Cook, 1976). Higher the alpha value i.e if alpha coefficient > 0.7 more reliable will be the variable and vice versa (Hassan, 2011; Nunnally, 1978; Selltiz, Wrightsman and Cook, 1976). However, some business researchers have accepted relatively a smaller alpha value of 0.60 or greater than 0.6 (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013; Peter, 1979).

In the current research, the reliability of variables has been determined by Cronbach's alpha test with the SPSS software as is reflected in the following table 3.6.

Table 3.5. Reliability Analysis

Serial No	Variables	Cronbach's Alpha Coefficients
1	Understanding of risks	0.71
2	Identification of risks	0.74
3	Assessment and analysis of risks	0.72
4	Monitoring and controlling of risks	0.73
5	Management of market risk	0.79
6	Management of credit risk	0.71
7	Management of operational risk	0.77
8	Management of liquidity risk	0.76
9	Risk management practices	0.75

Benchmark: Benchmark Cronbach's alpha value for the reliability of variables is 0.7 or greater than 0.7.

Above table 3.5 shows that Cronbach's alpha value for all variables is higher than the tolerable value 0.7 which reflects the reliability of data gathered through the questionnaire. Moreover, the alpha value for this study variables is concordant with arguments discussed above for reliability of data and other past research studies undertaken by Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi (2012) with the alpha value of 0.713 to 0.892, Al Tamimi and Al Mazrooei (2007) with the alpha value of 0.620 to 0.689 and Hassan (2011) with an alpha value of 0.621 to 0.688.

In addition, the reliability and validity of the contents of the survey questionnaire are also ensured by the following key factors:

- The pilot study has been undertaken before finalising the survey questionnaire that has assisted the researcher in scrutinising and refining the contents of the questionnaire.
- Use of covering letter illustrating the goal of conducting the study and maintaining the privacy of answers has increased the validity and reliability of data collected.
- Feedbacks and suggestions from banking professionals and experts on risk management have assisted the researcher in enhancing the validity of the questionnaire.
- Statistical validity has been enhanced by extensive reading of books, journal articles and publication on risk management that the researcher has done over the period of time and also by attending and participating in various workshops on data analysis software (SPSS, NVIVO) and techniques arranged by UWS through Eventbrite.
- Use of mixed methods to answer the research questions has validated the research questions and collected data has been checked for errors and mistakes.
- Various statistical techniques including multiple regression analysis, multicollinearity, Pearson correlation, reliability and descriptive statistics have been employed to draw an appropriate conclusion of the questionnaire data.

3.12.3 Multicollinearity

Multicollinearity is a statistical concept that is used in business research that indicates a linear association between two or more independent variables. In a multiple regression techniques, it is the occurrence of intercorrelations among independent variables. It assists the researcher in identifying misleading and skewed results particularly when the researcher intends to determine how effectively each independent variable is utilised to contemplate and predict the dependent variable in a statistical model (Kenton, 2020).

Singularity is an acute instance of multicollinearity in which two independent variables are perfectly correlated for which coefficient of correlation = 1 (Garson, 2012; Gujarati and Porter, 2009). According to Groebner et al., (2005), two frequently used models including variance inflation factor (VIF) with tolerance values and correlation coefficient are used to investigate the multicollinearity between variables.

The available literature on the multicollinearity does not specify a standard coefficient value for multicollinearity. If the value of $VIF < 0$ there is no problem of multicollinearity. On the contrary, Groebner et al., (2005) point out that in order to evade the difficulty of multicollinearity the value of VIF should be 5 or < 5 .

In the current research, variance inflation factor and correlation coefficients have been employed to check the multicollinearity between independent variables. The underneath table fleshes out the finding of multicollinearity analysis of independent variable.

Table 3.6. Multicollinearity Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
(constant)	.155	.273		.569	.575		
Risk understanding	.118	.039	.177	3.271	.001	.689	1.460
Risk identification	.154	.044	.171	3.466	.002	.827	1.214
Risk assessment and analysis	.118	.046	.129	2.449	.017	.728	1.376
Risk monitoring & controlling	.083	.044	.096	1.982	.047	.878	1.135
Managing market risk	.081	.029	.136	2.778	.007	.805	1.244
Managing credit risk	.218	.039	.308	5.617	.000	.663	1.523
Managing liquidity risk	.106	.039	.138	2.776	.007	.844	1.179
Managing operational risk	.123	.033	.187	3.578	.000	.821	1.246

Benchmark: Approved value of VIF is 10 or <10

It is apparent from collinearity statistics in the above table that the tolerance values are between .663 and .878. Likewise, values of variance information factor for all variables range from 1.179 to 1.460 and are not greater than 1.5. Therefore, on the basis of multicollinearity analysis, both tolerance and VIF confirm that there is no problem of multicollinearity in the data used for this study (Garson, 2012).

Besides running the collinearity analysis (multicollinearity) in this study, correlation coefficients between all independents variables have been determined. Results of Pearson correlation corroborate the values of VIF and tolerance as illustrated in above table 3.6 and thus indicative of not having a problem with multicollinearity underpinning independent variables of this study.

The following section sheds light on the brief description of Pearson correlation:

3.12.4 Pearson Correlation

Correlation analysis is a statistical model used by the researchers to explore the relationship between variables. This model is also undertaken to assess the strength of the association between variables and their value ranges from -1 to +1. The greater value of the correlation coefficient shows a strong relationship whereas a negative value or lower value is indicative of a weak negative relationship between variables (Gujarati and Porter, 2009).

Correlation statistics are of three kinds such as Spearman correlation, Pearson correlation and Kendall rank correlation (Gujarati and Porter, 2009; Garson, 2012).

Pearson correlation is commonly used correlation coefficient and tends to determine the linear relationship between variables. Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) and Pallant (2001) have assumed that variables are investigated either on interval or ratio scale of measurement in Pearson correlation and it tests the extent of in what proportions variables are correlated to each other. Gujarati and Porter (2009) support the above arguments and argue that the Pearson correlation is solely restricted to establish the strength of the relationship between variables of the study. Pearson correlation is undertaken to determine the relationship between independent and dependent variables of current research.

Regression and correlation analyses have been undertaken in this study to test the hypotheses and are discussed in chapter four. The following section sheds the spotlight on multiple regression analysis in detail.

3.12.5 Regression Analysis

This analysis is employed to determine the relationship between a single dependent variable and several independent variables (Gujarati and Porter, 2009; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007).

Multiple regression analysis used in this study is based on the following research equation:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Here, β_1 and β_2 are the regression coefficients which indicate the value at which dependent variable changes with the changes in independent variables. Y is the value of the dependent variable whereas X1 and X2 shows the values of independent variables.

The ordinary least square (OLS) technique has been adopted in this study to determine the significance of the relationship between dependent and independent variables. OLS is a widely accepted technique and extensively endorsed by various researchers in their pertinent research studies (Hassan, 2011).

It is vital to point out here that fundamental assumptions including reliability and multicollinearity with regards to data screening and data sorting have been undertaken

effectively before commencing data analysing by using SPSS. More discussion on regression analysis and its findings are expounded in section 4.9.2 of chapter 4.

3.13 Secondary Quantitative Data: Collection and Analysis Procedures

Secondary data is the data that is collected by an organisation for specific purposes at another point of time other than the current research and is in quantitative form. There can be various sources of secondary data collection for instance past research, official statistics, official publications published by various state and federal departments, annual reports/accounts of banks and official websites of various institutions etc (Sekaran and Bougie, 2013; Cooper and Schindler, 2011).

As one of the research questions are: is there any relationship between risk management and the amount of capital banks (LLOYDS and HSBC) hold. Therefore, secondary quantitative data has been collected to determine the relationship between risk management and capital adequacy of banks.

Risk-Weighted Assets (RWAs) of HSBC and LLOYDS have been chosen as a proxy to risk management. Amount of capital HSBC and LLOYDS maintain has been chosen on the basis of Basel III definition. The amount of capital that has been chosen in this study is the total bank capital comprising of common equity tier 1 capital and tier 2 capital (Grant, 2019, LLOYDS Annual Report, 2019). Tier1 capital is the most important source of bank's capital consisting of disclosed reserves and retained earnings. This money is saved by banks to carry on functioning through all risky transactions such as lending, investing and trading. Tier 2 capital consists of hybrid instruments such as undisclosed reserves, loan losses and revaluation reserves.

Ten years of secondary data with regards to RWA and the amount of capital have been collected from annual reports of HSBC and LLOYDS covering period 2010-2019. RWAs have been used by many researchers to determine the capital adequacy of banks. Vallascas and Hagedorff (2013) used an international sample of multinational banks from 2000 to 2010 to evaluate the risk sensitivity of minimum capital requirements with the help of risk-weighted assets (RWAs).

Risk susceptible capital needs are the basis of the global capital guidelines. The objective of using RWAs is to stop potential shareholders from investing in risky assets to capitalize on underpriced government bailout guarantees. The effectiveness of risk based capital requirements depends on the degree to which capital requirements are a true picture of the risk portfolio of banks (Rochet, 1992; Kim and Santomero, 1988).

In order to evaluate the association between risk management and capital adequacy of banks, Pearson correlation and regressions analysis have been used in this study. Findings of both tests are reported in section 4.11.

3.13.1 Normality of data

Normality tests are undertaken in statistics to investigate if the data is appropriately modelled by a normal distribution and to explore whether the data is normally distributed around the mean. A detailed examination of the normality of data is a prerequisite for many statistical models used by researchers to analyse data because normal data is a fundamental driving factor in the testing of parameters. There are many models of testing the normality of data such as skewness, kurtosis, Shapiro–Wilk test, Q-Q plot, histogram, mean, box plot and standard deviation (Kenton, W, 2019 and Chen, J, 2019).

This study has used skewness, kurtosis and Shapiro-Wilko test to assess the normality of data with the help of SPSS. Skewness is a distortion in the normal distribution or symmetrical bell curve in a given set of data. Skewness appears when the distribution curve is shifted to left or right. Skewness is quantified as a demonstration of the degree to which a given distribution fluctuates from the normal distribution. Whereas, Kurtosis determines how heavily the tails of a distribution fluctuate from the tails of a normal distribution and it explores the extreme values in distribution tails.

The Shapiro-Wilko test assists the researcher in determining if a random sample comes from the normal distribution. A small value of this test indicates that sample is not normally distributed and the researcher rejects the null hypothesis that the research population is normally distributed if its values are under a certain threshold (Cramer, 1998). The threshold for skewness, kurtosis and Shapiro-Wilko test are illustrated as follows:

For skewness and Kurtosis (z-values should be -1.96 to +1.96). For the Shapiro-Wilko test, the p-value or sig value should be higher than 0.05. Data is not always been perfectly normally distributed but it is approximately normally distributed. The following tables shed light on the results of descriptive statistics.

Table 3.7

Descriptives				
			Statistic	Std. Error
Total Capital (Tier1 & Tier2): HSBC \$m	Mean		174664.10	5024.313
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	163298.31	
		Upper Bound	186029.89	
	5% Trimmed Mean		175313.83	
	Median		175570.00	
	Variance		252437189.878	
	Std. Deviation		15888.272	
	Minimum		143624	
	Maximum		194009	
	Range		50385	
	Interquartile Range		24564	
	Skewness		-.647	.687
	Kurtosis		.471	1.334
	Total Capital (Tier1 & Tier2): LLOYDS \$m	Mean		42895.70
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	38142.34	
		Upper Bound	47649.06	
5% Trimmed Mean		42673.22		
Median		41167.00		
Variance		44152643.344		
Std. Deviation		6644.746		
Minimum		34800		
Maximum		54996		
Range		20196		
Interquartile Range		8635		
Skewness		1.035	.687	
Kurtosis		.173	1.334	

The z-values for skewness and kurtosis are computed by dividing values of skewness & kurtosis by their corresponding std. errors. Therefore, from the above table, the z-values are computed as

For Total capital in case of HSBC,

The z-value (skewness) = $-.647/.687 = -0.94$

The z-value (kurtosis) = $.471/1.334 = 0.35$

For total capital in case of LLOYDS,

The z-value (skewness) = $1.035/.687 = 1.50$

The z-value (kurtosis) = $.173/1.334 = .13$

Table 3.8

Descriptives				
			Statistic	Std. Error
Risk-Weighted Assets (HSBC) \$m	Mean		929651.40	102657.632
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	697423.70	
		Upper Bound	1161879.10	
	5% Trimmed Mean		959053.78	
	Median		981995.00	
	Variance		105385893459.16	
	Std. Deviation		324631.935	
	Minimum		110295	
	Maximum		1219765	
	Range		1109470	
	Interquartile Range		291601	
	Skewness		-.982	.687
	Kurtosis		1.839	1.334
	Risk-Weighted Assets (LLOYDS) \$m	Mean		248387.70
95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Lower Bound	212859.17	
		Upper Bound	283916.23	
5% Trimmed Mean		245110.11		
Median		231240.50		
Variance		2466657426.233		
Std. Deviation		49665.455		
Minimum		203431		
Maximum		352341		
Range		148910		
Interquartile Range		71725		
Skewness		1.251	.687	
Kurtosis		.774	1.334	

From the above table, the z-values are computed as

For Risk-Weighted Assets in case of HSBC,

The z-value (skewness) = $-.982/.687 = -1.4$

The z-value (kurtosis) = $1.839/1.334 = 1.38$

For Risk-Weighted Assets in case of LLOYDS,

The z-value (skewness) = $1.251/.687 = 1.82$

The z-value (kurtosis) = $.774/1.334 = .58$

All z-values in the above tables are within range of -1.96 to +1.96. Therefore, in terms of skewness & kurtosis, data for total capital and risk-weighted assets is a little bit skewed and kurtotic but it does not differ significantly from normality. Hence, it is assumed that data is normally distributed with regards to skewness and kurtosis.

Table 3.9

Tests of Normality						
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	Df	Sig.
Total Capital (Tier1 & Tier2): HSBC \$m	.150	10	.200*	.939	10	.546
Total Capital (Tier1 & Tier2): LLOYDS \$m	.238	10	.114	.877	10	.120

Table 3.10

Tests of Normality						
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	Df	Sig.
Risk-Weighted Assets (HSBC) \$m	.295	10	.014	.766	10	.006
Risk-Weighted Assets (LLOYDS) \$m	.197	10	.200*	.854	10	.065

Shapiro-Wilko Test

The null hypothesis for the normality test is that the data is normally distributed. If the p-value (sig) is less than 0.05 then the null hypothesis is rejected.

The tables 3.9 & 3.10 show that the p-values for total capital with regards to HSBC & LLOYDS are .546 & .120 respectively which are greater than 0.05. Similarly, risk-weighted assets of HSBC & LLOYDS have p-values of .006 & .065 respectively which are also greater than .05 that is a threshold determined for Shapiro-wilko test for testing the normality of data. This study keeps the null hypothesis because the p values (sig) in the above tables are higher than 0.05 which indicate that the data is approximately normally distributed. Based on the findings of skewness, kurtosis and the Shapiro-wilko test, it can be argued that data is not perfectly distributed but the data is approximately normally distributed.

3.14 Interviews for this study

As previously outlined in section 3.10, the current study undertook face to face interviews with bank managers and risk managers working in HSBC and LLOYDS in order to get their opinions and perceptions on risk management practices followed by the banking sector. The target of the researcher was to conduct interviews with the managers and risk managers working in various branches across London and also with risk managers specifically working in HSBC head office and LLOYDS head office. The motive behind selecting only managers, risk managers and risk managers from head offices was the selection of those personnel who had a deep understanding of risk management in the banks. Therefore, the respondents selected for this study held key positions in the banks such as middle and top management.

3.14.1 Interview Structure

Keeping in mind the seniority of interviewees, a precise list for the research questions was formed by the researcher within the context of the original research questions and research hypotheses. An interview schedule (see appendix) was also constituted consisting of both open ended and closed ended questions and was sent to interviewees along with the interview questions to make them aware and enhance their understanding of subject matter requiring their responses. There are total twenty three questions in the interview script and it mainly covers the same questions as in survey questionnaire because the aim of conducting interviews was to prove or disprove the conclusions drawn from questionnaire data analysis. Furthermore, before undertaking interview data collection, all interview questions were discussed, reviewed and approved by the researcher's lead supervisor (DoS).

3.14.2 Interview Participants

Using initial connections and contacts, participation request for an interview was sent to thirty respondents of selected banks by the researcher and gave them a brief outline of the subject matter and purpose of conducting this research. According to Rubin (2011), it is vital to choose the research participants for an interview who readily and willingly willing to give opinions in response to the research questions. Out of thirty persons, twenty five persons showed their readiness for contribution. Subsequently, prior appointment (time and date for interviews) was booked with all twenty five agreed participants by phone and personally as per their ease and convenience.

This research conducted interviews with twenty five bank managers, risk managers and risk managers belonging to HSBC and LLOYDS and their respective branches across London. All interviewees were ensured that data collected would be for academic purposes only and

their personal and contact particulars would not be shared to other people giving them openness to share their views and opinions on subject matter freely. Before commencing interviews, the researcher gave fifteen minutes presentations to the interviewees to enhance their understanding of subject matter under investigation enabling them to respond to research enquiries appropriately. Most of the interviews lasted for 30-35 minutes.

Mp3 audio recording device was used to record interview responses and prior permission was sought from each interviewee to record their responses who allowed the researcher to record their responses unless confidentiality of their personal details and information is ensured. Rather, unrelated topics and discussion were not recorded. All interviews were recorded in English, discussed and reviewed by the researcher's Lead Supervisor (DoS). Interview responses were coded and analysed using thematic analysis.

3.15 Summary

The methodology chapter has discussed the research methodology used in this study after taking into account the research objectives of the study. Moreover, a thorough review of literature on risk management has facilitated in the selection of research philosophy, research approach, research design, research strategy, methods of collecting and analysing data and their justifications to use in current research have been discussed in detail in this chapter.

Next two chapters (four and five) aim at presenting the findings and analysis of interview data analysis, questionnaire data analysis and secondary quantitative data analysis. Chapter four presents the findings of qualitative and quantitative data analysis. Whereas, chapter five is the analysis and discussion chapter in which the findings of data analysis are discussed, corroborated and compared with the literature review and objectives of the research in order to substantiate the findings and thus to attain the overall aim of the current study.

Chapter Four: Findings of Data Analysis

4.1 Introduction

Chapter four presents the findings of data analysis undertaken for interviews conducted with banking professionals, survey questionnaire and secondary quantitative data. For this purpose, this chapter has been divided into five parts. However, analysis and discussion of the findings have been discussed in next chapter (analysis and discussion chapter) in which the findings of thematic analysis; descriptive and statistical analysis have been compared and corroborated with the literature review to substantiate the findings in order to achieve the overall aim of the current research.

Part 1 explains the findings and discussion of interview data analysis. Part 2 sheds lights on the findings of questionnaire data that has been obtained through questionnaires sent to bank managers and risk managers in London. Part 3 presents the findings of one question undertaken to achieve the objective of the current study: To evaluate the application of Basel III in London banks and to determine the impact of Basel III in managing risks. Part 4 discusses the hypotheses development to determine the relationship between various aspects of risk management & risk management practices currently followed by HSBC and LLOYDS. In part 5, secondary quantitative data analysis has been discussed. The last section summarises the findings of the whole chapter.

Part 1

4.2 Interview Data Analysis and Findings

Exploring the opinions and perceptions of banking professionals in HSBC and LLOYDS

This section sheds light on the findings and discussion of results with regards to qualitative data analysis that has been gained through semi-structured interviews with banking professionals in HSBC and LLOYDS in London. Thematic analysis using coding technique has been used to analyse interview responses. The objective is to investigate the perceptions and opinions of banking professionals on risk management practices adopted by banks. It is worth pointing out here that thematic analysis has been utilised in this research to analyse interviews and are explained in the next sections:

4.2.1 Interview Data Analysis

A thorough description of interviews conducting process has been discussed in chapter 3, section 3.14. It is reiterated in this chapter that interviews conducted with bank managers and risk managers were recorded by Mp3 audio recorder with the prior authorization of interviewees. Some notes were also taken in shorthand by the researcher in case of inability to record some interviews due to spontaneity to engage in the interview; even notes were also taken when recording interview responses.

Interviews were transcribed and coded by the researcher and notes were frequently reviewed which facilitated the researcher in developing thematic analysis to create an understandable theme of each interview response. In addition, notes were converted into segments and transcriptions demonstrated absolute thoughts on each question with regards to the original questions of the study. All transcribed interviews were converted into code segments illustrating whole thoughts on subject matter under investigation.

4.2.2 Formation of Interview Themes

Interview questions and themes were developed after bearing into mind the research questions of the study and hypotheses to determine the relationship between variables discussed in chapter three. Interviews consisted of almost the same topics as contained in survey questionnaire because the aim of conducting interviews was to confirm or disapprove findings drawn from secondary quantitative data and questionnaire data analysis.

4.2.3 Interview Questions

An interview guide was prepared prior to conduct interviews by making a list of main topics to be investigated and formulating a list of questions and sub questions to be discussed with interviewees. Interviews were prepared in a way to permit interviewees the freedom to express their insights, opinions and thoughts on the research questions under investigation. The following are the most important questions included in interviews:

Theme A: Risk Awareness in London Banks

1. What are the key risks faced by the bank in the current business environment?
2. What risk management practices are followed by the bank in order to manage risks?
3. What do you believe about the mitigation of risks in banks and how significant is hedging to the banking sector?

Theme B: Risk Management in London banks: HSBC and LLOYDS

4. How do the managers of the bank manage and recognize risks?
5. What is the understanding of managers about various kinds of risks the bank faces and its corresponding risk management systems in place?
6. What risk management procedures are followed by the bank to manage and monitor risks?
7. How do you believe that the current risk management framework is working effectively?

Theme C: Capital Adequacy of London Banks (HSBC & LLOYDS)

8. How appropriate are Basel accords potentially Basel II and Basel III standards to the banking industry in the UK?
9. Do the banks need to maintain more or less capital to enhance their financial resilience?
10. Do the new Basel III regulatory standards help the bank in enhancing its financial resilience?
11. What impact may Basel III have on the banks in preventing a major financial crisis like the recent financial meltdown of 2007? Did Basel II fail in preventing this meltdown?

Theme D: UK Banking Industry and the Global Financial Meltdown

12. There is an extensive debate about the resilience of the banking industry against the economic meltdown. Do you think the banking industry in the UK is resilient to any financial crisis (bearing into mind the recent financial crisis of 2007-08)?
13. What type of risk management framework would you believe to be used to increase the financial resilience of the banking industry and any challenges in its implementation? Any specific recommendations and suggestions?

4.3 Results and Interview Data Analysis

4.3.1 Theme A: Risk perception in London Banks

The first part of the thematic analysis explains the opinions of interviewees pertaining to risk management issues in London banks. Questions from 1 to 3 explain risk awareness in banks including risk management practices currently followed by HSBC and LLOYDS, risks encountered by banks and how risk is perceived by bank managers.

Tables 4.1 to 4.4 (see appendix 2) illustrate the findings of coding analysis for question 1 pertaining to the most important risks faced by HSBC and LLOYDS in London. The findings of the coding analysis concerning question 2 are reported in tables 4.5 to 4.6 (see appendix 2), representing the opinions of interviewees regarding what risk management practices are followed in the banks. Tables 4.8 & 4.9 (see appendix 2) explain the findings of question three regarding the mitigation of risk and use of hedging in the banking industry to deal with risks.

Table 4.1: Results for Q1

Question 1	What are the key risks faced by the bank in the current business environment?
Focused Coding	
1	liquidity risk
2	asset liability management risk
3	concentration risk
4	market risk
Theme:	Key risks faced by banks in the current business environment consist of liquidity, market, concentration and asset liability management risks.

The above table 4.1 shows that various vulnerabilities and deficiencies have been recognized by the interviewees in risk management predominantly mismatching in the handling of asset liability maturity, market, credit, operational, and asset-liability management risks. Tables 4.2 to 4.4 (see appendix 2) outline the responses of interviewees within the context of the above discussed risks.

According to tables 4.2 and 4.3 (see appendix 2), several respondents recognised liquidity risk and asset liability management risk the most significant risks faced by HSBC and LLOYDS in London. They believed that liquidity risks and ALM strongly correlated with each other and banks needed to fully factored liquidity risk into banks' risk management strategy and framework. Because of the insufficiency of liquid investment vehicles (for example, fixed income), banks face problems in managing their balance sheet from an asset-liability management perspective in terms of margin rate risk and liquidity risk.

As it is reflected in table 4.3A (see appendix 2), some respondents were of the view that banks could suffer from concentration risk due to a lack of diversification and taking a large position in a single market and risk exposure. They opined that banks could suffer from

market risk and liquidity risk losses if they are excessively concentrated. This risk represents the overall spread of outstanding accounts of HSBC and LLOYDS over various debtors whom both banks lend money. Therefore, HSBC and LLOYDS use concentration ratio to determine the concentration risk that explains the percentage of outstanding accounts each banks' loan represents.

Like other risks as illustrated in tables presented in appendix 2, market risk (appendix 2, table 4.4) is one of the key risks faced by banks in London. Respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS held a consistent view that banks were exposed to market risk because of unfavourable fluctuations in market prices that resulted in losses in on and off-balance sheet positions of banks. According to some respondents from HSBC, market risk not only arises from all positions in trading books of the bank but also from the foreign exchange risk and trading positions in the whole balance sheet.

Most of the respondents referred to market risk as a systemic risk arising from various sources such as economic depressions, natural disasters, movements in interest rates and political instability. Therefore, it cannot be eradicated through diversification and it impacts the entire market at the same time. The detailed discussion of results has been presented in the next chapter (analysis & discussion chapter).

Question 2 sheds light on determining the risk management practices that are followed by HSBC and LLOYDS in order to manage risks. Its findings are described in tables 4.5 to 4.7 (see appendix 2).

Table 4.5: Results for Q2

Question 2	What risk management practices are followed by the bank in order to manage risks?
Focussed Coding	
1	Risk management is about the establishment and application of a plan to manage risks
2	Effective risk management plays a leading part in the recognition, evaluation, and management of risks banks face.
Theme: Risk management is about the formation and execution of a plan to recognize, measure, estimate and deal with risks the banks face while conducting their business activities.	

Table 4.5 to 4.7 (see appendix 2) shows that most of the interviewees hold the view that a stringent system of risk management is essential for banking institutions to manage various kinds of risks they face which can exert unpleasant impact on the operations of banks. Banks are using various risk management tools such as stress testing, Basel accords and hedging to make them financially more resilient to absorb economic shocks and enable them to integrate risk management processes into bank's day to day operations. Further discussion of results has been presented in the next chapter.

Table 4.8: Results for Question 3

Q 3: What do you believe about the mitigation of risks in banks and how significant is hedging to the banking sector?	
Focussed Coding	
1.	It can be utilised for hedging rather than for speculative trading activities
2.	In this current business environment especially after Brexit, HSBC and LLOYDS in the UK are using hedging to manage various kind of risks
Theme:	Current business environment, the collapse of Lehman Brothers, Northern Rock and other financial firms have enhanced the demand for risk mitigation tools among banks in the UK but still, there is a long way to go.

Almost all respondents unanimously agreed that innovative financial products offered by HSBC and LLOYDS and nature of risks faced by both banks emphasised the need for adopting robust risk mitigation tools to mitigate risks after taking into account their risk appetite and risk tolerance. However, most of the respondents asserted that various hedging techniques i.e. financial derivatives including futures, swaps, options and forward contracts are used by banks to hedge risks they face (see tables 4.9 and 4.10, appendix 2).

4.3.2 Theme B: Risk Management in London banks: HSBC and LLOYDS

Table 4.11: Results for Question 4

Q 4: How do the managers in HSBC and LLOYDS deal with risks?	
Focussed Coding	
1	Risk managers in the bank and a centralised risk management function are answerable and accountable for the identification and assessment of risks
2	Having a healthy banking environment in place ensures the robust managerial

	practice of risk assessment and risk management.
Theme:	Risk managers and risk management function in HSBC and LLOYDS are particularly responsible for risk management. A healthy banking environment and attitude of management towards effective risk management is a driving factor towards managing risks.

Tables 4.11 to 4.13 (appendix 2) indicate that risk perception plays a leading part in making decisions about risk management and the development of internal control function in the bank. These decisions are endorsed with other components in the bank including the risk managers' vision of risk which influences the attention required to command the decision making process.

Table 4.14: Results for Question 5

Q 5: What is the understanding of managers about various kinds of risks the bank faces and its corresponding risk management systems in place?	
Focussed Coding	
1	Banks have established a risk policy on dealing with risks and maintaining internal control in the bank.
2	Risk management is a vital element of the induction and training of all staff in the banks enabling them to encompass a good knowledge of risk management.
Theme:	Both LLOYDS and HSBC have established a risk policy on risk management and internal control requiring all bank managers and risk managers to keep updating their knowledge on risk management as new risks are emerging and ensure compliance with the guidance of best practice.

As depicted by tables 4.15 and 4.16 (see appendix 2), HSBC and LLOYDS have established a risk policy on risk management and all employees have been communicated to ensure the compliance with principles and guidance on the best practice and risk management. However, HSBC has been found with more stringent risk management system under the supervision of a chief risk officer with adequate resources, access, independence and stature to the board. Respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS consistently claimed that the risk assessment system in the banks is responsive to changes in the business environment.

Table 4.17: Results for Question 6

Q 6: What risk management procedures are followed by the bank to manage and monitor risks?	
Focussed Coding	
1	Basel accords are widely used risk management system across the banking industry to manage various kinds of risks.
2	Risk management framework consists of six components. These six components are risk identification, risk measurement, risk mitigation, risk reporting, risk monitoring and risk governance.
Theme:	Different risk management procedures are used by banks depending on the types of risks they are exposed to and how stringent are their internal control and corporate governance systems.

Most of the interviewees believe that a stringent risk management system is critical to managing risks and making the banking industry in the UK more resilient than ever before to absorb any financial stress ahead. As the banking industry in the UK is one of the biggest banking sectors across the globe, respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS confirmed that HSBC and LLOYDS are using Basel accords to absorb financial shocks. They are also required to ensure compliance with standards and procedures on risk management set by the Bank of England (BoE) and the Financial Conduct Authority (FCA). However, one interviewee from LLOYDS did not explain full details of risk management framework used in LLOYDS. But he asserted that LLOYDS has established a sound system of risk management for robust assessment and supervision of risks (see appendix 2, tables 4.18 & 4.19).

Table 4.20: Results for Question 7

Q 7: How do you believe that the current risk management framework is functioning efficiently?	
Focussed Coding	
1	The stringent corporate governance system in banks and guidance on risk management.
2	Risks prioritisation on the basis of their effect on the going concern status of banks and the development of risk response strategies.
Theme: There are clear guidelines and procedures laid down by the risk management	

department to manage risks the banking industry may face. The stringent corporate governance system in banks and guidance on effective risk management emphasises the need for ensuring compliance with all principles and guidelines necessary for effective management of risks.

Tables 4.21 and 4.22 (see appendix 2), demonstrate that both banks HSBC and LLOYDS maintain a sound system of risk management that is evident by different interviewees who gave a rating to their existing risk management systems (HSBC rating 8, LLOYDS 7) to manage various kind of risks. Some interviewees did not give any rating to their existing risk management framework but most of them assigned a rating to their current risk management system depending on their understanding and knowledge of risk management and banking operations. The high rating shows more effective risk management function and less rating shows less prudent as compared to high rating. HSBC seems to have an edge on LLOYDS in terms of having a robust system on risk management. HSBC defines the scope of various risks and determines the relationship with each other within the context of its risk appetite and risk tolerance. Bank determines the impact of various risks with a particular focus on its capital and liquidity position. Based on the assessment of the impact of assessed risks the bank reports aggregate of risks to the centralised department and then appropriate internal risk management action is determined to deal with risks. When it comes to LLOYDS, risk response strategies are developed after looking at the banks' objectives and strategies. Risks are managed and monitored in relation to each of the banks' strategic objectives.

4.3.3 Theme C: Capital Adequacy of London Banks (HSBC & LLOYDS)

This section including questions 8, 9, 10 & 11 determines the suitability of Basel accords particularly Basel II and III in relation to HSBC and LLOYDS and examines the capital requirements in an attempt to absorb financial shocks and evaluates the credibility of Basel III in preventing any future financial crisis ahead. Results of interviews with regards to these questions are underlined in tables 4.23 to 4.25 (see appendix 2).

Table 4.23: Results for Question 8

Q 8: How appropriate are Basel accords potentially Basel II and Basel III to the banking industry in the UK?	
Focussed Coding	
1	The banks in London are using Basel accords particularly Basel II & III.

2	Banks can use other standards too apart from Basel accords depending on types of risks they face and jurisdictions in which they operate
Theme: Apart from some provisions; Basel accords are applied to London banks especially HSBC and LLOYDS	

Interviewees from HSBC and LLOYDS have varying opinions on the suitability of Basel accords to HSBC and LLOYDS. They asserted that not all provisions of Basel II & III are significant to them. The applicability of Basel standards depends on the risk exposures of banks and the likelihood of risks materialised. The findings of the coding analysis are further discussed in tables 4.24 & 4.25 (see appendix 2).

Tables 4.24 and 4.25 (see appendix 2) demonstrate that in the present volatile business environment, Basel accords are good initiatives taken by the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision to help banking institutions to manage liquidity risk, market risk, and capital risk by introducing various capital requirements and standards enabling them to cope with the financial challenges. Almost a significant number of respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS were unanimously agreed on the applicability and appropriateness of Basel accords to both banks. However, some respondents from LLOYDS believed that with small changes to Basel II along with other risk management frameworks could help banks more in all areas that otherwise be ignored if only Basel accords might be using in the banks.

Respondents argue that poor risk management and corporate governance, overleveraging and inappropriate incentive structures can lead to bank failures. Basel II and Basel III can address these issues by focusing on three areas including minimum capital requirements, internal risk assessment processes, supervisory review of capital adequacy of banks and to promote efficient banking practices through supervisory review. It is worth pointing out here that the financial strength of the banking system and the degree of consistency between capital requirements of banks can be achieved with Basel accords.

Next question 9 sheds light on the opinions of interviewees regarding the level of capital banks need to maintain in order to enhance financial resilience. By looking at the table 4.26 and responses of interviewees in table 4.27 and 4.28 (appendix 2), it is summarised that a large number of interviewees hold a unanimous view of banks holding more capital in this volatile economic environment.

Table 4.26: Results for Question 9

Q 9: Do the banks need to maintain more or less capital in order to enhance their
--

financial resilience?	
Focussed Coding	
1	More Capital
2	Less Capital
<i>Theme:</i> Banks in London should maintain more capital in order to make them more financially strong after taking into account risks they are exposed to and severity and frequency of those risks.	

As demonstrated in tables 4.27 and 4.28 (appendix 2), it is evident that HSBC and LLOYDS should maintain more capital than usual because of uncertainty created due to Brexit, their complex business operations, multiple financial products and services offered by them. In addition, in the wake of Lehman Brothers and global economic meltdown of 2007 as discussed by interviewee 20, many regulators in the UK (PRA, Bank of England) have introduced regulatory capital requirements. Therefore, all banks functioning in the UK need to maintain buffer capital as required by Prudential Regulatory conduct Authority (PRA), BoE and Basel II and III.

Table 4.29: Results for Question 10

Q 10: Do the new Basel III regulatory standards help the bank in enhancing its financial resilience?	
Focussed Coding	
I	Basel III may have a significant effect on banks because of their business models
2	It is too early to judge until all details of Basel III come into force. However, most likely, it can help banks in enhancing their financial resilience.
<i>Theme:</i> Basel III can affect all banks and assist banks in making them financially sound and resilient.	

It is interesting to mention here that there are mix responses of interviewees (see appendix 2, tables 4.30 & 4.31) on the usefulness of Basel III in maximising the financial robustness of banks in London due to the lack of revelation of full details of all provisions of Basel III. Almost all respondents had a unanimous opinion that Basel III is more demanding and effective for HSBC and LLOYDS than Basel I & II in terms of dealing with systemic risk but

it is not the last accord of all Basel accords. They argued that Basel III could not be adopted blindly as it might not cover all risks that banks face currently.

Question II seeks the opinions of respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS on evaluating the inability of Basel II in stopping a major economic meltdown like the recent one and whether the Basel III can assist banks in preventing similar collapses in the future. Despite the difference of opinions of respondents, most of the respondents were of the view that identified deficiencies in Basel II are absolutely overcome in Basel III. Respondents showed their concerns that the Basel III could not stop the financial crisis from happening again as crises are part of a business cycle.

Table 4.32: Results for Question 11

What effect may Basel III have on the banking institution in preventing a financial meltdown just like the financial downturn of 2007? Did Basel II fail in stopping the economic downturn?	
Focussed coding	
1	Failures of Basel II need to be overcome and should ensure that this Basel overcomes these failures
2	The effectiveness of Basel III is correlated to robust economic and regulatory amplifications
Theme: Identified deficiencies in Basel II need to be overcome in new Basel III	

There was divergence among responses of the respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS on the question of determining the effect of Basel III has on the banks in stopping any future financial downturn. Results in tables 4.33 & 4.34 (see appendix 2) reveal that the respondents from HSBC across London emphasise the need for maintaining increased capital and liquidity buffers. Whereas, a large number of LLOYDS risk managers focus on the usage of stress testing, capital and risk management to manage risks.

4.3.4 Theme D: UK Banking Industry and Global Financial Crisis

Question 12 explores the opinions of respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS to determine whether the UK banking industry is resilient to any financial crisis (bearing into mind the recent financial crisis of 2007-08)?

Table 4.35: Results for Question 12

Q 12: There is an extensive discussion about the resilience of the banking industry against the economic meltdown. Do you believe the banking industry in the UK is resilient to any financial crisis (bearing into mind the recent financial crisis of 2007-08)?	
Focussed Coding	
1	Banks have shown strong resilience
2	UK banking industry has adopted various regulatory measures
Theme: UK banking seems to be displaying financial resilience particularly after the financial downturn of 2007 & 2008.	

Responses of the respondents show that the UK banking industry has improved a lot after the financial crisis and collapse of financial firms across the globe. It has transformed its banking activities through innovation, adopting new stringent regulatory measures and revolutionised its risk management framework. These measures whether they aim to manage liquidity, market, credit and operational risks, the UK industry is more regulated than ever before and they believe that it has the capability to absorb financial shocks in case of the future financial crisis. Stress testing with the help of @RISK software is used consistently by the UK banks to undertake simulation enabling the banks to determine their capital levels in the context of their risk-weighted assets (see appendix 2, tables 4.36 & 4.37).

The next and last question of semi-structured interviews aims at seeking the opinions of interviewees on what type of risk management framework would they believe to be recommended to enhance the financial resilience of the banking industry.

Results of their responses are explained in table 4.38 to 4.41 (see appendix 2) and findings are discussed in the next chapter (chapter five, section 5.6).

Table 4.38: Results for Question 13

Q 13: What type of risk management framework would you believe to be used to increase the financial resilience of the banking industry and any challenges in its implementation? Any specific recommendations and suggestions	
Focussed coding	
1.	Increased risk mitigation and risk management
2.	There is no specific answer to this question. But a comprehensive framework on risk management covering key aspects on risk may be appropriate.

3.	Increased cost and extensive regulatory burden can stop banks from implementing the risk management framework
Theme: Different risk management approaches are recommended. But a comprehensive risk management framework can be developed for effective risk management.	

As demonstrated in tables 4.38 to 4.41 (appendix 2), all respondents shared varied opinions on proposing comprehensive risk management that they believed could be used to boost the financial resilience of the UK banking industry. Majority of respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS emphasised the need for more advanced and sophisticated risk management system to manage risks and challenges they might counter. However, almost most of the interviewees gave the same responses with regards to impediments in implementing the risk management framework. They argued that more costs could be involved because of stringent regulation and enhance capital requirements by regulators and supervisory institutions. The adaptability of employees to new changes is one of the key impediments to be overcome. Inadequate supervision, training, inefficient information and management systems may undermine the effectiveness of risk management function in banks.

4.4 Summary

This section aimed to explain the semi-structured interviews conducted with bank managers and risk managers working in various branches of HSBC and LLOYDS across London. As regards the findings of interviews, it can be argued that the most important risks encountered by HSBC and LLOYDS are liquidity, market, asset-liability management and concentration risks. It is noticeable that HSBC and LLOYDS almost face the same types of risks as they are operating in the same country. However, market risk has been found to be the principal risk faced by HSBC and liquidity risk faced by LLOYDS in London. Empirical evidence indicates that banks in London are using a sound system of risk management that they have developed over the period of time particularly after the collapse of Lehman Brothers, Northern Rock and the economic meltdown of 2007-08.

Interviewees from HSBC and LLOYDS have varying opinions on the suitability of Basel accords to HSBC and LLOYDS. They asserted that not all provisions of Basel II & III are significant to them. Accordingly, the applicability of Basel accords depends on the risk exposures of banks and the probability of risks materialised. However, most of the interviewees were unanimously agreed on maintaining higher capital under Basel III in order to absorb the economic shocks and to make banks financially resilient.

Part 2

4.5 Findings of survey questionnaire data analysis

Different Aspects of Risk Management in HSBC and LLOYDS in London

4.5.1 Introduction

This section aims to analyse questionnaire data to determine the current risk management practices followed by HSBC and LLOYDS in London. Section 4.5.2 sheds light on the research instrument of the current research. Section 4.5.3 reports the findings of descriptive statistics analysis. Likewise, section 4.5.4 presents a short account of hypothesis development and the findings of statistical analysis to test the hypothesis with regards to evaluating various components of risk management. In section 4.5.5, an extensive discussion of questionnaire analysis is elaborated whereas a synopsis of the whole chapter is discussed in section 4.5.6.

4.5.2 Research Instrument

The current research has used the questionnaire to capture data from the managers and risk managers of HSBC and LLOYDS in London and their corresponding head offices. As highlighted in section 3.11.9, questions incorporated in the questionnaire have been selected from the current literature on risk management (Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei, 2007; Al-Tamimi, 2002; Abu Hussain, 2009). Questionnaire operationalisation has been done and demonstrated in chapter three, section 3.11.9 in order to investigate different variables of the study such as risk understanding, risk identification, measurement and analysis of risk, managing market risk, managing operational risk, managing credit risk, managing liquidity risk, risk monitoring and controlling. SPSS 25.0 software has been used in this research to undertake descriptive statistics, regression and correlation analyses.

4.5.3 Descriptive Analysis

This section presents the findings of descriptive analysis of a survey questionnaire which covers different demographical features of the research participants including work experience, age and gender. As mentioned in section 3.8.4, convenience sampling has been used in the current research to distribute questionnaires. As discussed earlier in section 3.11.12, 300 managers and risk managers from HSBC and LLOYDS working in 32 locations across London and corresponding head offices have been chosen to seek their responses on the research questions. Self-delivery and self-collection methods of the questionnaire have been adopted in this study and some questionnaires have also been delivered and received by email. However, after distributing three hundred questionnaires for this study; 265 survey

responses are received back out of which fifteen questionnaires received are incomplete and thus are excluded when analysing survey responses. Therefore, after excluding incomplete fifteen responses; 250 questionnaires are found appropriate, reasonable, and adequate and which shows a good response rate of 83 %.

The response rate for this study is consistent with the response rates for the previous studies such as Rehman et al. (2018), Salameh (2019), Al-Farsi (2020), Abdou (2014), Tafri et al. (2011), Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi (2012) and Dabari and Saidin (2016).

Rehman et al. (2018) conducted a comparative study of risk management practices of conventional and Islamic banks of Pakistan. In order to collect data, one hundred and eighty questionnaires were sent to senior managers, risk managers and regional managers of conventional and Islamic banks in various cities of Pakistan. Out of one hundred and eighty questionnaires, one hundred and fifty-five responses were returned and complete representing a response rate of 86 % which is considered to be a good response rate to analyse data. The higher response rate helped this research to get a rigorous understanding of how bank employees manage risks they face and how the understanding of risk management frameworks varies across operations of banks.

Salameh (2019) investigated the impact of the internal control system on the quality of financial reporting for Jordanian banks. Survey questionnaire was used in this study to seek the opinions and feedbacks of the respondents regarding risk assessment, control environment, communication and information systems and effectiveness of the internal control and risk monitoring frameworks in Jordanian banks. A total of one hundred questionnaires were randomly distributed to all staff of 25 Jordanian banks out of which eighty eight questionnaires were returned reflecting a good response rate of 88% which is considered to be a good response rate to test the hypotheses and reach the conclusions.

Similarly, Abdou (2014) explored the risk management practices of Islamic banks in Yemen. The survey questionnaire was the main instrument in this study to collect data. A total of one hundred and thirty questionnaires were administered to the senior risk management officers, relationship officers and branch managers of Islamic banks in the largest cities of Yemen. One hundred and six questionnaires were received back reflecting an effective response rate of 81.54% which had assisted this research to test the hypotheses in order to meet the aim and objectives of the research.

Al-Farsi (2020) explored the factors influencing the effectiveness of enterprise risk management in listed companies of Oman. A structured questionnaire was the main instrument in this study to collect primary data from the respondents. A total of one hundred

and twenty questionnaires were administered to senior management, middle management, chief executive officers and the board of directors of a large number of listed financial and non-financial firms in Oman. Out of one hundred and twenty questionnaires, ninety-four questionnaires were received back representing a good response rate of 77% which is reasonable to give a valid generalisation with regards to meeting the aim and objectives of this study.

Tafri et al. (2011) investigated the risk management practices adopted by commercial and Islamic banks of Malaysia and explored the degree to which banks in Malaysia use risk management models and frameworks. Forty-five questionnaires were sent out to Islamic and commercial banks in Malaysia in order to seek the opinions of the respondents on risk management. Thirty-five responses were received back out of which thirty-four responses were usable for statistical analysis with a good response rate of 75.5% which was very encouraging to conduct descriptive and statistical analyses.

Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi (2012) explored the risk management practices of Islamic and conventional banks of Bahrain. The survey questionnaire was used in this study to collect primary data and a total of seven hundred questionnaires were distributed to all bank employees of conventional and Islamic banks in Bahrain because risk management is the responsibility of all staff working in banks, out of which five hundred and sixty questionnaires were returned. Out of five hundred and sixty returned questionnaires, twenty-six responses were not included in data analysis because of missing data. The resulting response rate was 75% which is considered to be a good response rate for statistical analysis.

Dabari and Saidin (2016) determined the extent to which enterprise risk management is implemented in the Nigerian banking industry and it also investigated the role of the board of directors of the Nigerian banks in implementing and overseeing the process of risk management. The survey questionnaire was used in this study to collect primary data across 361 branches including the headquarters of the 21 commercial banks in Nigeria. A total of seven hundred and twenty-two questionnaires were distributed to the staff of internal audit, risk management, operational departments and other departments of the 21 commercial banks in Nigeria. Four hundred and thirty responses were received back which were complete and usable for statistical analysis representing a response rate of 60%.

Bobbie (2010), Hair et al. (2010), Nakpodia et al. (2007) and Neuman (2000) proposes that a response rate of 70% or higher is considered to be a statistically valid response rate in order to analyse data and undertake statistical analysis. It gives more accurate survey results and enhances the confidence in statistical findings and conclusions reached. A small response rate

results in a sampling bias if the non-response is different among the respondents with regards to the outcome and exposure. A good response rate depends on the design, format, and ways of distributing questionnaire and collecting survey responses.

According to Dillman (2000), messages contained in a covering letter and the self-administered questionnaire affect the response rate which assists the respondents in deciding whether to allow the researcher access to administer the questionnaire or not.

Therefore, the researcher sent the covering letters and reference letters to the respondents outlining the aim of sending the questionnaire, the theme of the research and background of conducting this research. Reference letters for HSBC and LLOYDS had been obtained from the Lead Supervisor in order to collect data from both banks which assisted the researcher to have access to the respondents with a request to respond to the research questions that had been developed only for academic purposes. Furthermore, a covering letter along with the survey questionnaire had been sent to the respondents in order to encourage their voluntary participation by providing the necessary information regarding the theme and objectives of the research. This helped the researcher to convince as many respondents as possible to participate in this research and a significant number of the respondents participated in this research reflecting a higher response rate.

According to Edwards et al. (2002), a higher response rate depends on whether the questionnaire is clearly worded, well laid out and an increase in the response rate is dependent on the way in which the questionnaire is administered. Therefore, in order to maximise the questionnaire responses, the draft questionnaire was pilot tested, reviewed and approved by the lead supervisor of the researcher before administering the questionnaire to collect data.

A pilot study was undertaken before distributing the questionnaire to ensure the reliability and usefulness of the questionnaire. Pilot testing ensured the reliability and validity of the questionnaire and removed the misunderstanding and confusion towards the research questions on the respondents' end. After pilot testing of the questionnaire, the design, contents and structure of the survey questionnaire were discussed and reviewed by the researcher's Lead Supervisor which ensured the reasonableness, clarity and overall presentation with regards to the depth of information sought and the length of the research questions.

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) illustrate that the self-delivery and self-collection method of the questionnaire administration is a widely used instrument in order to increase the response rate of the survey questionnaire. The response rate for this study had been

increased by using survey channels that best suited the respondents which were agreed during the preliminary visits and contacts to the respondents. Therefore, this study had used self-delivery and self-collection methods of distributing and receiving questionnaire responses to increase the response rate. Some questionnaires and their responses had also been delivered and received via email where it was hard to distribute and collect responses by hand. Both methods of distributing questionnaire had helped this study to receive maximum responses because it was convenient for the respondents to give back the questionnaire by hand and via email. During preliminary visits to various branches of HSBC & LLOYDS, majority of the respondents were agreed to respond to the questionnaire when delivered to them by hand and by email because they were comfortable with both methods because of lack of time on their part to give responses via by post, online and to conduct interviews on the phone which required more time to respond to the survey.

As the respondents were reluctant to share the company-specific information which might lead to a lack of responses to the survey, therefore, the respondents had been ensured that the confidentiality and privacy of their contacts will be maintained and their details would not be disclosed to anyone. This privacy confirmation had a significant effect on increasing the response rate and caused the research participants to answer honestly to the research questions. Comparing the response rate for this study to the response rates for the prior studies on risk management as discussed earlier it can be argued that the response rate for this study is within the range of the response rates for the previous research studies on risk management.

Table 4.42 underlines the demographic characteristics of survey respondents with regards to their age, gender and work experience.

Table 4.42 demographical features of the research participants

Table 4.42.1

Gender					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	177	70.8	70.8	70.8
	Female	73	29.2	29.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.42.2

Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	25-30	32	12.8	12.8	12.8
	30-35	33	13.2	13.2	26.0
	35-40	81	32.4	32.4	58.4
	40-45	81	32.4	32.4	90.8
	45-50	20	8.0	8.0	98.8
	Above 50	3	1.2	1.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.42.3

Work Experience (years)					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3-4	20	8.0	8.0	8.0
	4-9	16	6.4	6.4	14.4
	9-14	153	61.2	61.2	75.6
	14-20	60	24.0	24.0	99.6
	5	1	.4	.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Tables (4.42.1 to 4.42.3) demonstrate that majority of research participants are male 70.8% whereas female respondents are 29.2%. The age range of the majority of respondents is between 35-45 years old that total accounts for 64.8% of all respondents. A significant number of respondents who participated in this research had work experience of 9-14 years that accounted for 61.2% of all respondents. Bar charts with regards to the above variables are presented in the appendix.

4.6 Risks faced by banks and their severity

As illustrated in chapter 3, section 3.11.7, the third section of questionnaire question aims to seek details regarding the identification as well as exploring the severity of risks faced by banks, various techniques and models used by banks for identification, assessment, analysis, monitoring, controlling and reporting of risks. The ordinal scale of measurement (Yes/No) has been used to identify risks and models utilised by London banks to control and assess those risks. Descriptive tables and bar charts (see appendix 2) best illustrate key risks

currently faced by HSBC and LLOYDS in terms of their percentage. These results are illustrated in tables 4.52 to 4.66 (see appendix 2).

However, discussion of the findings reported in tables 4.52 to 4.66 in appendix 2 has been presented in the analysis and discussion chapter (chapter five) in section 5.2.

Moreover, the following figure puts a spotlight on key models and procedures employed by banks in London to recognize, assess, scrutinize, manage and communicate risks. These methods have been selected on the basis of the level of acceptance of respondents.

4.7 Summary

Part 2 of the findings chapter has presented a questionnaire data analysis and its findings with regards to the research questions of the study. It has identified various key variables of risk management followed by HSBC and LLOYDS with the assistance of descriptive statistics. This study has also determined the level of understanding of how bank managers in London perceive, analyse, manage and control risks with regards to key risk management practices that have been identified after seeking the responses of banking professionals on risk management. According to these findings, market risk, liquidity risk, asset liability management risk, interest rate risk, operational risk and credit risk are six key risks that are currently encountered by HSBC and LLOYDS across London. However, Market risk has been found one of the key risks faced by banks which are confirmed by unanimous agreement by a large number of respondents with a higher percentage of 56.9%. The findings of this chapter support the uniformity assumption of institutional theory (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983) under which all banks in the UK under the guidelines of Bank of England must adopt a robust risk management framework to meet regulatory requirements.

Part 3

4.8 Evaluation of the application of Basel III in London banks and determination of its impact

One research question in the current study is about to evaluate the application of Basel III in London banks and to determine the impact of Basel III in managing risks. Four questions were designed and incorporated in the survey questionnaire in an attempt to seek the opinions of research participants on these questions to answer the above-mentioned research question. The following table explains the responses of respondents:

Table 4.67. Responses of the respondents on the application of Basel III

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
In the context of Basel III; increased capital requirement is effective in reducing risks	250	2	5	4.76	.767
Basel II standards need to be reviewed after failing to prevent the financial crisis	250	4	5	3.99	.425
New Basel III regulatory standards may help banks in enhancing their financial resilience	250	2	5	4.39	1.090
Risk management processes and stringent capital, liquidity and leverage standards recommended under Basel III may prevent another financial crisis from occurring.	250	1	5	4.48	.977
Valid N (listwise)	250				

Average mean value **4.40**

It is interesting to mention here that all questions have almost similar mean values varied from 3.99 to 4.76 with a mean value of 4.40. The first question with a higher mean of 4.76 illustrates that the higher capital requirements under Basel III tend to be effective in reducing risks. Question with the lowest mean value of 3.99 depicts that Basel II should be reviewed in the context of its failure to stop the financial crisis from occurring.

A thorough symposium of the findings presented in table 4.67 has been presented in the analysis and discussion chapter (chapter five) in section 5.

Part 4

4.9 Research Hypothesis

Relationship between Risk Management & its Key Aspects

As one of the research questions in the current research is to explore the current practices of risk management followed by London banks (LLOYDS and HSBC) and to determine the relationship between various aspects of risk management to deal with risks, maximise opportunities and uphold economic stability. Therefore, this work aims to answer this research question by developing a hypothesis between dependent and independent variables outlined in the following table 4.68.

Table 4.68. Study variables

Independent Variables		
NO	Key used in SPSS 25	Description
1	Risk_U	Understanding of risk
2	Risk_I	Identification of risk
3	Risk_AA	Assessment & analysis of risk
4	Risk_MC	Monitoring & controlling of risk
5	Managing_MR	Management of market risk
6	Managing_CR	Management of credit risk
7	Managing_OR	Management of operational risk
8	Managing_LR	Management of liquidity risk
Dependent Variable		
1	Risk_MP	Risk management practices

A significant number of research articles have been reviewed in order to explore what variables had been used in the previous research studies which have assisted this research to choose more appropriate variables for this study. The variables reported in table 4.68 have been discussed in the following sections along with their descriptive statistics.

Table 4.69. A History Table of Previous Research Articles

The following table outlines the summary of articles in which the researchers in the previous research have used the same or similar variables that have been selected for this research.

Sr No	Name of Article	Name of Journal	Variables Used	The Researcher' Name	Year
1	Risk and risk management practices: A comparative study between Islamic and conventional banks in Qatar	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research	Identification and assessment of risk, recognition and analysis of risk, monitoring and controlling of risk	Adel Elgharbawy	2020
2	The Impact of Risk Management on the Profitability of Banks in Nigeria	World Journal of Innovative Research	Loan to deposit ratio, profitability of banks, capital adequacy ratio and non-performing loans	Abu Noruwa, Ikponmwosa	2020
3	The relationship between credit risk management and non-performing assets of commercial banks in India	Managerial Finance	Credit risk perception, Credit risk control, Credit risk assessment, Credit risk identification, Credit risk capital requirements	Sirus Sharifi, Arunima Haldar, S.V.D. Nageswara Rao	2019
4	A comparative study of Islamic and conventional banks' risk management practices: empirical evidence from Pakistan	Journal of Banking Regulation	Risk governance, risk identification, risk assessment and analysis of credit risk	Abdul Rehman, Abdelhafid Benamraoui, Aasim Munir Dad	2018
5	The Impact of Capital Structure on Risk and Firm Performance: Empirical Evidence for the Bucharest Stock Exchange Listed Companies	International Journal of Financial Studies	Profitability, bank size, Asset tangibility, Effective tax rate, Dividend distribution rate, Cash-flows volatility and the cost of capital for shareholders	Elena Alexandra Nenu, Georgeta Vintilă, Stefan Cristian Gherghina	2018
6	The Relationship between Risk Management and Profitability of Commercial Banks in Albania	Asian Themes in Social Sciences Research	Return on assets, return on equity, non-performing loans and capital adequacy	Arjeta Hallunovi, Miranda Berdo	2018
7	The Impact of Credit Risk Management on Profitability: Evidence from Nepalese Commercial Banks.	European Journal of Business and Management	Return on assets, return on equity, capital adequacy ratio, non-performing loan ratio, cost per loan assets, cash reserve ratio, assets growth ratio and leverage ratio	Ritesh Shrestha	2017
8	The effects of liquidity risk and credit risk on bank stability: Evidence from the MENA region	Borsa Istanbul Review	The liquidity gaps, the asset growth, the income diversity, return on assets, return on equity, capital adequacy ratio, the net interest margin, the GDP growth and the inflation rate.	Ameni Ghenimi, Hasna Chaibi, Mohamed Ali Brahim Omri	2017
9	The Effect of the 2007/2008 Financial Crisis on Enterprise Risk Management Disclosure of Top US Banks	Journal of Modern Accounting and Auditing	Bank size, board independence, profitability, leverage, board duality and board size	Daniel Zeghal, Meriem El Aoun	2016

10	Bank Capital Adequacy Requirements And Risk-Taking Behaviour In Tunisia: A Simultaneous Equations Framework	The Journal of Applied Business Research	Bank capital (equity to total assets), the ratio of weighted-assets to total assets, bank size, return on assets, return on equity and regulatory pressure.	Faten Ben Bouheni	2015
11	Risk Management Practices in the Republic of Yemen: Are Islamic Banks Different?	Journal of Islamic Economics, Banking and Finance	Risk management and risk understanding, identification and analysis of risk, risk monitoring, credit risk analysis and risk management practices	Hussein A Abdou	2014
12	The Impact of Credit Risk Management on the Commercial Banks Performance in Nigeria	International Journal of Management and Sustainability	Return on equity, return on assets, non-performing loans and capital adequacy ratio	Idowu Abiola, Awoyemi Samuel Olausi	2014
13	The Risk Sensitivity of Capital Requirements	Review of Finance	Risk-weighted assets (RWAs), total assets, total capital	Francesco Vallascas, Jens Hagendorff	2013
14	Banking Capital and Risk-taking Adjustment under Capital Regulation: The Role of Financial Freedom, Concentration and Governance Control	International Journal of Management, Economics and Social Sciences	Non-performing loans ratio, capital ratio, total assets, Loan loss reserve ratio, The ratio of non-operating expenses against the total revenue and concentration (The ratio of the assets of three largest banks)	Shu Ling Lin, Dar-Yeh Hwang, Keh Luh Wang, Zhe Wen Xie	2013
15	Risk management practices in Islamic banks of Pakistan	Journal of Risk Finance	Understanding and management of risk, risk management practices, risk identification, risk analysis and risk monitoring	Sania Khalid, Shehla Amjad	2012
16	Risk management practices of conventional and Islamic banks in Bahrain	Journal of Risk Finance	Understanding and identification of risks, risk monitoring, risk assessment, credit risk analysis and risk management.	Hameeda Abu Hussain, Jasim Al-Ajmi	2012
17	Risk management practices of Islamic banks of Brunei Darussalam	Journal of Risk Finance	Risk identification, risk understanding, risk assessment, credit risk analysis, risk monitoring and risk management practices.	Abul Hassan	2009
18	The relationship between capital structure and risk in emerging market banks	Banks and Bank Systems	The levels of capital (total assets) and the level of risk (non-performing loans)	Keegan Floquet, Nicholas Biekpe	2008
19	The Value of Enterprise Risk Management: Evidence from the U.S. Insurance Industry	The Journal of Risk and Insurance	Industrial diversification, firm size and book value of assets	Robert E. Hoyt, Andre P. Liebenberg	2008
20	Banks' risk management: a comparison study of UAE national and foreign banks.	Journal of Risk Finance	Credit risk analysis, risk identification, risk management, risk understanding, risk monitoring and risk analysis.	Hussein A. Hassan Al-Tamimi	2007
21	Examining the Relationships between Capital, Risk and Efficiency in European	European Financial Management	Loan-loss reserves, Equity to assets ratio, Cost inefficiency, Net loans to total assets, Return-on-assets	Yener Altunbas, Santiago Carbo, Edward P.M. Gardener, Philip	2007

	Banking		and Liquid assets to customer and short-term deposits	Molyneux	
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All the previous studies presented in history table 4.69 illustrate that various researchers have used different variables in their research in order to conduct research on risk management. It is evident from the above table that widely used variables by different researchers include identification and assessment of risk, total capital, return on equity, return on assets, non-performing loans, recognition and analysis of risk, monitoring and controlling of risk, risk governance, credit risk capital requirements, credit risk perception, credit risk control, credit risk assessment and credit risk analysis etc.

However, this study has used other important variables such as managing market risk, managing credit risk, managing operational risk and managing liquidity risk apart from variables used in the previous research (risk understanding, risk identification, risk assessment and analysis, risk monitoring and risk controlling). The reason for using these variables in this study is that banks and financial institutions offer various financial products and services to customers including loans, investment banking, mortgage lending, residential lending and insurance. Financial innovation, globalization, complex financial products and services have exposed banks to a wide range of various interrelated risks such as market risk, operational risk, liquidity risk, and credit risk. The use of these variables in this study may help in determining the relationship between all these variables because a stringent system of risk management consists of all key aspects. All above variables play a leading role in enhancing the effectiveness of a sound system of risk management in banks and are key aspects of risk management in banks.

Risk understanding is the first aspect of risk management in banks because a sound understanding of risks and risk management among employees of banks improves the ability of banks to manage their risks effectively and reduce their losses. It is vital for the staff of banks to understand different risk aspects in the banking operations and risks that are inherent in business operations.

A robust system of risk identification assists management to classify different risks according to their importance and frequency which helps bank management to allocate resources efficiently for effective management of risks. If employees of banks have a good understanding of risks and their dynamics; it can help banks in enhancing their ability to manage risks efficiently. Risk identification is one of the most important steps in risk management. Without appropriate identification of risks, banks can not develop and

implement risk responses strategies. Therefore, banks employ various risk identification models to identify various risks within the context of their declared aims and objectives.

Risk assessment is another significant variable in risk management process after risk identification in order to evaluate and analyse identified risks. Risks are identified at both the consolidated levels of an institution and the individual entity level which depends on the effectiveness of management policies on risk management.

Risk monitoring and controlling are used to ensure that risk management practices are in line with desired practices and risks are managed effectively. Adequate monitoring of risks assists bank management to identify issues at an early stage which enables them to take remedial actions to cope with the challenges. Risk management practices adopted by banks are in the form of policies, strategies and processes to identify, evaluate and analyse risks. If risk management practices are not efficient and effective, banks cannot manage and cope with risks. Therefore, various qualitative and quantitative analysis methods are used by banks to evaluate opportunities and prioritise risks which enable them to design and implement appropriate risk response strategies.

Banks face various types of risk. Credit risk is one of the most important types of risk as it is evident from the calculation of capital adequacy ratio under Basel II requirements. Credit risk occurs due to the default of a counterparty on its debt payments and non-compliance with its contractual obligations. A weak system of credit risk management has been one of the main causes of a bank failure in recent years.

Operational risk is the risk of loss due to non-performance of internal processes, system failures, and failure of internal control and reporting systems in banks and inability of employees to discharge their duties properly. Therefore, management of operational risk is vital for banks to operate as going concern. Market risk is another very important risk which is a risk of loss due to unfavourable fluctuations in the market prices of assets. Banks are exposed to market risks within the context of management of trading operation and the balance sheet position of banks. Therefore, like other risks, the management of market risk plays a dominant role in determining the effectiveness of risk management systems of banks.

Managing liquidity risk is another important aspect of risk management because liquidity risk is considered as a significant factor that contributed to the recent financial crisis. Therefore, a weak system of liquidity risk management not only undermines the financial stability of banks but also deteriorates the economy as a whole as well.

Liquidity risk, market risk, credit risk and operational risk have been considered as important risks under Basel accords. The Basel III accord has introduced various measures to cope with

these risks because of the susceptibility of banks to these risks. Therefore, this study has used all the above-discussed variables to investigate the impact of these variables on risk management as these variables are the main determinants of risk management.

4.9.1 Descriptive Statistics

Both standard deviation (SD) and the mean are frequently used models in descriptive statistics to characterise the underlying features of variables in business research. A higher value of standard deviation indicates that observations in data are extensively scattered from the mean. On the other hand, a small standard deviation illustrates the proximity of observations in data to the mean. Both higher and smaller values of SD enable the researcher to reach conclusions about the data (Pallant, 2001; Dancey and Reidy, 2004).

Descriptive analysis has been undertaken to calculate the standard deviation and the mean for independent and dependent variables discussed in table 4.68. The variability of variables has been determined by SD whereas the mean values have helped in measuring the average response. Both the mean values and standard deviation have been used by various researchers in past in order to describe the characteristics of their research variables (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007; Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei, 2007; Bilal, Talib and Khan, 2013; Khalid and Amjad, 2012).

Bearing into mind the research questions of this work, this study has made a broader argument which is based on a higher value of the mean and the lower standard deviation. Different risk management variables have been implied in the current research to investigate the current risk management practices followed by HSBC and LLOYDS within the context of the understanding of risk, identification of risk, measurement and analysis of risk, monitoring and controlling of risk, management of credit risk, management of market risk, management of liquidity risk, management of operational risk and risk management practices. Subsequent sections put a spotlight on the results of the descriptive statistics of the variables:

Risk Understanding

Table 4.70: Responses of the participants on risk understanding

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
There is a general understanding of risk management across the bank	250	3	5	4.77	.625

There is an adequate system for understanding different risks used in the bank	250	1	5	4.51	.712
Responsibility for understanding risk and risk management is clearly defined across the bank	250	1	5	3.67	.271
Accountability for risk management and understanding of risk is defined in the banks	250	1	5	3.88	.863
Valid N (listwise)	250				
Average value				4.2	

Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

Four questions have been incorporated in the current research to measure risk understanding in London banks. Table 4.70 presents the results of the descriptive statistics of four questions with regards to risk understanding in banks.

It is evident from table 4.70 that the mean values of all questions range from 3.67 to 4.77. Question with a higher mean of 4.77 and a standard deviation of .625 shows that managerial staff of HSBC and LLOYDS have a general comprehension of risk management across their banks. As the standard deviation of .625 is less than 1 which means that data values are close to the mean value of 4.77 and are not distant from 1. The higher mean value and a lower standard deviation indicate that majority of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that there is a general understanding of risk management across London banks. The higher value reflects the effectiveness and ability of banks to deal with their risk portfolios in future. The question with the smallest mean value of 3.67 and a standard deviation of 0.271 is about evaluating the responsibility of staff for understanding risk and risk management in banks. The lower mean value of 3.67 shows that responsibility for understanding risk and risk management in the bank is comparatively declining in contrast to risk comprehension. However, the average mean value (4.2) of all four questions in table 4.70 is higher than the midpoint value (3) on the five-point Likert scale which shows that the majority of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that overall bank managers and risk managers in HSBC and LLOYDS have a sound understanding of risk management in banks. These findings are consistent with the previous research on risk management conducted by Hassan (2009), Boston Consulting Group (2011), Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi (2012) and Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei (2007). It is important for banks to ensure that responsibility for risk understanding is clearly defined across banks and is communicated to all staff working in the banks for effective management of risks.

Risk Identification

Table 4.71: Responses of the participants on risk identification

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
The bank conducts a systematic and detailed identification of risks it faces pertinent to its established aim and objectives.	250	2	5	3.99	.752
Bank faces difficulties in prioritising risks	250	1	5	3.68	.643
The bank knows its strengths and weaknesses of its risk management function in place	250	2	5	3.90	.813
The banks has envisaged and established techniques for systematic identification of opportunities	250	1	5	3.74	.627
It is very important for bank to implement the most widely accepted techniques for risk identification	250	3	5	4.48	.411
Valid N (listwise)	250				
Average Value				3.95	

Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

Five questions have been included in the questionnaire about risk identification in banks. Table 4.71 presents a summary of the descriptive statistics of the survey responses.

Table 4.71 shows varying values of mean and standard deviation with regards to five questions underlying risk identification in banks. The mean values vary between 3.68 and 4.48 with an overall mean value of 3.95 for all questions and the standard deviation is less than 1 for all questions which shows that data points are close to the mean values and are not widely dispersed from the means. The highest mean value of 4.48 with a standard deviation of .411 is given to the last statement in which the respondents have been requested to share their opinions on the need for banks to implement the most widely used techniques for risk identification. The lowest mean of 3.68 is associated with the statement “the bank faces challenges in prioritising risks” which demonstrates that banks face issues and problems when prioritising their risks. This statement has a standard deviation of .643 which is less than 1 and shows that data points are close to the mean of 3.68 and are not dispersed from the mean value. Furthermore, the average value (3.95) of all five questions exceeds the midpoint value of 3 on the five-point Likert scale which indicates that the majority of the respondents agreed that banks and risk managers in HSBC and LLOYDS are good in risk identification. These findings are consistent with those reached by Nazir, Daniel and Nawaz (2012), Kromschroder and Luck (1998), Al-Tamimi (2002) and Hassan (2011). These findings

summarise that London banks are largely aware of risk identification and using widely accepted methods of risk identification.

In addition, the ordinal scale (No or Yes) has been used in this study to seek the responses of the respondents with regards to various techniques used by banks for risk identification. Based upon these feedbacks, some important risk identification techniques have been identified on the basis of the respondents' feedback. A summary of these techniques is presented in figure 4.1.

Risk Assessment and Analysis

Table 4.72: Responses of the participants on risk assessment and risk analysis

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
The bank evaluates the probability of risks occurring	250	1	5	3.78	.985
Quantitative analysis methods are used by the bank to assess risks	250	1	5	4.79	.411
Assessment of bank to analysed risks includes cost-benefit assessment of addressing risks	250	1	5	3.86	.748
The bank's response to analysed risks includes prioritization of risks and selection of those risks that require active management	250	2	5	3.99	.771
The bank's response to analysed risks includes prioritization of risk treatments where there are resource constraints on risk treatment implementation	250	2	5	3.72	.860
A computer based system is used by the bank to estimate the earnings and risk management variability.	250	2	5	3.97	.580
The bank relies on the output of quantitative data with human judgment	250	1	4	3.69	.834
Valid N (listwise)	250				
Average Value				3.97	

Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

The survey questionnaire includes seven questions about risk evaluation and risk analysis in London banks that are reported in table 4.72. The mean values of all questions vary from 3.69 to 4.79 with an overall average value of 3.97 and the standard deviation of all questions is smaller and less than 1 which shows that data values are close to their associated means and are not distant from 1. The question "quantitative analysis methods are used by banks to assess risks" has the highest mean of 4.79 and a standard deviation of .411 which indicates that those surveyed either strongly agreed or agreed that both banks are using quantitative

methods of risk evaluation and investigation. The lowest mean value of 3.69 and a standard deviation of .834 are given to the last question which shows that banks rely on the output of numeric data with human judgment. However, the midpoint value (3) on the five-point Likert scale is also less than the average value (3.97) of all seven questions which depict that majority of the respondents agreed that London banks are generally sound and good in assessing and evaluating various kinds of risk. These findings are consistent with other relevant studies on risk management (Pausenberger and Nassauer, 2000; Radu, 2020; Rot, 2008, Fuser et al, 1999; Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi, 2012; Drzik, 1995 and Hassan, 2009). In order for the exact measurement of risks; banks must use appropriate models to quantify potential losses and the corresponding probability of occurrence of risks. It is vital for banks to point out the developments with the utmost possibility to quantify potential losses that may affect banks.

Risk Monitoring and Controlling

Table 4.73: Responses of the participants on risk monitoring and controlling

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Monitoring the effectiveness of risk management is a key component of management reporting process	250	3	5	4.78	.561
The level of control by the bank is appropriate for the risks that it faces	250	2	5	3.52	.739
The bank has adopted a standard reporting system about the risk management from bottom to top management	250	2	5	3.70	.961
Reporting and communication processes within the bank support the effective management of risk.	250	3	5	4.71	.712
The bank's response to risk includes an evaluation of the effectiveness of the existing controls and risk management responses	250	2	5	3.89	.734
The bank's response to risk includes action plans in implementation decisions about identified risk	250	1	4	3.48	1.180
The bank effectively monitors the credit limit of every counterparty	250	2	4	3.77	.734
The borrower's business performance is regularly observed by the bank following the extension of financing	250	1	5	3.66	.619
Valid N (listwise)	250				

Average Value				3.94	
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Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

Eight questions have been incorporated in the questionnaire with regards to risk monitoring and controlling in London banks. Descriptive statistics are reported in table 4.73.

For the question regarding monitoring and controlling of risk in banks, the mean values range from 3.48 to 4.78 with an average mean value of 3.94. The mean of 4.78 is the highest value associated with the question “supervising the effectiveness of risk management system is a key component of the management reporting process in banks”. The highest mean of 4.78 and the lowest standard deviation of .561 demonstrate that the majority of the participants highly agreed with this question which reveals that overseeing the use of risk management function in London banks is a principal part of their reporting process. On the other hand, the question “the bank’s response to risk includes action plans in implementation decisions about identified risk” has the lowest mean of 3.48 and a standard deviation of 1.180. However, the overall mean value (3.94) of all questions exceeds the midpoint value (3) on the five-point Likert scale which demonstrates that a large number of the respondents agreed that London banks employ a sound system of risk monitoring and controlling for effective and timely management of risks. These findings are consistent with those reached by Irm, Airmic and Alarm (2002), Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei (2007), Oliveira et al (2011) and Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi (2012).

In addition, the respondents have also been requested to give opinions on the techniques used by banks to monitor and control risks by using the ordinal scale (Yes/No). Based on their responses, this study has identified a few techniques for monitoring and controlling that are reported in figure 4.1.

Managing Market Risk

Table 4.74: Responses of the participants on managing market risk

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
The market risk strategy is envisaged by the board of directors that is implemented by top management in the banks in the form of policies and procedures	250	2	5	3.97	.263
Market risk exposure of bank is maintained at prudent levels and is in accordance with capital bank holds	250	3	5	4.85	.719

The bank has a sound system of risk management in the form of policies, infrastructure and processes for managing market risk	250	2	5	3.77	.638
Assessment of bank to analysed risks includes cost-benefit assessment of addressing risks	250	1	4	3.73	.741
Valid N (listwise)	250				
Average Value				4.08	

Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

The survey questionnaire contains four questions pertaining to managing market risk with the mean values ranging from 3.73 to 4.85 with an overall average mean value of 4.08. There is no major difference in the responses of the respondents as reported in table 4.74. The highest mean value of 4.85 with a standard deviation of 0.719 is given to the question “market risk in banks is sustained at prudent levels and they manage market risk after taking into account their capital requirements”. On the contrary, the last question has the smallest mean of 3.73 (with a standard deviation of .741) which reflects the evaluation of banks’ potential to analyse risk after conducting a cost-benefit analysis of identified risks. The standard deviation of all questions in the above table is less than 1 which indicates that data points are close to their mean values and are not dispersed from means. Moreover, the average mean value (4.08) of all questions is higher than the midpoint value (3) on the five-point Likert scale which shows that the majority of the respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that London banks are effectively managing market risk. These findings are supported by existing literature (BIS, 2019; Gallati, 2003; Schroeck, 2002 and Crouhy, Galai and Mark, 2006) that market risk is one of the most significant risks currently faced by banks due to changes in market prices of stocks and assets. Banks should utilise various sophisticated models and tools (stressed testing, value at risk, and stressed value at risk) in order to measure and manage market risk.

Managing Credit Risk

Table 4.75: Responses of the participants on credit risk

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
The credit risk strategy is envisaged by the board of directors that is implemented by top management in the banks in the form of policies and procedures	250	1	5	3.88	.316

The bank adopts a credit risk system to assess the creditworthiness of customers across all its credit activities	250	1	5	3.71	1.363
The bank has a sound system of risk management in the form of policies, infrastructure and processes for managing credit risk	250	1	5	4.77	.712
Credit portfolio is monitored by the bank on day to day basis and takes action in case of any unpleasant credit events	250	1	4	3.68	.705
A periodic report of credit risk is prepared by bank regularly	250	2	5	3.79	.803
Valid N (listwise)	250				
Average Value				3.21	

Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

Five questions have been included in the survey questionnaire in respect of managing credit risk. Table 4.75 presents the descriptive statistics of each question.

It is evident from the above table that the average mean value of all questions is 3.21 and the mean value for every single question fluctuates from 3.68 to 4.77. The highest mean value (4.77) and the lower standard deviation of .712 indicate that majority of the respondents strongly agreed that banks in London maintain a stringent risk management system in the form of models, processes and policies for managing credit risk. On the contrary, the question with the lowest mean value of 3.68 and a standard deviation of .705 specifies that banks oversee their credit portfolios on a regular basis and undertake corrective actions in case of any unpleasant credit events. Moreover, the average mean value of 3.21 exceeds the midpoint value of 3 on the five-point Likert scale which illustrates that London banks have developed policies, procedures and guidelines in order to deal with credit risk. They regularly monitor their credit portfolios and take prompt actions to cope with credit risks. Existing literature on risk management supports the above findings according to which credit risk is one of the most important types of risk currently faced by banks in the current volatile business environment. Banks need to develop, execute, oversee models and tools to manage and reduce credit risk. Various models and techniques can be used by banks to cope with credit risks such as exposure limit, creditworthiness analysis, stress testing, credit portfolio models, internal ratings and inspection by branch managers (Aven, 2016; Ramachandran and Gavoury, 2011; Carbo and Rodriguez, 2007).

Managing Operational Risk

Table 4.76: Responses of the participants on managing operational risk

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Bank adopts a comprehensive set of policies, guidelines and policies for managing operational risk	250	1	5	3.67	.554
All categories of operational risk are defined and contemplated by executive management and board of directors in the bank.	250	1	5	3.61	.409
The bank ensures business continuity and contingency plans in the event of any business disruption in order to minimise losses and operate as a going concern.	250	3	4	3.74	.431
Thorough operational risk management policy established by the top management of the bank transforms the strategic direction given by the board of directors	250	1	4	3.88	.830
The bank has a sound system of operational risk management	250	2	5	4.72	.937
A periodic report of operational risk is prepared by bank regularly	250	1	5	3.58	.628
Valid N (listwise)	250				
Average Value				3.86	

Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

The current research has incorporated six questions to seek the responses of the respondents on the management of operational risk in banks. Their descriptive statistics are reported in table 4.76.

The mean values of all questions vary from 3.58 to 4.72 with an overall mean of 3.86 that is higher than the midpoint value of 3 on the five-point Likert scale chosen for the survey questionnaire. The highest mean value of 4.72 with a standard deviation of .937 is indicative of the development of a sound system of operational risk management in HSBC and LLOYDS across London. On the other hand, 3.58 is the lowest mean value and a standard deviation of .628 is associated with the question which specifies that a periodic report of operational risk is regularly prepared by banks. However, the average mean value of 3.86 is higher than the midpoint value (3) on the five-point Likert scale which depicts that London banks have developed the operational risk management policy approved by the board of

directors and have business continuity and contingency plans in place to deal with operational risks and reduce losses. These findings are supported by the empirical findings of Lowe (2010) and Gallati (2003) that operational risk occurs due to failed and inappropriate people, internal processes or external events which may lead to adverse customer impact, financial loss, and reputational damage of banks. Therefore, banks should develop stringent systems of operational risk management in order to operate as going concern.

Managing Liquidity Risk

Table 4.77: Responses of the participants on managing liquidity risk

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Bank adopts a comprehensive set of policies and guidelines for managing liquidity risk	250	4	5	4.32	.415
Bank can reduce its liquidity losses by applying a robust system of liquidity risk management	250	1	5	3.91	.743
A periodic report of operational risk is prepared by bank regularly	250	1	5	3.89	.518
Valid N (listwise)	250				
Average Value				4.04	

Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

Three questions have been developed to capture the responses of the respondents on managing liquidity risk. Table 4.77 reports the descriptive statistics of each question.

All questions have been found with almost similar mean values i.e. ranging from 3.89 to 4.32. The overall mean value of all questions is 4.04 and the standard deviation of all questions is less than 1 which means that data values are close to the mean values and are not dispersed from their associated means. The question with the highest mean value of 4.32 and a standard deviation of .415 depicts that the majority of the respondents strongly agreed that banks in London are using the comprehensive systems of liquidity risk management which are in the form of guidelines, policies and best practices on liquidity risk. On the other hand, the question with the smallest mean of 3.89 and a standard deviation of .518 reports that banks are regularly preparing reports regarding liquidity risk. Moreover, the midpoint value (3) on the five-point Likert scale is less than the average mean value of 4.04 which demonstrates that the majority of the respondents either strongly agreed or agreed that London banks are good in liquidity risk management. These findings are reinforced by available literature (Saunders and Cornett, 2008 and Matz and Neu, 2006) that banks should develop, implement

and oversee risk management policies to cope with liquidity risk. Banks need to determine their liquidity requirements by establishing targets and minimum ratios with the help of scenario and stress testing.

Risk Management Practices

Table 4.78: Responses of the participants on risk management practices

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Executive management of the bank regularly reviews the performance of its operations in managing its risks	250	1	5	3.87	.619
Bank has an effective system of receiving feedback on risk management strategies and its performance	250	2	4	4.61	.714
Bank's strategy and policy ensure adequate training and induction of all employees in relation to risk management	250	3	5	3.79	.783
Risk management processes and strategies are documented and appropriate guidance is provided to staff responsible for risk management	250	3	5	4.58	.689
Bank needs to employ specialised people in its risk management department	250	3	5	4.67	.242
Establishment of a sound risk management function is one of the main objectives of the bank.	250	3	5	4.45	.711
Bearing into mind recent financial crisis of 2007-08, banks hold enough capital to absorb financial shocks if capital ratio to risk weighted assets (RWA) is equal to capital adequacy ratio set by Bank of England.	250	1	5	4.88	.861
Current risk management practices adopted by the bank in current volatile business environment are sound and efficient.	250	3	5	3.60	.656
Valid N (listwise)	250				
Average Value				4.31	

Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

Eight questions have been included in the survey questionnaire to investigate the current risk management practices followed by London banks. Their descriptive statistics are reported in table 4.78.

There are mixed responses of the respondents when questioned about risk management practices. However, their mean values fluctuate from 3.60 to 4.88 with an overall mean value of 4.31. Question with the highest mean of 4.88 and a standard deviation of .861 demonstrates that banks in London maintain buffer capital to absorb financial shocks after bearing into mind the financial crisis of 2007-08. However, the lowest mean value of 3.60 with a standard deviation of .656 specifies that the current risk management frameworks used by banks are sound and robust. Furthermore, it is evident from the above table the average mean value of 4.31 is greater than the midpoint value of 3 on the five-point Likert scale which means that London banks have sound risk management strategies and processes that are regularly reviewed by the executive management of banks. These findings are consistent with those concluded by Walker (2009), Turner (2009), Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi (2012) and Hassan (2009) that banks need to develop stringent systems of risk management in the forms of policies, procedures and guidelines. These risk management strategies should be responsive to changes in the business environment in order to cope with the new and emerging risks.

Fig. 1: Methods and Models used by LLOYDS and HSBC for Risk Management

The existing literature on risk management within the context of the banking industry illustrates that banks use various models and practices to manage the risks they face. From a theoretical perspective, why banks use risk management practices is that they are required by various regulatory bodies to meet regulatory requirements? According to DiMaggio and Powell (1983) & Collier and Woods (2011), the institutional theory explains the phenomenon of the application of risk management. Both researchers are of the view that institutionalization prevails only when the existing risk management system used by banking institutions become homogeneous. They further argue that this homogeneity is only exercised when the coercive isomorphic instrument by which regulatory, legitimacy and political pressures are exerted on businesses by virtue of invitation, persuasion and direction (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983).

Based on current theories, practices and existing literature on risk management, this work aims to study risk management in London banks. In the context of HSBC and LLOYDS, it is expected that both banks should refine their existing risk management frameworks and are needed to employ an effective and a sound system of risk management covering its key aspects such as understanding, identification, assessment, analysis, monitoring and controlling of risks, management of credit risk, market risk and liquidity risk to meet the requirements of Bank of England (BoE).

Reviewing the findings of other pertinent studies on risk management conducted by (Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei, 2007; Shafique, Hussain and Hassan, 2013; Bilal, Talib and Khan, 2013; Hassan, 2011), a significant relationship can be expected between risk management practices and the above-mentioned aspects of risk management. Thus, the following hypothesis has been developed to determine the relationship between risk management practices and various components of risk management.

H01: There is a positive significant relationship between risk management practices and understanding of risk, identification of risk, assessment and analysis of risk, monitoring and controlling of risk, management of credit risk, market risk, operational risk and liquidity risk.

4.9.2 Correlation Analysis

Correlation statistics and ordinary least square regression have been undertaken in this study to test the relationship between dependent and independent variables. As outlined in chapter 3, section 3.12, this study has used Pearson correlation to investigate the relationship between variables and its results are presented in table 4.69.

Table 4.79

Correlations										
		Risk_U	Risk_I	Risk_A	Risk_M C	Managin g_MR	Managin g_CR	Managin g_OR	Risk_M P	Managi ng_LR
Risk_U	Pearson Correlation	1	.237*	.251**	.438**	.234	.407**	.382*	.534**	.252**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.143	.022	.000	.228	.000	.003	.000	.000
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
Risk_I	Pearson Correlation	.237*	1	.351**	.368**	.333**	.351*	.284*	.573*	.646*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.037		.000	.024	.006	.047	.041	.13	.445
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
Risk_A	Pearson Correlation	.251**	.351**	1	.152**	.342	-.351	.313	.581*	.341**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.038	.040		.511	.325	.561	.434	.135	.205
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
Risk_MC	Pearson Correlation	.438**	.368**	.152**	1	.259**	.286**	.374**	.661**	.642**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.044	.548		.034	.043	.000	.000	.011
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
Managing_M R	Pearson Correlation	.234	.333**	.342	.259**	1	.311**	.421**	.426**	.252
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.343	.000	.347	.144		.000	.045	.000	.542
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
Managing_C R	Pearson Correlation	.407**	.351*	-.351	.286**	.311**	1	.362*	.371**	.284**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.037	.655	.041	.000		.000	.011	.000
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
Managing_O R	Pearson Correlation	.382*	.284*	.313	.374**	.421**	.362*	1	.538**	.352**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.049	.031	.005	.000	.000	.033		.000	.000
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
Risk_MP	Pearson Correlation	.534**	.573*	.581*	.661**	.426**	.571**	.538**	1	.468*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.003	.025	.000	.000	.000	.000		.004
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250

Managing_L R	Pearson Correlation	.252**	.646*	.341**	.642**	.252	.284**	.352**	.468*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.514	.030	.000	.437	.052	.000	.000	
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250	250
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).										
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).										

The above table shows that the correlation coefficients (r) of the independent and dependent variable are positive and most of the correlation coefficients are higher than 0.5 which indicate there is a positive association between risk management practices (Risk_Mp) and other aspects of risk management (independent variables: Risk_U, Risk_I, Risk_AA, Risk_MC, Managing_CR, Managing_MR, Managing_OR, Managing_LR etc). As the Pearson correlation determines the direction and strength of the linear relationship between two or more variables; therefore, the correlation coefficients(r) and the p- values in table 4.79 have been used to explore the correlation between various aspects of risk management and risk management practices and to explain the reasons for the significance and insignificance of the correlation between variables.

The value of the correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to +1. The higher the value of the correlation coefficient, the stronger is the association between risk management practices and aspects of risk management. The correlation between variables will be significant if the p-values are less than the significant levels of .05* & .01**.

It is evident from table 4.79 that risk understanding (Risk_U) and risk management practices (Risk_MP) have a strong correlation of 0.534** which illustrates that there is a strong positive correlation between both variables. The results reported in table 4.79 demonstrate that the p-value (.000) for the correlation between risk management practices and understanding of risk is less than the significance level of 0.01** which shows that the correlation between both variables is significant. The main reason for a significant correlation between variables is that a proper understanding of risks and risk management is a key aspect of a sound system of risk management in banks which is significantly influenced by the understanding of risks. These findings are consistent with the previous research findings (Hassan and Dicle, 2006; Hudin and Hamid, 2014 and Boston Consulting Group, 2001) that it is important for the staff of banks to enhance their understanding of risk management and the way risks are managed by banks. Risk understanding is important at all levels of bank management because line officers of banks are directly involved in risk management as they

take risks on behalf of the banks. Banks should give their staff adequate training and induction in order to enhance their understanding of their responsibilities with regards to their commitment towards effective risk management.

These results are in line with the findings of the previous studies on risk management such as Hassan (2011), Nazir, Daniel and Nawaz (2012), Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi (2012) and Collier and Woods (2011). These findings explain that an adequate understanding of risks by employees of banks is a value-boosting factor in making the risk management frameworks of banks sound and resilient. Moreover, the enhanced risk understanding plays a leading role in intermediation activities of banks where risk management is considered to be one of the most significant activities.

Similarly, table 4.79 shows a positive strong correlation between risk identification (Risk_I) and risk management practices (Risk_MP) because the correlation coefficient for this correlation is .573* which is significant at a significant level of .05* as its p-value (.003) is less than the significant level of .05*. These results are consistent with the previous research by Tchankova (2002), Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei, 2007, Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi, 2012, Bilal, Talib and Khan (2013) and Hassan (2009), according to which risk identification is the first step in the risk management process. An efficient and robust system of risk identification process assists bank management to identify risks at an early stage which helps in designing and implementing appropriate risk response strategies to cope with risks. Risk managers should investigate what is happening at all levels of banking operations. If financial institutions employ a sound system of risk identification, they can manage and respond to risks in an effective and timely manner.

Moreover, table 4.79 depicts that risk management practices (Risk_MP) and risk assessment (Risk_A) are strongly correlated with each other because the value of the correlation coefficient is .581* and the correlation between variables is significant at the significant level of .05* because its p-value (.025) is less than the significant level of .05*. These results are consistent with the previous research findings (Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi, 2012; PWC, 2008a; Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei, 2007 and SBP, 2003; 2010) which explain that there is a significant relationship between risk management and risk assessment and analysis. Quantification of risk is vital in order to assess and analyse risks and their impact on business operations. A sound system of risk assessment helps banks in developing and executing future action plans to manage risks. Qualitative and quantitative modelling techniques can be used by banks to quantify, measure and analyse risks. A sophisticated system of risk

assessment and analysis enhances the effectiveness of risk management functions which can increase the resilience against financial stress.

Furthermore, table 4.79 points out a strong positive correlation between risk monitoring (Risk_MC) and risk management practices (Risk_MP) with a correlation coefficient of .661**. As its p-value of .000 is less than the significant level of .01**, therefore, it can be summarised that risk monitoring is an influencing aspect of risk management. These findings are supported by Cumming and Hirtle (2001), Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi (2012) and Collier and Woods (2011), according to which there is a significant correlation between risk monitoring and controlling and risk management practices. Risk management departments in banks are responsible for risk monitoring and implementing risk management policies set by the board of directors in order to cope with existing and emerging risks arising from day to day operations of banks. Banks should decide their risk appetite and risk tolerance levels for effective management of risks which help bank management to develop appropriate risk response strategies. Banks can refine their risk management systems by giving more importance to their risk monitoring and controlling frameworks.

In addition, table 4.79 reports the correlation coefficient (r) for the relationship between risk management practices (Risk_MP) and managing market risk (Risk_MR, $r=.426^{**}$) which shows that there is a strong positive correlation between risk management practices and managing market risk and this correlation is significant because its p-value (.000) is less than the significant level of .001**.

These results are consistent with the previous research findings (Roy, 1952; Richard et al., 2008; Marschak, 1938; Jesswein, 2008; Hicks, 1962) according to which market risk is the risk arising from fluctuations in interest rates, stock prices, commodity prices and exchange rates. Market risk management has a positive association with risk management which helps bank management in measuring and analysing market risk. Various financial models are used by banks to deal with market risk. Financial models help banks to capture key elements that explore sensitivities and prices in financial markets. Moreover, the correlation coefficients for managing credit risk (Risk_CR, $r=.571^{**}$, p-value=000), managing operational risk (Risk_OR, $r=.538^{**}$, p-value=000) and managing liquidity risk (Risk_LR, $r=.468^{*}$, p-value=004) demonstrate that managing credit risk, managing operational risk and managing liquidity risk are strongly correlated with risk management practices and these correlations are significant because their p-values are less than the significant levels of .01** and .05*. As the values of the correlation coefficients (r) are positive and greater than zero; therefore it can be argued that there is a positive strong association between the above variables. These

results are in line with the previous research findings (Striscek, 2009; Ghosh, 2012; Greenbaum and Thakor, 2007) that credit risk is one of the most significant risks faced by the banking industry in recent times and it is considered as one of the main reasons for the failure of banks in recent years. Management of credit risk has a significant relationship with risk management because if banks have established a stringent system of risk management, it can help in managing credit risk more rigorously and efficiently. A sound system of credit risk management involves developing an environment that is suitable for managing credit risk, having an appropriate credit administration and establishing an efficient credit-granting process to assess the creditworthiness of the counterparties. Collateral, conditions, capital, cash flows and character are mostly used tools to evaluate credit risk (Van Greuning and Bratanovic, 2003). Banks should treat their operational risk management frameworks as independent and separate risk management functions in order to identify, evaluate, monitor and manage operational risk. The size and complexity of banking operations play a leading role in developing a sound system of operational risk. Operational risk management is developed after taking into account the targeted capital level, working environment and risk appetite of banks.

According to the financial intermediation theory, the provision of financial services and liquidity are the primary reasons for the existence of banks. Banks take deposits from the depositors and lend these deposits to businesses and individuals in the form of loans and thus earn interest income on these loans. These activities make banks vulnerable to liquidity risk which requires banks to maintain enough capital to cope with liquidity risk. Liquidity risk management is one of the most influencing aspects of the risk management process and has a positive relationship with risk management.

Different techniques are used by banks to cope with liquidity risk. Firstly, banks can invest in more liquid assets which can easily be converted into cash. Secondly, through diversification; banks can maintain extended sources of funds from various depositors and the central bank as a lender of last resort can assist banks in meeting liquidity requirements (Basel Committee on Banking Supervision, 2008a). These findings are also endorsed by DiMaggio and Powell (1983), according to which banks must take into account various kind of risks they face and should develop and design policies and procedures to manage various interrelated risks. Risk management policies and procedures are enforced on banks by virtue of direction, supervision and persuasion.

4.9.3 Regression Analysis

Testing of Relationship between Risk Management and its Key Aspects

As highlighted earlier in section 4.5.1, ordinary least square has been used in this study to evaluate the importance of the relationship between criterion and predictor variables. For this purpose, regression analysis has been undertaken with the help of IBM SPSS 25 after bearing into mind that the regression is a well-accepted and widely used statistical model used by many researchers namely Bilal, Talib and Khan (2013), Hassan, (2011) & Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei, (2007).

Acceptance or rejection of hypothesis H01 in the current research is based on the findings of regression analysis. To evaluate the relationship between variables, the following regression equation has been applied:

$$\text{Risk_MP} = f (\text{Risk_U}, \text{Risk_I}, \text{Risk_AA}, \text{Risk_MC}, \text{Managing_MR}, \text{Managing_CR}, \text{Managing_OR}, \text{Managing_LR})$$

Regression Tables

Table 4.80

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.850	.631	.721	.611

Table 4.81

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	337.212	8	42.825	117.812	.000
	Residual	94.713	241	.366		
	Total	437.612	249			

Table 4.82

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig (p)
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.414	1.264		1.442	.000
	Risk_U	.462	.369	.316	.219	.000
	Risk_I	.488	.319	.447	.144	.002
	Risk_AA	.512	.247	.318	.163	.005
	Risk_MC	.334	.413	.228	.522	.041
	Managing_MR	.762	.251	.349	1.063	.000
	Managing_CR	.412	.134	.311	.169	.004
	Managing_OR	.769	.236	.241	.417	.000
	Managing_LR	.814	.270	.339	.062	.045

Where,
 Risk_MP: risk management practices
 Risk_U: risk understanding, Risk_I: risk identification, Risk_AA: risk assessment & risk analysis
 Risk_MC: risk monitoring & controlling, Managing_MR: managing market risk, Managing_CR: managing credit risk, Managing_OR: managing operational risk, Managing_LR: managing liquidity risk, Risk_MP: risk management practices.
 Correlation is significant at: 5% & 1% levels

Tables 4.80-4.82 present the findings of the regression analysis. Results of the regression analysis indicate that all independent variables are significantly related to risk management practices and their individual relationships are discussed in the following sections.

Capital R is a multiple correlation coefficient that facilitates in determining how strongly the various independent variables are related to the dependent variable. R is .85 in table 4.80 which shows that 85% of variations in independent variables are explained by the dependent variables. Whereas R^2 is .631 in table 4.80 which demonstrates that seven independent variables explain 63% of variations in risk management practices. Table 4.82 presents the regression results of all independent variables. Beta (the standardized coefficient) and the significant values (p-values) have been used to investigate the relationship between variables and test the hypothesis. Whereas, the beta compares the contribution of each independent variable in order to explain the dependent variable. A positive beta leads to a positive contribution to the dependent variable and indicates a positive relationship with other variables. Similarly, if the p-value for a variable is smaller than its significant level (5% or 1%) then it is statistically significant with the dependent variable.

Table 4.82 indicates that all independent variables are significantly correlated to the risk management practices (Risk_MP) because their beta values are positive and have significant values of $p = .000$. Therefore, it can be argued that these variables have a positive correlation with each other.

According to the regression results reported in the above table, a positive significant impact of risk understanding has been reported on risk management practices as $\beta = .316$ & $p = .000$, $t = .219$ at a significant level of 1%. These findings show that risk understanding has a positive beta coefficient of .316 and its p-value is less than the significant level of 1% which means that risk understanding makes a positive contribution to the explanation of dependent variable such as risk management practices and is statistically significant at 1% significant level. A positive beta coefficient of .316 indicates that an increase of one standard deviation in the independent variable (risk understanding) leads to an increase of a standard deviation in the dependent variable (risk management practices). Moreover, the findings of the Pearson correlation reported in table 4.79 also support these findings and have shown a positive correlation between risk understanding and risk management practices. Therefore, an inference can be drawn that risk management practices followed by banks are significantly influenced by risk understanding. These findings also depict that understanding of risk and risk management is an important aspect of risk management in banks. These findings are consistent with the previous research findings (Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei, 2007; Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi, 2012; Hassan, 2011) according to which adequate understanding of risks by bank employees assist in coping with various kinds of risks inherent in the banking operations. Therefore, a sound system of risk understanding plays a leading role in intermediation activities of banks where management of various risks is considered to be one of the most significant activities. Therefore, the above findings demonstrate that risk understanding has a significant positive relationship with risk management practices.

For the relationship between risk identification and risk management practices; table 4.82 reports the findings of the regression analysis according to which $\beta = .447$, $t = .144$ & $p = .002$. According to these results, beta is positive and the p-value is less than the significant value of 5% which demonstrates that risk identification significantly leads to the explanation of risk management practices. A positive beta coefficient depicts that an increase of one standard deviation in risk identification leads to an increase of a standard deviation in risk management practices and shows a statistically significant relationship with each other because their p-value is smaller than the significant value of 5%. Findings of the correlation analysis (table 4.79) also substantiate these results which indicate a positive correlation

between risk management practices and risk identification. These results are consistent with the previous research findings (Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi, 2012; Hudin and Hamid, 2014; Hassan, 2009) according to which risk identification is a vital aspect of the risk management process in banks. It is important for banks to develop and implement a rigorous and comprehensive structure of risk identification in order to deal with risks irrespective of whether these risks are in direct control of banks or not. Therefore, a positive significant relationship between risk identification and risk management practices emphasises the need for a rigorous risk identification framework in order to enhance the effectiveness of risk management practices in London banks.

Regression results with regards to the relationship between risk management practices and assessment and analysis of risk have the beta, $\beta = .318$, $t = .163$ & $p = .005$. A positive beta shows that risk assessment and analysis make a unique positive contribution to risk management practices and this relationship is statistically significant at a 5% significant level. These findings are also reinforced by the findings of the correlation analysis in table 4.79 which indicate a positive correlation between risk assessment and analysis and risk management practices. Therefore, these results confirm risk assessment as an influencing aspect of risk management in banks and these variables are significantly correlated to each other. These results are in line with the findings of the previous research (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983; Hassan, 2011; Bilal, Talib and Khan, 2013) which explain that it is important for banks to design, implement and review a rigorous system of risk assessment and analysis in order to meet the regulatory requirements of central banks. A direct association between risk management practices and risk assessment and analysis indicates that banks can enhance the efficiency of their risk management practices by giving more attention and focus to their risk assessment models and techniques.

Moreover, the regression results for the association between risk management practices and risk monitoring and controlling indicate that $\beta = .228$, $t = .522$, $p = .041$. A positive beta coefficient and a smaller p-value indicate that risk monitoring and controlling makes a positive contribution to the explanation of risk management practices and have a statistically significant relationship with risk management practices. Findings of the Pearson correlation also endorse these results which demonstrate that risk monitoring and controlling are positively correlated to risk management practices and highlight an active relationship with risk management practices. These findings are also consistent with the empirical findings of previous research (Kao et al. 2011; Pastor, 1999) according to which risk monitoring is a significant aspect of risk management in banks. Banks are required to develop and design

policies of risk monitoring and controlling for effective and timely management of risks irrespective of their size and complexity of their business operations. Considering a direct relationship between risk management practices and risk monitoring and controlling, an inference can be drawn that an improvement in risk monitoring and controlling can increase the effectiveness of risk management functions in London banks. Timely assessment and identification of risks enable banks to accept those risks which are in line with their risk appetite and risk tolerance. Therefore, the management of risks is not only significant for the banking industry but also plays a leading role in enhancing the growth of the economy and increasing consumer confidence in the banking sector. SBP (2003) and Oldfield and Santomero (1997) support these findings and point out that risk management is a complete set of various activities including identification, analysis, assessment, supervision, follow up and monitoring of risks in order to make sure that bank managers who are responsible for risk management understand various kinds of risks and their risk exposures are in line with the limits set by the board. Banks need to hold enough resources to cope with risks and their risk response strategies and policies should be in line with the objectives set by the board.

Based on the regression results, a positive significant influence of managing market risk has been reported on the risk management practices because $\beta = .349$, $t=1.063$ & $p = .000$. A positive beta coefficient of .349 indicates that an increase of one standard deviation in managing market risk leads to an increase of a standard deviation in risk management practices. Therefore, it shows a direct positive relationship that is statistically significant because its p-value (.000) is smaller than the significant value of 1%. Pearson correlation results also support these findings and reveal a positive correlation between risk management practices and managing market risk. Both regression and correlation results demonstrate that risk management practices are significantly inclined by market risk management which confirms that managing market risk is another significant aspect of risk management in banks. These findings are in line with the findings of the previous research (Mehta et al., 2012; Pyle, 1997; Christie, 2000) according to which market risk is one of the most significant risks faced by banks in the current business environment. In order to cope with market risk, banks need to implement both quantitative and qualitative models to measure and evaluate market risk. An active relationship between managing market risk and risk management practices can help banks to improve their risk management frameworks by improving their existing market risk models.

The association between risk management practices and managing credit risk has $\beta = .311$, $t=.169$ & $p=.004$ which shows a positive relationship between variables. A positive beta

indicates that managing credit risk makes a positive contribution to risk management practices which means that an increase of one standard deviation in managing credit risk results in an increase of a standard deviation in the risk management practices. The relationship between both variables is statistically significant because their p-value of .004 is less than the significant level of 5%. Therefore, the relationship between variables is statistically significant which influences the risk management practices of London banks. Furthermore, these findings are also endorsed by the Pearson correlation analysis (table 4.79) which has determined a positive significant influence of managing credit risk on risk management practices. Therefore, it can be argued that there is a significant association between managing credit risk and risk management practices. These results are supported by the earlier argumentations presented in existing literature (Musyoki and Kadubo, 2012; Hennie, 2003; Basel Committee, 2000) which highlight that the potency of management of credit risk is a key element of a rigorous approach to risk management in banks. A significant positive relationship between risk management practices and managing credit risk postulates that a robust system of credit risk management is vital to enhance the efficiency of risk management practices followed by London banks.

Moreover, the regression results in table 4.82 indicate that managing operational risk has a direct impact on the risk management practices because $\beta = .241$, $t=.417$, $p=.000$. A positive beta value and a smaller p-value of .000 show that managing operational risk has a statistically significant relationship with risk management practices. A positive beta value illustrates that operational risk management makes a positive contribution to risk management practices and it is a significant aspect of risk management. These findings are also substantiated by the findings of the Pearson correlation which highlight a positive correlation between both variables. These results are consistent with the existing literature (Stan-Madduka, 2010; Chapelle et al., 2007) on risk management according to which operational risk is one of the key risks faced by banks and banks can effectively deal with operational risk by adopting a stringent system of operational risk management.

The relationship between managing liquidity risk and risk management practices has been determined with the help of regression analysis according to which $\beta = .339$, $t=.062$, $p=.045$. According to the regression results, a positive beta of .339 depicts that managing liquidity risk makes a unique positive contribution to risk management practices and shows a positive relationship with risk management practices. Moreover, its p-value (.045) is less than the significant level of 5% which means that liquidity risk management has a statistically significant relationship with risk management practices.

These results are substantiated by the findings of the correlation analysis according to which there is a positive correlation between managing liquidity risk and risk management practices. These results are also consistent with the empirical findings of the previous research (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983; Shafique, Hussain and Hassan, 2013) which illustrate that liquidity risk management is a significant aspect of risk management and all banks need to implement a sound system of liquidity risk management in order to fulfil the regulatory requirements of central banks and financial regulators. A significant relationship between risk management practices and liquidity risk management indicates that the efficiency of risk management practices of London banks can be increased by improving the models and procedures for managing liquidity risk. A sound system of risk management framework consists of key aspects and all aspects play a significant role in coping with risks. Banks are required to apply and enforce rules set by the regulatory bodies and the central banks for timely and effective management of risks (Hassan, 2011; Greuning, 2008; Abu Hassan and Al-Ajmi, 2012).

4.10 Summary

This section has discussed the findings of hypothesis H01 that had been established to investigate the relationship between various aspects of risk management and risk management practices. Multiple aspects of risk management have also been determined with the help of Ordinary Least Square regression and Pearson correlation to meet the aim and objectives of the research. Based on the findings of correlation and regression analyses, it can be argued that all aspects of risk management have a significant positive relationship with risk management practices. A significant positive relationship has been confirmed between risk management practices and risk understanding, risk identification, risk assessment, risk monitoring and controlling, managing credit risk, managing market risk, managing operational risk and managing operational risk. Therefore, these findings confirm this hypothesis. Certain assumptions of institutional theory used for this study have been tested through the findings of the analysis. The findings of this chapter support the uniformity assumption of an institutional theory under which banks in the UK specifically HSBC and LLOYDS need to adopt various risk management practices to meet the regulatory requirements.

In addition to survey questionnaire data, the current research has conducted secondary data analysis to determine the relationship between capital the banks (HSBC & LLOYDS) hold and risk management in the form of risk weighted assets.

Next section puts the spotlight on the secondary quantitative data analysis and its findings:

Part 5

4.11 Relationship between risk management and the amount of capital banks hold

Quantitative Data Analysis and its Findings

As one of the research questions in this work is to determine the relationship between risk management and capital adequacy of banks within the context of HSBC and LLOYDS (see section 3.2.3), therefore, the Pearson correlation and regression models have been employed to explore the relationship between the dependent and independent variables:

In Case of HSBC

Dependent Variable: Amount of capital (Total capital; equity tier 1 and tier 2 capital)

Independent Variable: risk-weighted assets

In Case of LLOYDS

Dependent Variable: Amount of capital (Total capital; equity tier 1 and tier 2 capital)

Independent Variable: risk-weighted assets

Hypothesis

Hypothesis H02 has been established to examine the relationship between the amount of capital banks maintain and their risk-weighted assets.

H02: There is a positive significant relationship between capital adequacy of banks and risk management

Pearson correlation and regression analysis have been utilised to test the correlation between variables. The following regression equation has been used in this study for regression analysis (Gujarati and Porter, 2009; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2007):

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Here, β_1 and β_2 are the regression coefficients which point out the value at which dependent variable changes with the changes in the independent variable. Y is the value of the dependent variable whereas X1 and X2 indicate the values of the independent variables.

Results of correlation and Regression analysis have been reported in the following tables.

Table 4.83

Correlations			
		Risk Weighted Assets (LLOYDS) \$m	Total Capital (Tier1 & Tier2): LLOYDS \$m
Risk Weighted Assets (LLOYDS) \$m	Pearson Correlation	1	.832**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003
	N	10	10
Total Capital (Tier1 & Tier2): LLOYDS \$m	Pearson Correlation	.832**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	
	N	10	10
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Table 4.84

Correlations			
		Risk Weighted Assets (HSBC) \$m	Total Capital (Tier1 & Tier2): HSBC \$m
Risk Weighted Assets (HSBC) \$m	Pearson Correlation	1	-.050
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.891
	N	10	10
Total Capital (Tier1 & Tier2): HSBC \$m	Pearson Correlation	-.050	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.891	
	N	10	10

Varied findings have come out as a result of correlation analysis. The above tables 4.83 and 4.84 demonstrate that the value of coefficient (r) is 0.832 which shows a positive strong relationship between risk-weighted assets and capital adequacy of LLOYDS. In the case of HSBC, the value of coefficient (r) is -.050 which indicates a negative medium relationship between risk-weighted assets and capital adequacy of HSBC. Detailed analysis and discussion of results have been presented in the next chapter, section 5.4. Regression findings have been discussed after reviewing the results of the following tables 4.85 to 4.90.

Regression: HSBC

Table 4.85

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.050	.02	-.122	16831.045

Table 4.86

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5662019.526	1	5662019.526	.020	.891
	Residual	2266272689.37	8	283284086.172		
	Total	2271934708.90	9			

Table 4.87

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	176935.498	16925.064		10.454	.051
	Risk Weighted Assets (HSBC) \$m	.002	.017	-.050	-.141	.891

Regression: LLOYDS

Table 4.88

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.832	.693	.654	3905.868

Table 4.89

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	275327358.495	1	275327358.495	18.047	.003
	Residual	122046431.605	8	15255803.951		

	Total	397373790.100	9			
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Table 4.90

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15233.985	6627.476		2.299	.000
	Risk Weighted Assets (LLOYDS) \$m	.111	.026	.832	4.248	.003

As mentioned earlier in section 4.11, Hypothesis H02 has been established to determine the relationship between the amount of capital banks hold and their risk weighted assets. Pearson correlation and regression analyses have been conducted to test the relationship between variables. In the case of HSBC, regression table 4.85 shows that $R^2 = .02$ which means that only 2% variations in the amount of capital HSBC currently holds are due to its risk-weighted assets. In addition, $\beta = -.05$ & $p = .051$ (table 4.87) which means that risk management in the form of risk weighted assets has a negative effect on the capital sufficiency of HSBC and the p value shows no correlation between capital and risk-weighted assets which means that in case of HSBC, risk management does not influence the capital adequacy of HSBC. By contrast, the value of R^2 is .69 for LLOYDS (table 4.88) which shows that 69% variation in LLOYDS' Capital is due to its risk-weighted assets. $\beta = .832$ & $p = .000$ (table 4.90) which confirms a positive influence of risk management on the capital adequacy of LLOYDS because higher Beta coefficients show a unique and extensive contribution of risk weighted assets to capital adequacy of LLOYDS.

Mixed results came out in the light of Pearson correlation and regression analysis for HSBC and LLOYDS. A final inference cannot be drawn that there is a significant relationship between the amount of capital banks hold and their risk-weighted assets until a detailed analysis and discussion of findings has been conducted. For that reason, a detailed discussion of results has been presented in the next chapter (analysis and discussion chapter, section 5.4).

4.12 Summary

The current chapter has discussed the findings of data analysis undertaken for interviews conducted with banking professionals, survey questionnaire and secondary quantitative data. For this purpose, this chapter had been divided into five parts that have been discussed in earlier sections. For interview data analysis, thematic analysis has been conducted to explore the opinions and feedbacks of interviewees on risk management. In addition, descriptive and statistical analyses have been employed to analyse survey questionnaire and secondary quantitative data to answer the research questions of the study.

However, analysis and discussion of findings have been presented in next chapter (analysis and discussion chapter) in which the findings of thematic analysis; descriptive and statistical analysis have been compared and corroborated with the literature review to substantiate the findings in order to achieve the overall aim of this study.

Chapter Five: Analysis and Discussion

5.1 Introduction

This is the analysis and discussion chapter in which the findings of data analysis have been discussed in detail, corroborated and compared with literature review, research questions and objectives of the research to substantiate the findings and thus to meet the overall aim of the current study. Findings of data analysis are critically discussed after keeping in mind the research questions and the objectives of the current work. The following sections aim to present an in-depth discussion regarding the empirical findings discussed in chapter 4:

5.2 Key risks faced by HSBC and LLOYDS

In this study, the main risks faced by London banks within the context of HSBC and LLOYDS have been explored by interview data analysis with the help of thematic analysis (section 4.3.1), descriptive analysis (questionnaire data analysis: section 4.5.3) and literature review (section 2.2). The following sections aim to shed light on the detailed discussion of findings with regards to thematic analysis, descriptive analysis, and literature review which helps in determining the key risks faced by London banks.

Different opinions have come out with regards to the determination of key risks encountered by HSBC and LLOYDS. The findings of this study are partially supported by those of Bank of England (2020), HSBC (2019), LLOYDS (2019), Hassan (2009) and Amjad et al (2012). The literature review presents a comprehensive discussion on the risks that are faced by London banks within the context of the Bank of England's Systemic Risk Survey (SRS) that is conducted every six months. HSBC and LLOYDS also detail the key risks that they face after bearing into mind their risk appetite and risk policies. Whereas the findings show just generic risks that are faced by HSBC and LLOYDS which do not reflect a true picture of risk management framework of London banks. According to interview data analysis (thematic analysis; section 4.3.1), banks in London are facing market risk, concentration risk, liquidity risk, and asset liability management risk. The thematic results reported in tables 4.2 and 4.3 recognized liquidity risks and asset-liability management risks (ALM) to be the most important risks faced by HSBC and LLOYDS. Liquidity is one of the vital factors enhancing the abilities of banks to meet their collateral and cash obligations without sustaining unacceptable losses. Short-term liquid assets and deposits are utilized by banks to finance their long term liabilities. Ultimately, this liability arrangement affects their funding facilities and reflects the asset-liability management policies of banks. Therefore, many respondents believed that by adopting an effective asset-liability management framework, banks in

London can manage their liquidity and enable banking institutions to maintain appropriate balance sheet structure and adequate liquidity.

Some respondents from HSBC believed that bank may suffer from concentration risk because of a lack of diversification and taking a large position in a single market and risk exposure (table 4.3A). The risk of default is a significant driver leading to concentration risk for many respondents working in risk management departments in HSBC and LLOYDS. Risk of default necessitates the need for determining the extent to which outstanding loans of banks match the overall risk posed by the UK economy.

Market risk is another risk that has been considered to be the most important risk faced by London banks (table 4.4, appendix 2). Some respondents from LLOYDS considered fluctuations in equity prices, market volatility, and interest rates the most likely reasons for market risk in the bank. Therefore, in order to manage risks, banks are required by the regulators to adopt market risk framework as a central component of their independent risk function. Market risk management ensures that risk exposure of banks is aligned with the approved appetite commensurate with their defined risk management strategy.

Similarly, descriptive findings reported in section 4.6, tables 4.52 to 4.66 (appendix 2) indicate that there are six key risks that are currently faced by HSBC and LLOYDS across London. Those risks include market risk, liquidity risk, asset liability management risk, interest rate risk, operational risk, and credit risk. According to these findings, market risk has been found one of the key risks currently faced by banks in London with a higher percentage of 56.9% among other risks. Similarly, when respondents were questioned about the severity of risks faced by London banks, interesting responses came out. Almost most of the risks discussed above have been considered important in the current volatile business environment. However, using the ordinal scale, it has been revealed that market risk is the most important risk with a higher percentage of 72.8%.

Findings of thematic and descriptive analysis are partially endorsed by those of Bank of England (2020), HSBC (2019), and LLOYDS (2019) (literature review, section 2.2). The findings of this work show that market risk, liquidity risk, asset-liability management risk, interest rate risk, operational risk, credit risk, and concentration risk are key risks faced by London banks. Whereas, England (2020), HSBC (2019) and LLOYDS (2019) suggest that credit risk, market risk, operational risk, liquidity risk, political risk, risk of cyber attack, interest rate risk, underwriting risk, model risk, capital risk, and geopolitical risk are the principal risks currently faced by HSBC and LLOYDS. Hassan (2009) explored the most important risks faced by banks of Brunei Darussalam according to which operational risk,

credit risk and foreign exchange risk are the key risks encountered by banks in Brunei Darussalam. Similarly, Amjad et al (2012) argue that political risk, foreign exchange risk and credit risks are the most imperative risks faced by banks in Pakistan.

The researcher believes that findings with regards to investigating the key risks faced by London banks do not give a comprehensive answer to this question. The findings indicate that market risk is the most important risk to HSBC and LLOYDS in London in the current business environment. As far as the researcher knows, London banks may be facing credit risk because it is one of the most important risks that results in financial losses if counterparties and customers are unable to meet financial obligations under a contract. Credit risk arises from leasing businesses, loans and advances, direct lending, trade finance, credit derivative, and guarantees.

Credit risk exposes banks to huge financial losses and impairment charges. For example, on 31 December 2018, HSBC granted loans and advances of \$990bn to the customers and these loans and advances increased to \$1,045bn on 31 December 2019. Accordingly, total credit losses on the loans increased from \$1.8bn (2018) to \$2.8bn (2019). Similarly, LLOYDS offered loans of £m 1,063 in 2019 as compared to £m 861 in 2018 and its credit loss allowances increased from 3.7% in 2018 to 4.1 % in 2019. Therefore, the findings of this study are not comprehensively endorsed by existing literature on risk management.

Considering the findings that the researcher has examined it can be argued all the risks discussed above are equally important and capital risk, interest rate risk, credit risk, market risk, operational risk, liquidity risk, risk of a cyber attack, underwriting risk, model risk, and geopolitical risk are main risks currently faced by HSBC and LLOYDS. However, credit risk has been found as the principal risk faced by London banks.

5.3 The risk management practices followed by HSBC & LLOYDS and their effectiveness

As discussed in the literature review, there are many risk management practices that are followed by banks. For example, stress testing, capital planning, Basel accords, hedging techniques, options, swaps, futures, forward contracts, capital planning and risk management frameworks are used by banks to manage the risk exposures of banks (Tufano, 1996; Hassan, 2009; Mok and Saha, 2017). Thematic analysis and descriptive statistics have assisted the current research to investigate the risk management practices followed by LLOYDS and HSBC. The findings of the thematic analysis reported in section 4.3.1, tables 4.5 to 4.10 (appendix 2) indicate that a stringent system of risk management is essential for banks to

cope with different risks they face that may have a potentially unpleasant impact on their business operations. The findings indicate that HSBC is more focusing on stress testing, Basel accords, and hedging to manage risks. However, most of the respondents from LLOYDS and HSBC emphasised the need for using hedging techniques such as futures, options, swaps and forward contracts. The findings are in line with existing literature on risk management as hedging, stress testing and Basel accords are widely used risk management instruments in banks (Tufano, 1996; Hassan, 2009; Kumru and Sarntisart, 2016). In Canada and the United States, there are 50 closely watched and publicly traded firms which share a clear and common risk exposure as they are exposed to multiple risks. These firms use various risk management practices such as hedging, options, swaps and forward contracts to cope with risks. Quarterly reporting of risk management instruments used by firms in USA and Canada provide shareholders and investors with a bulk of information on the use of hedging, forward sales, options and other embedded risk management activities which allow analysts to determine the effective measures of the extent of risk management practices undertaken (Tufano, 1996).

However, it is important to note that thematic findings do not show that HSBC and LLOYDS are using capital planning to manage risks which contradicts the findings of Mok and Saha, (2017). Capital planning is a new regulatory measure introduced by regulators which assist banks to plan their capital structures thereby enabling them to weather future events. As London banks are major commercial banks in the UK, the researcher believes that apart from using stress testing and hedging techniques, capital planning may also assist banks in managing financial challenges.

In addition, thematic findings indicate that innovative financial products offered by HSBC and LLOYDS and nature of risks faced by both banks emphasise the need for adopting robust risk mitigation tools to mitigate risks after taking into account their risk appetite and risk tolerance. However, most of the respondents asserted that various hedging techniques i.e. financial derivatives including futures, swaps, options and forward contracts are used by banks to hedge risks. In addition, interviewees asserted that hedging employs various risk management techniques but takes equal and opposite positions in two different markets i.e. future and cash markets. HSBC is perceived to be using hedging to protect its capital against adverse effects of inflation by investing in high yields financial instruments such as shares, notes and bonds.

The findings reported in tables 4.15 to 4.17 (appendix 2) highlight that risk management framework utilised in London banks consists of various components such as understanding of

risk, identification of risk, assessment and analysis of risk, monitoring and controlling of risk, management of market risk, liquidity risk and operational risk etc. This is consistent with previous empirical research which demonstrates that risk management practices followed by banks in Brunei Darussalam consist of four main variables such as understanding, supervision, evaluation, monitoring and analysis of risks. These findings are also supported by Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei, (2007) and Amjad et al (2012) which determined risk management practices in UAE and Pakistani banks. However, thematic findings do not show which variables are the most influencing variables in risk management practices which are determined by descriptive statistics.

Descriptive statistics (section 4.9.1) have been undertaken on the evaluation of key components of risk management. The highest mean value is 4.77 (table 4.70) for the question with regards to the understanding of risk management in banks and the SD is .625 which shows that data values are close to the mean values and are not distant from 1. The higher mean and lower standard deviation values show that the majority of the participants either agreed or strongly agreed that there is a general understanding of risk management across London banks. The findings confirm those of Boston Consulting Group (2011), Hassan (2009) and Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei (2007) that it is vital for employees of banks to understand the dynamics of risks that are inherent and exposed to the operations of banks. Sound knowledge of risks and risk management plays a central role in enhancing the ability of banks to weather financial stress.

On the other hand, table 4.70 reports the lowest mean of 3.67 and a standard deviation of .271 which indicates that the data points are close to the mean of 3.67. The lowest mean value and a smaller standard deviation value indicate that majority of the respondents agreed that responsibility for risk management is explicitly defined across London banks. These findings are in line with the general literature indicating that for a stringent risk management system in banking institutions; responsibility for risk management is clearly defined and communicated to all staff working in banks (Kromschroder and Luck, 1998; HSBC, 2019; LLOYDS, 2018; Amjad et al, 2012). To the best knowledge of the researcher, as HSBC and LLOYDS are big banks in the UK, both banks are using three lines of defence in their risk management frameworks which highlight that there is a requirement for reporting and disclosure of risk management activities to those charged with governance and responsibility and accountability for risk management is defined across London banks.

Furthermore, the overall mean value of 4.2 for all four questions with regards to risk understanding is higher than the midpoint value of 3 on the five-point Likert scale. This

higher average value than midpoint value shows that overall all managers and risk managers in HSBC and LLOYDS across London have a sound understanding of risks in their banks. These results have been qualitatively corroborated with those existing literature on risk management such as (Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi, 2012; Al-Tamimi, 2002, Hassan, 2011, Al-Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei, 2007).

The higher mean value of 4.48 in table 4.71 reveals that London banks emphasise the need for adopting and implementing a sound system of risk identification in the banks. The standard deviation reported in table 4.71 is .411 which is close to the mean value of 4.48 and less than 1 indicating that a large number of who surveyed either strongly agreed or agreed that it is vital for banking institutions to utilise widely accepted methods of identification of risks. This is supported by existing literature demonstrating that risk identification is the first step towards a risk management system in banks (Luck, 1998; Pausenberger and Nassauer, 2000; Kromschroder and Luck, 1998). Various risk identification models have been suggested in the existing literature which requires banks to implement for effective identification of risks. These techniques include scenario analysis, risk mapping, risk workshops, checklists of possible disturbances and breakdowns, early warnings, internal inspections, and an examination of corporate processes, interviews and loss balance.

On the other hand, the second item regarding the respondents' opinions on whether the banks encounter challenges when prioritising risks in the banks has the smallest mean of 3.68 and the smaller standard deviation of .643 which is less than 1 which indicates that data points are not dispersed from 1. The smallest mean of 3.68 demonstrates that the majority of the respondents believe that banks face challenges when prioritising risks. In addition, the average mean value of all questions relating to risk identification in table 4.71 is 3.95 which is greater than the midpoint value on the five-point Likert scale (3) reflecting that bank managers and risk managers in London banks are good at identifying risks they face. In addition, these findings have been endorsed with available literature undertaken by various researchers including Hassan (2011), Nazir, Daniel and Nawaz (2012), Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi (2012). Furthermore, as far as the researcher knows, banks can face challenges when prioritising risks because of their innovative financial products and services, the types of risks they are exposed to, the complexity of operations and sophisticated information systems.

Table 4.72 outlines the mean and standard deviation pertaining to risk evaluation and investigation in London banks. The maximum mean of 4.79 is associated with the question pertaining to quantitative methods of risk assessment used by London banks. Its associated standard deviation is .411 which is close to the mean of 4.79 which indicates that the majority

of the respondents either strongly agreed or agreed with the question of the use of quantitative methods of risk assessment by HSBC and LLOYDS. These findings are in line with the existing conceptual studies on risk assessment and analysis with regards to mitigation and measurement of risks (Pausenberger and Nassauer, 2000; Fuser et al, 1999; Drzik, 1995). In order for the exact measurement of risks; banks must use appropriate models to quantify potential losses and the corresponding probability of occurrence of risks. It is vital for banks to point out the developments with the utmost possibility to quantify potential losses that may affect banks. For adequate analysis and investigation of risks, it can be argued that risks can be categorized appropriately after taking into account the likelihood of their occurrence and associated losses.

The smallest mean value of 3.69 and a standard deviation of .834 are associated with the question: The bank depends on the outcome of numeric statistics with human judgment. The smaller values of mean and standard deviation indicate that those surveyed agreed with this question that London banks rely on the outcome of quantitative data. These findings are consistent with the empirical findings of Fuser et al, 1999; Drzik, 1995; Pausenberger and Nassauer, 2000) meaning that if banks are utilizing quantitative methods of risk assessment appropriately, they can rely on their outputs if models are applied effectively and interpreted appropriately. These findings are also in line with the existing literature (Radu, 2020; Rot, 2008) showing that banks can use quantitative and qualitative methods of risk assessment for timely and effective management of risks. Quantitative methods include the information security risk analysis method, Fisher's method, annual loss expected method, and derived ratios. Qualitative methods consist of failure mode and effects criticality analysis, failure mode and effects analysis. However, the overall mean value of all questions is 3.97 which is greater than the Likert scale value of 3. Considering the findings that the researcher has examined; it is argued that London banks have a sound system of risk assessment and analysis to deal with financial challenges.

Risk monitoring and controlling are employed to make sure that risk management guidelines are consistent with the desired practices of risk management. Table 4.73 reports the results of mean and standard deviation. The question: supervising the effectiveness of risk management is a key component of the management reporting process has the highest mean of 4.78 and a standard deviation of .561 which means that data points are close to the mean of 4.78. This higher and lower standard deviation illustrates that most of the participants either agreed or strongly agreed that monitoring the effectiveness of risk management is a fundamental component of reporting processes in London banks. These results confirm the findings of

(Irm, Airmic and Alarm; 2002; Pausenberger and Nassauer, 2005) that a sound system of risk management requires an appropriate structure of monitoring, controlling and reporting of risks in order to make it certain that risks are recognized and assessed effectively and adequate risk responses and controls are in place. By contrast, the question pertaining to opinions of research participants on whether the risk response of bank incorporates action plans with regards to the implementation decisions about identified risk has the lowest mean of 3.48 and a standard deviation of 1.180. These results point out that the majority of who surveyed are not agreed with this statement which means that actions plans are not a part of banks' response strategies and implementation decisions because standard deviation is greater than 1 which means that data points are dispersed from the mean. These findings contradict the findings of (Irm, Airmic and Alarm; 2002; Pausenberger and Nassauer, 2005; Oliveira et al., 2011) that banks must develop risk response and control strategies in response to identified risks. Control should be developed and monitored at various levels of banking operations. Management control is not sound enough for the proper execution of the monitoring function because they do not have enough time to practice far-reaching monitoring and control. Therefore, an internal audit system is installed to carry out the task of internal supervision. However, the overall mean of 3.94 is greater than the mid-point value (3) on the five-point Likert scale which indicates that the majority of the respondents agreed that London banks are effectively monitoring and controlling risks.

In the case of managing market risk, the question within the context of market risk has the highest mean of 4.85 and a lower standard deviation of .719 (Table 4.74) which is close to the mean of 4.85 indicating that a significant number of research participants highly agreed or agreed that exposure of the market risk is established at prudent levels in London banks and capital is maintained in accordance with market risk. These findings are supported by existing literature (BIS, 2019; Gallati, 2003; Schroeck, 2002) that market risk is one of the most significant risks currently faced by banks due to changes in market prices of stocks and assets. However, it is worth pointing out here that in order to manage market risk for regulatory capital requirements; banks can use two methodologies including the internal models approach and the standardized approach for market risk that is discussed earlier in the literature review section 2.2. These findings also confirm the recommendations of the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision that capital requirements for market risk are established at prudent levels and are applied on a consolidated basis in London banks. It is important for banks to include the purchase and forward sales when determining capital requirements for market risk. According to the principles of the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision,

banks need to hold capital to counter market risk in a way that capital regulatory requirements are met on a regular basis.

By contrast, the question with regards to the assessment of bank to analysed risks consists of a cost-benefit evaluation of addressing risks has the lowest mean of 3.73 and a standard deviation of .741 which means that majority of the research participants agreed with this question. These findings are consistent with findings of the empirical literature (Schroeck, 2002 & Crouhy, Galai and Mark, 2006) that cost-benefit analysis of risk management must be taken into account when developing risk response strategies. These findings are endorsed by the findings of (BIS, 2019) that capital requirements are not only confined to market risk but also credit risk, liquidity risk and interest rate risk are influenced by the capital requirements. The researcher also believes that besides market risk, banks need to explore their capital requirements within the context of liquidity risk, operational risk and commodities risk.

With credit risk, the highest mean of 4.77 and a standard deviation of .712 (Table 4.75) are associated with the question concerning London banks which maintain a sound risk management system in the form of policies, infrastructure and processes. The higher mean and lower standard deviation indicate that a large number of the respondents are agreed or strongly agreed with the question that London banks are using a good system of credit risk management. These findings are reinforced by existing literature (Waemustafa and Sukri, 2015; Aven, 2016) that management of credit risk is the most significant factor in the modern business environment particularly in the banking sector where credit risk is the main driving factor towards influencing the revenue and performance of banks. These findings are also endorsed by the empirical findings of Ramachandran and Gavoury (2011) and Carbo and Rodriguez (2007) that banks need to design, build and execute policies and models to reduce and deal with credit risk. Various models and techniques are used by banks to cope with credit risks such as creditworthiness analysis, credit portfolio models, stress testing, internal ratings, inspection by branch managers, and risk rating method, exposure limit. The question in table 4.75: credit portfolio is monitored by the bank on day to day basis and takes action in case of any unpleasant credit events has the smallest mean of 3.68 and a smaller standard deviation of .705. The smaller standard deviation of .705 illustrates that data points are close to the mean of 3.68 which indicates that banks oversee their credit portfolios regularly and take remedial actions in case of unpleasant credit events.

Considering these findings that the researcher has examined; it can be argued that credit risk management in London banks is sound and robust because the overall mean value (3.21) of

all questions with regards to credit risk management is greater than the mid-point value on the five-point Likert scale.

The question relating to managing operational risk in London banks has the highest mean of 4.72 and a standard deviation of .937 (table 4.76) which is not far from 1 and is close to the mean of 4.72. This higher mean and the lower standard deviation are indicative of a large number of respondents who highly agreed or agreed that London banks adopt a sound system of operational risk. LLOYDS (2019), HSBC (2019), Gallati (2003) and Lowe (2010) confirm these findings that operational risk occurs due to failed and inappropriate people, internal processes or external events. For example, inefficient risk management systems of operational risk in HSBC and LLOYDS lead to adverse customer impact, financial losses, and reputational damage of banks. For that reason, London banks are using an appropriate system of operational risk management system. In HSBC, operational risk is monitored with the help of various internal risk management models and within the limits approved by management within a framework of delegated authorities. Operational risk is managed by using a stringent risk control framework that underpins consistent and explicit principles, guidance and policies for risk managers in HSBC (HSBC, 2019). Similarly, LLOYDS has designed and implemented effective controls in all its branches across the UK in order to manage operational losses, regulatory breaches and reputational events. Furthermore, LLOYDS is reviewing and investing in its control environment to address the inherent risks and employs various risk management strategies such as acceptance, transfer, mitigation and avoidance (LLOYDS, 2019).

The question concerning the preparedness of a periodic report on operational risk by London banks has the smallest mean of 3.58 and a standard deviation of .628 (Table 4.76). This lower mean and the standard deviation demonstrate that most of the research participants agreed with this question that London banks are preparing regular reports of operational risk. These findings are compatible with those of HSBC (2019) and LLOYDS (2019) that London banks are following corporate governance and risk management systems under which disclosure of risk management strategies and policies are necessary for transparency and enhancing the understanding of intended users of annual accounts of London banks. As far as the researcher knows and to the best knowledge of the researcher that is gained through extensive literature review (section 2.2) and review of annual accounts of London banks (HSBC, 2019, 2018, 2017; LLOYDS, 2019, 2018, 2017); reporting and disclosure of risk management strategies and changes in accounting and risk management policies are vital for banks in London.

The question: the bank adopts a comprehensive set of policies, guidelines and policies for managing liquidity risk has the highest mean of 4.32 and a standard deviation of .415 which is close to the mean of 4.32 (table 4.77). These values specify that a large number of participants are of the view that London banks are using effective policies and procedures for managing liquidity risk. These findings have been supported by available literature (Bank of England, 2020; Saunders and Cornett, 2008; Matz and Neu, 2006; HSBC, 2019; LLOYDS, 2019) which depict that HSBC and LLOYDS have designed, implemented and monitored policies in order to address liquidity risk. In HSBC, liquidity risk is determined by using appetites established as minimum ratios and targets. It is also projected and overseen against appetites with the help of scenario and stress testing. HSBC employs other measures to cope with liquidity risks such as liquidity resources and control of the capital in line with its cash flows and risk profiles (HSBC, 2019). Likewise, LLOYDS holds a sound balance sheet structure and liquidity profile that restricts its reliance on volatile means of funding. It manages and oversees liquidity risk and ensures that arrangements for liquidity risk management are appropriate within the context of its base (LLOYDS, 2019). The findings are also endorsed by empirical literature that the liquidity and funding positions of banks in the UK are underpinned by their sound customer deposit base and are also strengthened by stringent relationships across customer segments (Bank of England, 2020).

By contrast, the question concerning the periodic report of liquidity risk is regularly prepared by London banks has the lowest mean of 3.89 and a standard deviation of .518 (Table 4.77). The lowest mean of 3.89 shows that most of the respondents agreed with the question that London banks regularly prepare reports on liquidity risk. HSBC (2019), LLOYDS (2019) and the Bank of England (2020) endorse these findings according to which banks must need to disclose and report on the risk they face and risk management policies and processes used by banks in order to ensure transparency and increase the understanding of intended users of annual accounts. After reviewing the literature review and annual accounts of HSBC and LLOYDS, it can be argued that London banks are following a good system of liquidity risk and are reporting regularly on liquidity risk management.

Findings of descriptive statistics and thematic analysis are consistent with the findings of other relevant studies on risk management indicating that in the current business environment; banks need to use robust risk management practices consisting of different effective aspects of a sound risk management framework. These findings are in line with other pertinent studies undertaken by Walker (2009), Turner (2009), Abu Hussain and Al-Ajmi (2012), Hassan (2009). HSBC has been found with a more stringent risk management

system under the supervision of a chief risk officer with adequate resources, access, independence and stature to the board. Respondents from banks consistently claimed that the risk assessment system in the banks is responsive to changes in the business environment. Furthermore, there is an effective procedure for identifying, assessing and prioritizing the banking and emerging risks that play a vital role in managing key risks. Therefore, based on the responses of the respondents, it can be argued that all staff working in the banks have a sound understanding of what risks may be faced by banks and risk managers in the banks are overall responsible and accountable for risk management.

5.3.1 Relationship between Study Variables

The literature review (chapter 2, section 2.2) and the above discussion (section 5.3) highlight that there is a relationship between various aspects of risk management and risk management practices followed by London banks.

Hypothesis

H01: There is a positive significant relationship between risk management practices (RMPs) and understanding of risk, identification of risk, assessment and analysis of risk, monitoring and controlling of risk, management of market risk, management of credit risk, management of operational risk, and management of liquidity risk.

This study aims to test this hypothesis through statistical analysis. This section attempts to analyse and discuss the findings of multiple regression analysis as reported in section 4.5.2. The regression results with regards to the determination of risk management and aspects of risk management have been discussed deeply in tables 4.80 to 4.82 (chapter 4, section 4.9.3)

Acceptance of hypothesis H01

Considering the findings discussed in section 4.9.3, chapter 4, it can be argued that Hypothesis H01 is confirmed because all aspects of risk management have a positive significant relationship with risk management practices. From this, it can be concluded that risk understanding, risk identification, risk assessment and analysis, risk monitoring and controlling, managing liquidity risk, managing market risk, managing operational risk and managing credit risk are the most important and influencing variables in risk management practices and have a statistically significant relationship with risk management practices. This means that London banks need to give more attention to all these variables in order to make their risk management systems more effective and robust.

These findings are supported by other relevant studies on risk management conducted by (Bilal, Talib and Khan, 2013; Khalid and Amjad, 2012; Hassan, 2011; Hassan, 2009; Al-

Tamimi and Al-Mazrooei, 2007). It is worth discussing here that adequate understanding of risks and risk environment by banking staff can add value to the banks' risk management framework which enables them to manage risks effectively. Enhanced risk understanding of risk management can play an overriding part in the intermediation activities of banks where risk management is perceived to be one of the key banking activities. Therefore, a significant relationship between variables confirms that it is vital for the bank management to pay more attention and focus on the understanding of risks among employees of HSBC and LLOYDS to improve current risk management practices.

Hassan (2009) determined the risk management practices of banks in Brunei Darussalam and found that risk identification and risk assessment and analysis are the most influencing variables in risk management. These results are also supported by the empirical findings of Amjad et al (2012). According to Amjad et al (2012), understanding of risk management, managing credit risk and risk assessment are the most important variables. However, to the best knowledge of the researcher, understanding, identification, assessment and analysis of risk, risk monitoring and controlling, managing liquidity risk, managing market risk, managing operational risk and managing credit risk are the key variables that underpin a sound system of risk management. If anyone of these variables is insignificant and has no relationship with risk management, it may erode the efficiency of risk management systems in London banks.

Furthermore, these findings confirm the homogeneity assumption of institutional theory (section 2.4.3) that tends to be achieved by means of a coercive isomorphic mechanism which exerts regulatory pressures on banks in terms of direction and persuasion (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983; Hudin and Hamid, 2014). In the context of LLOYDS and HSBC, regression results endorse the policy implications of the Bank of England's risk management guidelines that encourage the appropriate risk identification and adequate reporting of various risks that are critical to be managed efficiently. Risk management guidelines of the BoE require all banks operating in the UK to set up and execute a sound system of risk identification to cope with all risks regardless of whether these risks are in their direct control or not. As a result, a significant positive association between risk identification and risk management practices emphasises the need for a sound risk identification framework to enhance the usefulness of risk management in HSBC and LLOYDS in London.

Reviewing the above-discussed assumption of institutional theory, the overriding principles of risk management introduced by the Bank of England are pertinent to all financial firms in

the UK and they are required to comply with those risk management guidelines irrespective of their size and nature of operations.

Thus, all banking institution in the UK particularly HSBC and LLOYDS are required to develop and execute a sound and efficient framework of risk monitoring and controlling for timely assessment and management of risks. From the above discussion, an inference can be drawn that both HSBC and LLOYDS can further improve their risks management frameworks by paying more attention to their risk monitoring and controlling systems, managing market risk, managing credit risk, managing liquidity risk and managing operational risk.

5.4 Relationship between risk management and the amount of capital banks hold

As discussed in the previous chapter, section 4.11, hypothesis H02 has been developed to test the relationship between the amount of capital banks hold and their risk-weighted assets.

H02: There is a positive significant relationship between capital adequacy of banks and risk management

This hypothesis has been tested on the basis of the values of R^2 , beta, significant levels (0.05* & 0.01**) and the p values. The significance of these indicators has already been discussed in the last section 5.3.1.

Varied results have come out within the context of correlation and regression analysis with regards to hypothesis H02. In case of HSBC, regression tables (4.85 to 4.87) show that $R^2 = .02$ (table 4.85) which indicates that only 2% variations in the amount of capital held by HSBC are explained by its risk-weighted assets. In addition, $\beta = -.05$ & $p = .051$ (table 4.87), negative beta coefficient shows that there is a negative correlation between risk management and capital held by HSBC which means that an increase of one standard deviation in the risk management results in a decrease of one standard deviation of capital HSBC. Therefore, it is indicative of an inverse relationship between both variables for HSBC. Furthermore, the p-value of .051 is higher than the significant level of 0.01** which demonstrates that the relationship between risk management and capital of HSBC is statistically insignificant as well.

By contrast, the value of R^2 is .69 (table 4.88) for LLOYDS which shows that 69% variations in LLOYDS' capital are explained by its risk-weighted assets. Whereas, $\beta = .832$ & $p = .000$ (table 4.90), a higher beta coefficient of .832 depicts that risk weighted assets makes an exclusive and strongest contribution to the dependent variable such as capital held by LLOYDS. In addition, capital of LLOYDS is statistically significant at 1% significant level

(0.01**) because its p-value of .000 is less than the significant level of 0.01**. These findings indicate that a statistically positive significant relationship exists between risk management and capital adequacy of LLOYDS. By contrast, in the case of HSBC, there is an inverse relationship between capital adequacy and risk management.

Rejection of hypothesis H02

Based on the above findings, hypothesis H02 is rejected due to varied findings of statistical analysis for LLOYDS and HSBC. However, as discussed in the literature review varied opinions have come out on the relationship of risk management and capital adequacy of banks. The findings of regression analysis to determine the relationship between bank capital and risk management confirm those of the FSA (2004) that the amount of capital held by building societies and banks depend on risk management, regulatory environment and market discipline. Building societies and banks in the UK hold more capital than required by the regulators because buffer capital facilitates banks in absorbing financial shocks. The amount of capital held by banks is not only required by regulators but also the risk preferences of bondholders, shareholders and managers play a critical role in determining the capital needs of banks.

Empirical literature by Osborne and Francis (2012) also supports the above findings and suggests that the capital requirements of banks affect their capital ratios. In response to the economic meltdown of 2007-08 policymakers have introduced key amendments to the prudential regulation of banks in the UK aiming at reducing the severity and likelihood of future crisis ahead. These changes include aligning the capital requirement with risk management, rise in capital requirements, and introduction of key policy tools such as countercyclical capital requirements and leverage ratio. Basel II aligns the amount of capital held by banks with the economic risk that is also called economic capital under which all banks are required to maintain capital equal to 8% of their risk-weighted assets (Heid, 2007). Aligning capital with risk management means that the bank maintains buffer capital after taking into account their risk-weighted assets that are the key measures of their capital requirements (FSA, 2004; Vallascas and Hagendorff, 2013; Rochet, 1992; Kim and Santomero, 1988).

Different opinions of interviewees also came out with regards to the question of the relationship between risk management and the amount of capital. Interview 1 was of the view that banks can reserve less capital because of the risk-sharing characteristics of capital rules. The risk-sharing principle was discussed by interviewee 3 according to which banks may be less vulnerable to economic shocks. Unfortunately, this principle is unlikely to be applied to

commercial banks as argued by respondents in table 4.25. Many interviewees revealed that banks are prone to various kinds of risks encouraging them to hold more capital in order to make them financially more resilient. Some interviewees argued that banks should adopt an internal performance management approach to determine the cost of capital and liquidity in their business decisions. Literature review (section 2.11) on risk management also supports these findings indicating that banks should maintain enough capital in the light of their risk-weighted assets, global financial meltdown and collapse of big firms such as Lehman Brothers, Northern Rock (Ciurlau, L., 2016; Jayadev, 2013; Berger et al, 1995; Leland, 1994).

On the contrary, some research scholars argue that risk management does not influence the amount of capital held by banks as in the case of HSBC in which there is an inverse relationship between its capital and risk management. If banks establish a strong system of risk management that enables them to manage risks they face thereby reducing the probability of maintaining more capital which in turn may reduce the costs associated with maintaining more capital (Stulz and DeAngelo, 2015). If banks have weak systems of corporate governance and risk management, they may need to maintain more capital to weather unpleasant financial events. As discussed earlier, statistical findings for HSBC indicate a negative correlation between its capital and risk management. Empirical literature explains the main reasons for this inverse relationship that is its strong risk management and corporate governance systems in place. For example, the risk management system of HSBC consists of three lines of defence which delineates responsibilities for risk management, the control environment, and management accountabilities (HSBC, 2019). Its board assumes overall responsibility for sound management of risks and approves its risk appetite. Similarly, the Royal Bank of Scotland has established a stringent system of risk management enabling it to deal with risks successfully. Its risk management framework consists of five lines of defence which includes management and supervision, oversight and control, and risk appetite (RBS, 2019).

Under the recommendations of the examiners, the underneath piece of work has been divided into three sections, each section sheds light on key points required by the examiners to be discussed individually. Section one aims to discuss the guidelines of the Bank of England with regards to the prudential regulations of banks in order to seek information relating to capital requirements and risk-weighted assets of banks. In section two, conclusions from meetings with HSBC and LLOYDS have been included and discussed in detail. Section three

explains the Pillar 3 disclosures of HSBC and LLOYDS in order to seek valuable information with regards to the risk-weighted assets (RWAs) and capital adequacy of banks.

Section 1: Prudential Regulations of the Bank of England (BoE)

The BoE oversees and regulates banks, building societies, investment firms and insurers through the Prudential Regulation Authority (PRA). According to the prudential guidelines of the BoE, all banks having a position in financial instruments for which no specific treatment has been explained in the CRR (capital requirements directive) are required to determine their own capital requirements of an appropriate percentage of their current value of the position by employing the most appropriate models with regards to the positions specified in the UK CRR. The PRA requires banks to hold enough capital and maintain stringent risk controls in place. The PRA has addressed material deficiencies in risk capture by banks' internal approach on market risk and has set out guidelines to estimate extra own funds by implementing Article 101 of CRD IV (Capital Requirements Directive). It requires banks to determine their own fund requirements for one or more types of market risk. The PRA has introduced a new framework called RNIV (Risks not in VaR) which requires banks and financial firms to identify other risks that are not captured by their internal risk assessment models (VaR and stressed VaR) and to maintain their own funds to cover those uncaptured risks by their internal models apart from holding funds to cover risks identified by the internal risk assessment models. Where appropriate, banks must ensure that they have extra funds for VaR and stressed VaR models. Banks are responsible for capturing additional risks which create opportunities for management and risk managers to evaluate the deficiencies in their risk assessment models (BoE, 2020).

The RNIV framework helps banks to ensure that they maintain their own funds to cope with all risks that are inadequately captured or not captured by the VaR and stressed VaR models of banks. These risk factors include illiquid risk factors, calibration parameters, cross risks, higher-order risks and basis risks. On a quarterly basis, banks need to systematically identify and evaluate poorly captured and non-captured risks and this estimation determines the losses that might arise due to non-captured or poorly captured risks by the internal risk assessment models of banks. In addition, the BoE requires banks to estimate a stressed VaR and VaR metric for each risk factor. The multipliers utilised for VaR and stressed VaR can assist banks in generating their own funds requirements.

Banks can have an option to determine the size of the risk with the help of stress testing only when they cannot estimate a VaR and stressed VaR metric for risk factors. For that reason, banks are required to ensure that the capital horizon and confidence level of the stress test are

commensurate with the liquidity of the risk under the internal models approach. This capital charge must be equal to the loss incurring from the stress test (BoE, 2021).

Under the Capital Requirements Directive (2013/36/EU) which is an EU legislative package applicable to banks, investment firms in the UK and across the globe, the PRA (Prudential Regulatory Authority) requires banks in the UK to determine their own funds requirements for market risk and credit risk on the basis of the external credit ratings to a large extent. Banks are required to use internal models or internal ratings-based models when credit risk is material in nature. On the other hand, where credit risk is less material; banks can use standardised approaches which are based on the external credit ratings. Under the new proposals of Capital Requirements Directive V on reducing reliance on external credit ratings, banks in the UK are encouraged to develop and use their own internal credit ratings rather than external ratings in order to estimate own funds requirements (BoE, 2021).

The recent financial crisis highlighted deficiencies in the regulatory framework and risk management systems of banks. In 2013, CRR (Capital Requirements Regulation) and CRD IV, the EU regulations tried to solve these issues by implementing Basel III and enhancing the quality and quantity of liquidity resources and banks' capital. New CRD V has been introduced by Basel III to enhance the financial resilience of banks. The PRA sets out measures and guidelines with regards to CRD V which requires banks to implement the Pillar2 approach of risk management and to use the IRRBB (interest rate banking book). It has also introduced the EU-specific regulations to harmonise macro and micro-prudential monitoring and to set out enhanced proportionality in prudential requirements. Under CRD V, the PRA has simplified the application of the guidance and supervisory requirements of Pillar 2 and has revised the governance requirements applicable to financial firms. The PRA has clarified the amount of capital stack, determined the maximum distributable amount (MDA), revised the capital buffers applied to banks and has set out regulatory measures to oversee, evaluate and control the interest rate risk in (IRRBB) banking book.

The PRA has issued guidelines with regards to setting Pillar 2 capital, the PRA buffer and the internal capital adequacy assessment process (ICAAP) of banks. The PRA requires banks not to maintain CRD IV buffer with any CET 1 capital (common equity tier 1) held to cover their total capital requirements (TCR). In order to estimate the quality and quantity of the Pillar 2A capital requirements, banks can apply under section 55M of the Financial Services and Markets Act 2000 (FSMA). The PRA can inform banks about the amount of capital they need to maintain over and above the amount of capital required to cover their total capital requirements and above the CRD IV buffers. Depending on the banks' specific supervisory

assessment, the PRA buffer is the significant amount of capital that allows banks to meet the overall financial adequacy requirements in internal capital adequacy Assessment 2.1 (BoE, 2020).

The PRA requires banks in the UK to maintain Pillar 2A requirements in excess of Pillar 1 requirements according to which banks need to meet the requirements of 56.25% of common equity tier 1 capital, 43.75% of additional tier 1 capital and 25% of tier 2 capital. It has also introduced guidelines for banks that are part of global systematically important institutions (G-SIIs) and other systemically important institutions (O-SIIs). According to these guidelines, if a bank is a part of G-SII then it needs to estimate a *G-SII* buffer of common equity tier 1 capital which is equivalent to total risk exposure multiplied by the *G-SII* buffer rate. Similarly, if a bank relates to *O-SII*, it must determine an *O-SII* buffer of common equity tier 1 capital which is equal to the *O-SII* buffer rate multiplied by its total risk exposure (BoE, 2021).

The PRA has defined capital buffer which is the sum of the capital conservation buffer, the countercyclical capital buffer, the *O-SII* buffer and the *G-SII* buffer. If a bank is unable to maintain the combined buffer, it must estimate its maximum distributable amount (MDA) and report the MDA to the Prudential Regulatory Authority within 5 working days of determining that the bank does not meet its combined buffer. Moreover, the bank should not undertake distribution with regards to the common equity tier 1 capital and should not develop an obligation to pay discretionary pension benefits or variable remuneration if it cannot meet its combined buffer. Besides this, the banks can develop a capital conservation plan which comprises of the maximum distributable amount (MDA), a timeframe and a plan in order to enhance its own funds to meet the combined buffer, estimates of expenditure, income and a forecast balance sheet and actions taken by the bank to increase its capital ratios. This conservation plan is required to be reported to the PRA within 5 working days of determining that the bank cannot meet its combined buffer.

In the light of the recent financial meltdown and pro-cyclical mechanisms that contributed to the economic meltdown, the PRA has introduced prudential rules which require banks to maintain countercyclical capital buffers and to ensure the maintenance of capital conservation in addition to their own funds requirements. These sufficient buffers may help banks to absorb financial shocks in stressed periods during periods of financial growth.

Furthermore, the PRA under CRD V requires banks in the UK to maintain a systemic risk buffer apart from a countercyclical capital buffer and a capital conservation buffer in order to reduce and prevent long term macro-prudential risks and non-cyclical systemic risks because

systemic risk causes disruption in the financial system which brings negative consequences for the real economy and the global financial system.

Where a bank does not meet the combined buffer requirement, the PRA encourages the bank to ensure that it maintains its own levels of funds in a timely manner. In order to conserve capital, the Bank of England (BoE) requires banks in the UK to put limitations on the discretionary distribution of profits such as payments of variable remuneration and dividend payments. The years preceding the recent economic downturn were characterised by the huge build-up in the exposure of banks with regards to their own funds which is called leverage. During the economic crisis, the shortage of liquidity and losses forced banks and investment firms to reduce their leverage over a short period of time. Therefore, according to the guidelines of the PRA; risk-based own funds requirements are vital to cover unanticipated losses and banks have been encouraged to be less leveraged. As a part of the internal capital adequacy assessment process (ICAAP); banks need to oversee the changes and levels in the leverage ratio and leverage risks which should be incorporated in their supervisory review process.

Under the new guidelines of CRD V; the PRA has required banks in the UK to develop and implement policies and strategies to identify and evaluate exposures to operational risk arising from outsourcing. CRD V has introduced the maximum distributable amount (MDA); according to which the PRA requires banks to restrict their percentage of distributable profits from their last distribution where the banks use their combined buffer. Rather, it allows banks to distribute year-end and interim profits that are not part of their CET 1 (common equity tier) resources regardless of the last timing of their distribution.

Moreover, the stress-testing framework of the BoE is offering a quantitative and forward-looking estimation of the capital adequacy of banks in the UK. The BoE requires banks and building societies in the UK to run annual stress tests to determine the capital requirements of banks. Three types of stress test are introduced by the Bank of England (BoE). The BoE runs annual stress test of the largest building societies and banks in the UK which informs the setting of capital buffers by its Prudential Regulatory Authority (PRA) and Financial Policy Committee (FPC). Banks that are not part of the first annual stress test are required by the BoE to run their own stress testing. A scenario is published every six months by the PRA which provides banks with guidance and policies to design their own scenarios. The last stress testing refers to an additional scenario (the biennial exploratory scenario) which is run every other year to probe the financial resilience of the banking industry to risks that are not neatly related to the financial cycle (BoE, 2021). Results of stress testing are reported at the

highest level of UK consolidation which is defined by the Capital Requirements Directive (CRD) IV and the Capital Requirements Regulation (CRR). Banks are required to evaluate the influence of the scenarios on insurance activities and model the impact on risk weightings, dividend streams and remarkable investments. Furthermore, banks are required to submit anticipated capital positions and starting point capital positions in the stress and baseline scenarios. Therefore, the capital adequacy of banks is determined with regards to leverage ratios and risk-weighted capital ratios. The PRA also expects banks to use IFRS 9 throughout the projection period and apply it in their starting position while estimating the capital adequacy with the help of stress testing and credit loss provisions for calculating regulatory capital.

The PRA has emphasised the need for using internal ratings-based approaches such as the probability of default (PD), loss given default (LGD) and exposure at default (EAD) to cope with the credit risk. For PD, the PRA requires banks to determine default risk over a fixed time period of one year. Under this approach, the rise of default risk in a downturn leads to a general trend of migration to lower grades. Higher capital requirements are expected when associated with the fixed estimate of the long-run default rate for the grade. On the contrary, the PRA classifies loss given default (LGD) into negative LGDs and low LGDs. For negative LGDs, the PRA requires banks to ensure that the LGD estimate should not be less than zero. However, for low LGDs, it expects banks not to use zero LGDs estimates except where banks are having cash collateral reinforcing the exposures (BoE, 2020).

Section 2: Conclusions from meetings with HSBC and LLOYDS

The interviewee from HSBC confirmed that RWAs are used by HSBC to estimate its capital requirements which enable the bank to decrease the risk of solvency. Various classes of HSBC assets carry different risk weightings which are assigned by various rating agencies and internal risk assessment models of the bank. In order to calculate RWAs of HSBC, its assets are categorised into various classes which are based on risks and probability of incurring losses. The overall loan portfolio of HSBC with other assets such as investments and loans are estimated in order to estimate its overall risk portfolio. In the case of higher amounts of risk-weighted assets (unsecured loans have a higher risk of default, therefore these assets have high-risk weightings than cash & Treasury bill), the bank maintains higher capital requirements and capital adequacy ratio. When the interviewee from LLOYDS was questioned about the risk-weighted assets, almost similar responses came out as the respondent from HSBC responded to the question. The interviewee from LLOYDS

responded that various factors are taken into account when estimating the risks attached to bank assets and then the bank determines its capital requirements and investigates its capital adequacy ratio. These factors include the significance of collateral used as security to approve a loan, whether the loan is of commercial nature and assessment of loan repayment history and consistency of the borrower. Moreover, the respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS confirmed that after assessing the risk portfolio and risk-weighted assets (RWAs) of banks by using internal assessment models and the Basel accords, both HSBC and LLOYDS hold buffer capital after taking into account the level of risks of their assets.

The respondent from HSBC explained that HSBC groups its assets within the context of specific risk categories in order to ensure that the required amount of capital is matched with the risk levels of assets by using credit ratings of various assets. This practice assists HSBC not to lose a significant amount of capital when the market value of a certain class of assets declines sharply. Risk managers in HSBC are also required to identify and assess the potential of assets to generate reasonable returns on assets which can help in meeting its regulatory capital requirements. When the interviewee was questioned about why banks are using the risk-weighted approach in order to estimate the bank capital. The interviewee responded that the risk-based approach is a widely used approach by my banks globally in determining their capital requirements and is recommended by Basel accord in order to determine the riskiness of the bank assets and to explore the capital adequacy of the bank. A risk-based approach to estimate the capital requirements assists banks in using their off-balance-sheet exposures to estimate their capital adequacy and banks can compare the performance of their subsidiaries and network branches within the context of their risk-weighted assets and their ability to maintain buffer capital in order to withstand financial stress.

The interviewee from HSBC made it clear that HSBC actively manages its capital and liquidity positions to meet regulatory requirements and support its business strategy at all times specifically under stress. It takes various measures to oversee its capital position such as capital ratios, stress testing, leverage ratio and internal capital assessment models. It regularly undertakes stress tests to assess the resilience of its capital adequacy and its balance sheet which provides valuable insights into how its business activities can be monitored appropriately during crises.

The interviewee further confirmed that apart from the stress testing framework, HSBC identifies other emerging risks as well which may affect its capital position and RWAs. Various scenarios are assessed against capital management by its risk specialists who take

remedial actions when necessary. It closely monitors future regulatory changes and assesses the influence of these changes on its capital requirements.

Similarly, the respondent from LLOYDS confirmed that stress testing is used as one of the key risk management tools by LLOYDS which is used for risk identification, risk mitigation, capital and strategic planning, and the findings of the stress test are evaluated against the risk appetite of LLOYDS in order to ensure that its risks are managed within the risk parameters set by the board. Moreover, it undertakes annual macroeconomic stress tests of its operational plan in order to ensure that LLOYDS has the potential to identify vulnerabilities in its operating plan which assists management to seek and utilise enough capital resources in the event of a financial meltdown.

In order to cope with new and emerging risks, LLOYDS maintains its own funds in good quality and quantity. It uses a capital adequacy ratio which enables it to absorb financial losses and it assists the management of the bank to estimate its capital requirements. By using the capital adequacy ratio, LLOYDS tends to ensure the protection of its depositors and thus promotes its financial resilience and stability to withstand financial shocks. RWAs of LLOYDS play a leading role in estimating its minimum capital requirements in order to maintain its solvency. The respondent is of the view that minimum capital requirements of LLOYDS are based on its risk assessment for various kinds of bank risk exposure because in the case of the riskier assets, the higher can be the RWAs and the higher amount of capital is required in order to withstand financial stress.

Moreover, LLOYDS maintains a capital management framework in order to ensure that it maintains its capital at a prudent level in line with its capital risk appetite. It regularly monitors its leverage and capital ratios in order to comply with regulatory capital requirements and risk appetite enabling it to utilise its capital resources efficiently. A rigorous regulatory and internal stress testing (discussed earlier) is undertaken by LLOYDS to estimate its capital adequacy and mitigating actions are taken by management in response to any financial turmoil.

In response to the question regarding what models are used by HSBC and LLOYDS to quantify required capital within the context of their RWAs. The respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS confirmed that banks under the guidelines of the advanced internal ratings-based approach are using their own quantitative models to quantify required capital after taking into account risk-weighted assets. These models include loss given default (LGD), exposure at default (EAD) and probability of default (PD). After taking into account the findings of these

quantitative models, banks estimate their required capital as a percentage of their risk-weighted assets

When the interviewee from HSBC was questioned about capital management, the respondent responded that various key performance indicators are used by HSBC to evaluate its progress against its strategic objectives such as financial and non-financial measures. HSBC prudently manages its capital to ensure that it holds enough capital in excess of capital buffer and total capital prescribed by the PRA. On the other hand, the interviewee from LLOYDS stated that LLOYDS is conducting an internal capital adequacy assessment process (ICAAP) on a regular basis which helps management to evaluate the capital requirements of LLOYDS and facilitates in designing and implementing appropriate risk management systems to cope with risks.

Moreover, the interviewees from HSBC and LLOYDS confirmed that both banks are reducing their risk-weighted assets over a period of time since the financial meltdown of 2007 because of information asymmetry between market participants and banks with regards to how risky RWAs are, results in uncertainty about the capital adequacy of banks. Moreover, the respondents unanimously agreed that a higher capital in response to higher RWAs could not stop the financial crisis from occurring. Therefore, respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS had a unanimous agreement that banks can enhance their capital adequacy ratio by reducing their RWAs and increasing regulatory capital. For these reasons, the importance of market discipline under Basel III has increased in recent years. Market discipline requires investors to oversee market conditions of banks and to include those assessments into the stock values. These disclosures enable investors to determine their stock returns after measuring the riskiness of the bank assets.

Section 3: Pillar 3 disclosures of HSBC and LLOYDS

According to the Pillar 3 disclosures of LLOYDS, it maintains its capital on an individual and consolidated basis which is commensurate with a prudent level of solvency to seek market confidence and financial resilience. In order to support the maintenance of capital, LLOYDS calibrates its capital risk appetite after considering its external regulatory requirements and internal view of the amount of capital to maintain. LLOYDS estimates its amount of capital resources and capital requirements through applying the regulatory framework such as the Capital Requirements Directive and Regulation (CRD IV), the revised Capital Requirements Directive (CRD V) implemented in December 2020 and the revised Capital Requirements Regulation (CRR II).

Regulators took various measures in 2020 in response to the Coronavirus pandemic such as

amendments to the IFRS 9 transitional arrangements for capital which LLOYDS is fully complying with. These arrangements have granted some stability with regards to capital requirements against the enhanced provisioning and volatility related to the IFRS 9 impact. LLOYDS under Pillar 1 maintains a minimum amount of capital which is equal to 8% of its risk-weighted assets (RWAs). Moreover, under Pillar 1 capital requirements, 4.5% of its RWAs needs to be covered by common equity tier 1 (CET1) capital and 6% of RWAs are required to be covered by tier 1 capital. In addition, Pillar 1 capital requirements of LLOYDS are also supported by additional capital requirements under the guidelines of Pillar 2A. Pillar 2A sets additional capital requirements with the issuance of an Individual Capital Requirement (ICR) which adjusts capital requirements for those risks that are not covered by Pillar 1. As of 31 December 2020, Pillar 2A capital requirement of LLOYDS are reduced to c.4% from c.4.9 % of its RWAs of which c.2.3 needs to be met with CET1 capital. LLOYDS is also complying with additional capital rules which need to be met with CET 1 capital. According to these capital rules, LLOYDS maintains a capital conservation buffer which is equal to 2.5% of RWAs and a countercyclical capital buffer of 0% of RWAs because the Bank of England has reduced the UK countercyclical buffer rate to nil in response to the Coronavirus pandemic. LLOYDS is a part of other systemically important institution (O-SII), therefore, it maintains an O-SII buffer (the systemic risk buffer) of 2% of RWAs. This O-SII buffer enables banks to maintain higher capital standards in order to withstand financial stress (LLOYDS, 2020).

Besides the risk-based capital framework, LLOYDS is also subject to the UK Leverage Ratio Framework of minimum capital requirements. According to this framework, the minimum leverage ratio requirement is 3.25%. This leverage ratio is supplemented by an additional leverage ratio buffer of 0.7% of the leverage exposure and a countercyclical leverage buffer of 0% of the leverage exposure. For LLOYDS, 75% of the 3.25% of the minimum leverage ratio requirement and 100% of regulatory leverage buffers is required by the Bank of England to be met by CET1 capital. However, the leverage ratio framework does not offer higher capital requirements for LLOYDS than the risk-based capital framework (LLOYDS, 2020).

In the context of the Covid-19 pandemic, LLOYDS has a profit after tax of £1.4 billion which is 54% lower than 2019 because of higher impairment charges of £4.2 billion in 2020 (£1.3 billion: 2019) and lower income. However, LLOYDS has a strong capital position with a CET1 ratio of 16.4% as compared to the CET1 ratio of 13.8% in 2019. This strong capital position of LLOYDS has enabled it to resume capital distributions of an ordinary dividend of 0.57 pence per share which is the maximum allowed under the temporary framework on 2020

distributions by the Prudential Regulatory Authority. This increase of CET 1 of 252 basis points in 2020 reflects the reductions in RWAs of LLOYDS, underlying profitability and the updated accounting treatment of intangible software assets within the context of IFRS 9 transitional arrangements. Its total risk-weighted assets (RWAs) are decreased by £0.7 billion in 2020 over the year and a significant reduction in RWAs occurred in the fourth quarter of 2020 which reflects reductions from model calibrations, credit migrations, disposal of a legacy equity investment in Visa Inc and the increased optimisation of the Commercial Banking portfolio. Moreover, as of 31 December 2020, total RWAs of LLOYDS are decreased to £170,862 million (1% reduction) from £171,940 million as of 31 December 2019 which indicates that it is reducing its RWAs over a period of time.

Capital build of LLOYDS is adversely affected in 2020 by impairment provisions. However, its capital position at year-end 2020 is strengthened because of the earlier reversal of the full-year ordinary dividend accrual of 2019 and enhanced IFRS 9 transitional relief, which offset the rise in impairment provisions.

Capital requirements of LLOYDS are reduced in 2020 because of lower Pillar 2A requirements and reduction in countercyclical capital buffer rate of the UK in response to the adverse compact of Covid-19. Therefore, LLOYDS has remarkable headroom to absorb future losses and to support businessmen and households as they recover from the pandemic. LLOYDS has experienced the highest impairment charge of £4247 million in 2020 (2019; £1291 million) because of increased expected credit loss allowances were taken predominantly in 2020 due to dire consequences of pandemic and restructuring cases in the Commercial Business Support Unit (BSU).

LLOYDS estimates its liquidity coverage ratio (LCR) on consolidated-all currencies and a significant currency basis. LLOYDS maintains extra liquid assets to meet Pillar 2 buffer capturing the liquidity risk defined by the PRA which is regularly monitored by a risk management team which enables them to be alert to the early warning indicators. A strong customer deposit base and strong relationships across customer segments reinforce the liquidity and funding position of LLOYDS (LLODS, 2020).

In 2015, the Financial Stability Board established a standard for the total loss-absorbing capacity (TLAC) of the global systematically important banks (G-SIBs) which assists banks to increase their financial resilience and enables them to maintain sufficient capital to absorb financial shocks and recapitalise under resolution. The MREL framework (minimum requirements for own funds and eligible liabilities) exhibits the implementation of the international TLAC standard. The Bank of England (BoE) in the UK has implemented the

MREL framework through the MREL policy statement (the MREL SoP) and the Banking Act. Under the MREL framework, the BoE requires banks to maintain enough own funds and eligible liabilities which assist banks to bear losses and to recapitalise them whilst in resolution. MREL can be met by a combination of certain unsecured liabilities and regulatory capital. LLOYDS is subject to MREL SoP of the BoE and thus holds minimum external MREL resources and operates a single point of entry (SPE) resolution strategy in order to comply with the MREL framework.

On the contrary, according to Pillar 3 disclosures of HSBC, the total capital requirements of HSBC consist of two key elements. Firstly, the total capital of HSBC is the sum of Pillar 1 and Pillar 2A capital requirements as set by the Prudential Regulatory Authority which is based on a point in time assessment and is 3% of RWAs, out of which 1.7% is fulfilled by common equity tier 1(CET1). Secondly, HSBC is complying with the regulatory transitional arrangements such as article 473a of the Capital Requirements Regulation for IFRS 9 financial instruments published by the European Union. Under these requirements, HSBC adds back to its capital base a proportion of the impact that IFRS 9 has on its loan loss allowances for five years (HSBC, 2020).

The impact of the IFRS 9 on loan loss allowances is estimated with the help of internal ratings-based (IRB) and standardised (STD) approaches. These findings support the findings of quantitative data analysis that banking capital not only depends on risk management but also on other factors as well. For example, in the case of HSBC, its capital requirement depends on Pillar 1, Pillar 2 capital requirements and the addition of a proportion of the impact of the IFRS 9 to its capital base as discussed above.

The common equity tier 1 ratio (CET 1) of HSBC is increased by 1.2% points in December 2020 from 14.7% (2019) to 15.9% (2020) because of \$3.4bn differences in foreign currency translation, \$2.8bn of capital generation net of dividends relating to equity instruments, a reduction of \$1.8bn in expected losses and \$3.4bn of cancellation of the fourth interim dividend for 2019. This rise in CET 1 ratio reflects the fluctuations in the capital treatment of software assets and the impact of the cancellation of an interim dividend of 2019. CET1 ratio determines the financial strength of the bank and requires it to maintain capital buffers in order to withstand financial stress (HSBC, 2020).

Covid-19 has brought unprecedented challenges for the global economy. In order to cope with these challenges; regulatory authorities, central banks and governments have responded to these challenges with different operational capacity and customer support measures along with changes to liquidity, risk-weighted assets (RWAs) and capital frameworks.

In June 2020, one of the most important measure “CRR Quick Fixes’ was enacted in UK and EU. This package implemented the useful components of key amendments to the CRR II (capital requirements regulation) together with other measures to reduce undue volatility in capital ratios arising from the Covid-19 pandemic. Moreover, transitional provisions on the regulatory capital treatment of IFRS 9 have been amended and both LLOYDS and HSBC are complying with IFRS 9. HSBC has brought changes to the capital treatment of its software assets.

In early 2020, following the suspension of dividend payments due to the pandemic, the PRA (Prudential Regulatory Authority) in the UK had revaluated the capital positions of the UK banks in the context of the financial uncertainty created by Covid-19. It has now allowed banks in the UK to resume external distributions which are subject to certain restrictions. Following the permission of distribution of dividend by the PRA, both HSBC and LLOYDS have resumed shareholder distribution of dividends during 2021. However, the PRA has required prudent dividends to be accrued but not to be paid out and the PRA aims to provide further updates until the 2021 half-year results are announced by large UK banks (HSBC, 2020).

The Second Bank Recovery and Resolution Directive (BRRD II) and the Fifth Capital Requirements Directive (CRD V) were enforced on the European banks on 28 December 2020. However, the PRA aimed to enact those elements of both models that came into force before the UK stopped being subject to EU law. These elements include the amendments to the structures of capital buffers that are applied to the regulation of the financial holding companies and ring-fenced banks.

In response to these models, the PRA published its CRD V rules in December 2020 such as changes to the estimation of the maximum distributable amount (MDA), the re-designation of ring-fenced bank’s buffers from Systemic Risk Buffers (SyRB) into Other Systemically Important Institutions (O-SII) buffers and the introduction of regulation for bank holding companies. Big banks in the UK are required to implement these changes in BRRD II and both HSBC and LLOYDS are complying with these measures in different phases as suggested by the PRA.

The leveraged ratio of HSBC is increased to 5.5% as of 31 December 2020 from 5.3% as of 31 December 2019 because of the rise in tier 1 capital which is offset by an increase in exposure primarily because of growth in financial investments and central bank deposits. This excessive leverage is managed under the global risk appetite framework of HSBC and is overseen by its leverage ratiometric in line with its risk appetite. However, on 31 December

2020, under the UK leverage framework of the PRA, the minimum leverage ratio (3.25%) of HSBC was supplemented by a countercyclical leverage ratio buffer of 0.1% and an additional leverage ratio buffer of 0.7%. These additional capital buffers are translated into capital values of \$1.8bn and \$17.9bn respectively.

MREL (minimum requirements for own funds and eligible liabilities) includes liabilities and own funds that are converted or written down into capital resources to recapitalise a bank in case of its collapse and to absorb losses. HSBC issues loss-absorbing instruments to potential investors in order to ensure that its loss-absorbing capacity supports the objectives of a resolution. It is expected that MREL issued by HSBC can be converted into equity by the Bank of England using its statutory powers. This process enables the subsidiaries of HSBC to be recapitalised when required and supports the objectives of a resolution and grant the provision of critical functions. Currently, the MREL requirement of HSBC is the highest of 6% of its consolidated leverage exposure, 16% of its consolidated RWAs and the sum of loss-absorbing requirements and capital requirements relating to group entities and sub-groups.

The ICAAP (internal capital adequacy assessment) is approved by its board which is responsible for a sound system of risk management and determines and reviews the risk appetite of HSBC. During the evaluation and supervisory review process of HSBC, the ICAAP is reviewed by a team of supervisors and the PRA as key elements of its decision making and the joint risk assessment process enables the regulators to determine the minimum capital requirements and individual capital requirement (ICR) for HSBC and define the PRA buffer when required. The PRA buffer is set after taking into account vulnerability in a stress scenario and is evaluated through the annual stress testing exercise of the PRA. Following the supervisory review and internal capital adequacy assessment of HSBC by the PRA, the PRA buffer and minimum capital requirements of HSBC are estimated by the PRA. Pillar 2 consists of Pillar 2A and Pillar 2B capital requirements. Risk categories covered by Pillar 2A depends on the specific requirements of HSBC and the nature of its business operations. Moreover, Pillar 2B of HSBC consists of the PRA capital buffer in order to ensure that HSBC maintains its capital above individual capital requirements (ICR) in adverse circumstances that tend to be outside the direct and normal control of HSBC. For example, during a period of plausible and severe downturn stress when capital surplus and assets values of HSBC are strained, the PRA capital buffer may enable HSBC to absorb financial shocks and to protect its capital position by maintaining adequate good quality capital (HSBC, 2020).

Pillar 3 requires all material risks to be disclosed to market participants in order to offer a

comprehensive risk profile of HSBC. Basel issued the Basel III reforms in December 2017 and completed the recalibration of the market risk, RWAs regime. These reforms will be implemented on 1 January 2022 and have a transition provision of five years for the output floor. This output floor at the end of the transitional period requires banks not to hold RWAs less than 73.5 % of RWAs created by the standardised approach. Therefore, HSBC estimates its RWAs to be within the range of 5% to 10% by 1 January 2022 in response to the regulatory changes. The approach of HSBC to its capital adequacy is driven by organisational and strategic needs after taking into account the economic, commercial and regulatory landscape. HSBC maintains a robust capital base to manage risks inherent in its business operations (HSBC, 2020).

Minimum capital requirements of HSBC for market risk, credit risk, operational risk, counterparty credit risk and securitisation are reported in terms of RWAs and are covered by Pillar 1. The following sections present various permissible approaches and models that are used by HSBC and LLOYDS with regards to the above-mentioned risks in terms of their RWAs.

The Basel accord has recommended three models to estimate the minimum capital requirements for Pillar 1 credit risk. The first approach; the standardised approach requires a bank to employ external credit ratings to explore risk weightings applied to pertinent counterparties. The next approach, the foundation IRB (internal ratings-based approach) requires banks to use the probability of default (PD) of a counter-party to estimate their capital needs for credit risk.

Probably of default determines the likelihood of a default on a specific period of time and the probability that a borrower cannot meet its financial obligations. Last approach, the advanced IRB model permits banks to utilise their internal assessment when exploring the probability of default (PD) and quantifying exposure at default (EAD) and loss given default (LGD).

EAD represents a total amount of loss when a debtor defaults on a loan. EAD is estimated by the bank for each loan with the help of the internal ratings-based (IRB) model to determine overall default risk. LGD is the value of money a bank loses when a borrower defaults and cannot pay back its debt obligations.

HSBC is using the advanced internal ratings-based approach (AIRB) approach to cope with credit risk. HSBC maintains the highest amounts of RWAs (\$691.9bn) as of 31 December 2020 with regards to credit risk because credit risk is the most important risk currently faced by HSBC because of the inability of counterparties to meet their debt obligations. RWAs of HSBC are decreased by \$14.1bn as of 31 December 2020. RWAs with regards to credit risk

are decreased by \$20bn in 2020 including a rise of \$13.6bn because of differences in foreign currency translation. These reductions in RWAs are driven by active portfolio management; assets size reductions of a significant amount, changes in policies and models used by HSBC to cope with credit risk. On the contrary, the standardised approach and the advanced internal ratings-based approach (AIRB) are used by LLOYDS to measure credit risk. RWAs with regards to the credit risk of LLOYDS decreased by £0.3bn in the year ended 2020 which show optimisation activity in commercial banking which are drawdowns by corporate customers (LLOYDS, 2020).

Capital requirements for market risk are estimated by the internal models approach (IMA) and standard rules on managing market risk. The IMA model uses the value at risk (VaR) approach to cope with market risk and estimates capital requirements accordingly. Value at risk is about the estimation of the risk of loss of investments in given market conditions. VaR assists banks and investors to gauge various assets required to cover anticipated losses. HSBC estimates its capital adequacy for market risk by using its internal market risk models such as VaR and stressed VaR. RWAs concerning market risk decreased by \$2.8bn in 2020 because of reductions in portfolio exposures of sovereign and flow credit.

However, in the case of LLOYDS, trading positions of LLOYDS are assigned capital requirements by employing the internal models approach and the standardised approach. Similar to HSBC, the standardised approach is also used by LLOYDS to measure operational risk. However, the net stable funding ratio (NSFR) and liquidity coverage ratio (LCR) are also used by LLOYDS to determine its liquidity and capital adequacy positions. NSF ratio requires banks to hold stable funding resources to cover their long terms assets and to meet their liquidity problems. Similarly, the LCR determines the ability of banks to cover their short term financial obligations by requiring them to hold high-quality liquid assets. RWAs relating to market risk are the same (£0.2bn) in the year 2020 & 2019 because of the rise in market risk and increase in back-testing overshoot relating to Covid-19 (LLOYDS, 2020).

Four models have been proposed by the Basel framework for counterparty credit risk. These approaches include mark to market, internal model method (IMM), original exposure and standardised approach. HSBC is using the internal model method and the mark to market model to cope with counterparty credit risk. The aim of using both approaches is to enhance the proportion of positions on the internal model method. RWAs concerning counterparty credit risk increased by \$1.2bn because of mark to market movements which are offset by reductions under management activities. For LLOYDS, counterparty credit risk and derivatives are estimated by using the mark to market model and supervisory slotting

approach. Its RWAs increased by £0.4bn as of 31 December 2020 because of fluctuations in assets size and their market rates. Common equity tier1 (CET1) ratio of LLOYDS increased to 15.5% in 2020 from 14.3% as of 31 December 2019 which reflects accruals of ordinary dividends, profits with the effect of impairment charge partially offset by an increase in IFRS 9 transitional relief for capital.

Two approaches have been recommended by the Basel framework in order to determine capital requirements for securitisation in non-trading books. These approaches include the internal ratings-based approach (IRB) and the standardised approach which further incorporates other models such as the supervisory formula method (SFM), the internal assessment approach (IAA) and the ratings based method (RBM). However, in trading books, securitisation is covered within the market risk management framework with the help of the Capital Requirements Directive (CRD IV) rules on capital adequacy.

For a large number of securitisation within the non-trading book, HSBC uses the interval ratings-based approach and the standardised approach. Furthermore, HSBC uses CRD IV rules for securitisation in the trading book. RWAs concerning securitisation are increased by \$0.1bn as a result of new transactions relating to securitisation and novel deals on the current security facilities. On the contrary, securitisation positions of LLOYDS are risk-weighted with the help of the ratings based-approach (RBA) and the standardised approach.

In addition, the leverage ratio of LLOYDS increased to 5.5% in 2020 from 5.1% which reflects a rise in fully loaded tier 1 capital position offset by the increase in the leverage exposure estimate indicating fluctuations in off-balance sheet items and securities financing transactions. Like HSBC, LLOYDS has RWAs that have also been decreased by £1bn in 2020 which shows an extensive optimisation activity in its banking operations and introduction of new internal risk assessment models. In addition, LLOYDS has a strong liquidity position in 2020 with a liquidity coverage ratio (LCR) of 126%. Similarly, LLOYDS holds the highest amount of RWAs (£120.9bn) with regards to credit risk which also confirms the findings of thematic analysis, HSBC (2019) and LLOYDS (2019). These findings show that credit risk is the most significant risk currently faced by HSBC and LLOYDS as both banks hold the highest amount of RWAs. For LLOYDS as of 31 December 2020, its RWAs reduced by £1bn, counterparty credit risk RWAs increased by £.4bn, operational risk RWAs decreased by £1.1bn and market risk RWAs have remained the same (£.2bn) in 2020 & 2019.

The above discussion indicates that both banks are decreasing their RWAs to a large extent over a period of time as a percentage of total assets but total assets for both banks have

increased from 2019 to 2020. This reduction in RWAs of both banks suggests that both banks are aggressive in reducing higher risk exposures. But these reductions in RWAs are achieved by adjustment to their internal risk assessment models. Changes in exposure at default (EAD) is analysed by banks in order to determine the actual level of the balance sheet of banks as recommended by the Basel framework.

It is interesting to draw a conclusion from the findings of interviews with HSBC and LLOYDS, Pillar 3 disclosures and the guidelines of the BoE on the Prudential Regulation with regards to determining the effect of risk management on the capital adequacy of London banks. From the above discussion, it is evident that banks are reducing their RWAs after the recent financial crisis. The main reason for reducing the RWAs is that during the financial meltdown of 2007-08, the performance of the higher RWAs had been worse. Generally, RWAs do not anticipate market measures of risks banks face. The recent financial meltdown emphasised the need for banking institutions to be highly liquid, more transparent, less leveraged and not to take excessive risks. Moreover, the private and public sectors urge banks to build high-quality capital buffers while reducing the riskiness of their risk portfolios at the same time.

As RWAs did not play a significant role in stopping the recent financial crisis and maintaining the higher riskier assets have been proved to be ineffective and costly in terms of the most cost involved, eroding of profits and dividends. Therefore, banks can reduce RWAs by improving their internal risk assessment and capital estimation models such as the probability of default (PD), loss given default (LGD) and exposure at default (EAD). Banks can maintain high-quality assets by using net stable funding ratio (NSFR) and liquidity coverage ratio (LCR) to improve their liquidity positions and finance their cash outflows. Banks need to be less leveraged, transparent and not take excessive risks. Interviews, the Prudential Regulation of the BoE and Pillar 3 disclosures also indicate that banks can also use Internal Capital Adequacy Assessment Process (ICAAP) to estimate their capital adequacy requirements and IFRS 9 can be used by banks to estimate their credit loss provisions for calculating regulatory capital.

From the above discussion, it can be concluded that the capital adequacy of banks not only depends on the soundness of risk management systems but also on other factors such as risk profile, regulatory requirements, risk preferences of risk managers, shareholders, internal capital assessments and impact of IFRS 9 on loan loss allowances of banks after taking into account pillar 3 disclosures of banks.

5.5 Evaluation of the application of Basel III in London banks and the determination of its impact

The findings of descriptive statistics, thematic analysis and the literature review have been compared and corroborated to substantiate the results of data analysis that has facilitated this research to evaluate the application of Basel III in London banks and to determine its impact on the UK banking sector.

The question concerning the effectiveness of increased capital in reducing risks within the context of Basel III has the highest mean of 4.77 and a standard deviation of .767 (section 4.8, table 4.67). The highest mean and low standard deviation which is closer to 1 means that the data points are close to the mean of 4.77 which demonstrate that most of the respondents highly agreed or agreed that increased capital may help banks in absorbing financial shocks. Whereas, the question relating to the review of Basel II in the light of its failure to the stop recent financial crisis has the lowest mean of 3.99 and standard deviation .425. Furthermore, the results in table 4.67 indicate that the overall average mean value of all four questions is 4.4 which is greater than midpoint value on the Likert scale (3) which depicts that Basel III is a good standard with the introduction of various regulatory measure for example stress testing, capital ratio and net stable funding ratio which can help banks in managing the various type of risk they face thereby enabling them to enhance their financial resilience.

These findings are also endorsed by interview data analysis (thematic analysis, tables 4.21 to 4.31) which explains that various regulatory measures introduced by Basel III can help banks in absorbing financial shock in case of financial stress. A large number of interviewees believe that Basel III can play a vital role in stopping a financial crisis because the soundness of Basel III is mutually associated with the stringent economic and regulatory reinforcements. Stringent regulations, enhanced emphasis on maintaining buffer capital and more significantly introduction of equity and tier1 capital may help banks in maintaining buffer capital with regards to their risk weighted assets in order to absorb financial shocks.

Basel III is an amazing framework that helps banks in dealing with their liquidity problems and operational challenges. One of the key features of Basel III is the introduction of macro-prudential elements into the capital framework. It also promotes capital preservation requirements to stop the inappropriate distribution of capital. Interviewee 19 from LLOYDS asserted that Basel III has issued measures that support the build-up of capital buffers in good times that can be used in times of financial stress. It promotes capital preservation requirements in order to stop the inappropriate distribution of capital.

Empirical literature (section 2.13) endorses the above findings highlighting that Base III is optimising the financial resilience of the banking industry by underpinning the regulatory capital framework that is based on three pillars of Basel II. These reforms enhance the quantity and quality of the capital base and enhance risk coverage of banks underpinned by a leverage ratio serving as a backstop to risk-based measures. Enhancing the coverage risk ratio of banks is one of the key measures introduced under Basel III. One of the key reasons of the financial downturn of 2007-08 was the failure to identify on and off-balance sheet risks and derivative related exposures was a significant factor in the failure of banks (BCBS, 2017; Balthazar, 2006; Archer and Karim, 2007).

These findings also confirm the empirical findings of Tanupa et al (2016), Guo and Cummings (2018), King and Tarbert (2011) and Moody's (2018) that Basel III is designed in a way to ensure stability and safety of banking industry at international level. As post-crisis reforms, Basel III is assisting banks in reducing the variability of risk-weighted assets, introducing capital ratios, net stable funding ratios and focusing on its cyber risk measures to enable banks to address various emerging risks. It has introduced a wide range of regulatory measures aiming at supporting supervision and introducing buffer capital requirements for banks. These measures include guidance and principles on risk management, corporate governance, the prudential treatment of assets, and an improved set of core principles for effective banking supervision. This is in contrast to the empirical literature (Perez, 2014) indicating that under Basel III, the enhanced capital requirements may reduce competition among existing players by increasing barriers to entry into the banking sector but higher capital requirements are effective for big banks which in turn can enhance their effectiveness. Moreover, Basel III has not addressed yet risk weighted method of determining the capital requirements of banks that was the main reason behind the subprime crisis. Risk weighting of assets depends on the credit rating agencies and Basel III still depends on bond rating agencies because weights assigned to assets of banks depend on the rating awarded by rating agencies such as Moody's. Evidence from the subprime crisis indicates that rating agencies can be wrong in determining risk weighting of assets.

By contrast, some interviewees from HSBC and LLOYDS contradict above findings and argue that though the Basel III is more demanding and effective for HSBC and LLOYDS than Basel I & II in terms of dealing with systemic risk but it is not the last accord of all Basel accords. They argued that Basel III could not be adopted blindly as it might not cover all risks that banks face currently.

These findings also contradict Ingves (2018) arguing that Basel III has addressed various weaknesses in the pre-crisis regulatory framework and provided a basis for a financially sound banking system that facilitates in reducing the effect of future banking crises and the build-up of systemic vulnerabilities. However, these reforms are not enough and full details of its standards have not come out as well and its implementation period starts from 2022. For that reasons, the effectiveness of Basel III may be eroded and banks may be reluctant to follow its reforms because Basel standards are just global minimum standards having no supranational authority, it cannot impose fines in case of non-compliance with its standards because its decisions carry no legal force.

Considering the above arguments the researcher believes that financial crises are inevitable and Basel standards cannot stop the future financial meltdown. However, Basel III can reduce the likelihood and impact of any financial crises ahead by remaining alert for emerging risks. Moreover, Basel III has the potential to enhance the financial resilience of the banks by requiring them to use stress testing and liquidity ratio. These measures may assist banks in determining their capital requirements and thus reduce systemic risk.

5.6 Recommendation of a sound risk management framework for the banking industry

This is the last objective of this work that the current research has attempted to achieve with various approaches. Literature review and thematic analysis have been used to explore the opinions and feedbacks of banking professionals in order to get a feel of what kind of risk management framework is appropriate for the UK banking industry to enhance their financial resilience.

Findings of the thematic analysis reported in tables 4.36 to 4.40 indicate that there is no specific answer to this question of a recommendation of an effective risk management framework for the banking industry. A large number of respondents gave varied opinions on proposing comprehensive risk management that they perceived to be used for banks in order to cope with the risks. Majority of respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS emphasised the need for more advanced and sophisticated risk management system to cope with risks and challenges they might counter. One interviewee from HSBC suggested that a detailed study of Basel Accords, guidance on banking risk management introduced by European Central Bank (ECB), Bank of England and other central banks and regulators across various countries may help in developing a comprehensive framework on risk management. Risk management framework and risk management policies can be redefined and improved in the light of new developments in risk management undertaken by the banking industry. A comprehensive

framework reflecting key factors of risk management should be developed in an attempt to deal with challenges in years to come.

Literature review (section 2.12) also endorses above findings highlighting that a stringent risk management framework can be developed on the basis of risk management guidelines issued by the Bank of England, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the International Monetary Fund, COSO framework (Enterprise risk management) and Sarbanes Oxley Act (Borghesi and Gaudenzi, 2012; IMF, 2018; Financial Stability Board, 2013; Taleb, 2004).

Above discussion summarises that no unanimous agreement among respondents has been found on what kind of risk management framework should be used for the banking industry in order to make it more resilient. However, a comprehensive risk management framework can be developed for the UK banking sector based on the recommendations of the above-discussed frameworks adopted in various jurisdictions.

However, almost all of interviewees gave the same responses with regards to the impediments in implementing the risk management framework. They argued that more costs could be involved because of stringent regulation and enhanced capital requirements by regulators and supervisory institutions. The adaptability of employees to new changes is one of the key impediments to be overcome. Inadequate supervision, training, inefficient information and management systems may undermine the effectiveness of risk management function in the banks.

5.7 Summary and Conclusion

This chapter has shed light on the analysis and discussion of the findings of data analysis that have been undertaken in the previous chapter (chapter four) with a specific focus on the research objectives of this research. Findings of thematic analysis, descriptive analysis, statistical analysis and literature review have been compared and corroborated to substantiate the findings of analysis that have assisted the current research to achieve the overall aim of the study.

As regards the findings of above-detailed discussion, it can be concluded that main risks faced by HSBC and LLOYDS are capital risk, interest rate risk, credit risk, market risk, operational risk, liquidity risk, risk of a cyber attack, underwriting risk, model risk, and geopolitical risk. It is noticeable that both banks almost face the same types of risks as they are operating in the same country. However, credit risk has been found the key risk faced by HSBC and LLOYDS in London. It is obvious from the above discussion that banks in

London are following a stringent risk management system and their risk management practices are sound enough to cope with financial challenges. Furthermore, statistical and descriptive analyses indicate that key aspects of risk management have a significant influence on the risk management adopted by banks. If any one of those aspects is not sound enough, banks may lead to poor risk management system in place leading them to be exposed to more risk exposures.

Certain assumptions of institutional theory used for this study have been tested through a detailed discussion of results. The findings of this chapter endorse the uniformity assumption of the institutional theory under which banks in the UK specifically HSBC and LLOYDS need to adopt different management practices to meet the regulatory requirements.

Having undertaken statistical analysis including Pearson correlation and regression, it has been envisaged that capital adequacy of banks not only depends on risk management but also on other factors such as risk profile of banks, risk preferences of shareholders, bondholders and risk managers, and capital regulatory requirements.

Different banks use different risk management strategies depending on their structure, size and nature of operations. Basel III is commonly used by HSBC and LLOYDS in order to absorb financial shocks. Findings of data analysis also indicate that Basel III is a fact and it can play a vital role in stopping a financial crisis because the soundness of Basel III is mutually associated with stringent economic and regulatory reinforcements.

Chapter Six: Conclusion

6.1 Introduction

The earlier chapters have discussed data collection, data analysis and put a spot light on the discussion of results in order to answer the research questions of the current research. This chapter summarises the findings of all previous chapters and sheds light on the overall conclusion reached with respect to the aim and objectives of the study. To reiterate, the current study has been undertaken to evaluate the effectiveness of current practices of risk management followed in London banks with a specific focus on LLOYDS and HSBC in order to develop an effective risk management framework to enhance the financial resilience of the banking sector. In order to achieve the aim and objectives of this work; opinions and feedbacks were sought from managers and risk managers through semi-structured interviews, survey questionnaires and secondary data collection and analysis. The results of the questionnaire, interviews and secondary data have been corroborated with literature review and theoretical framework in order to substantiate the results.

6.2 Risk Management in Banks

Over the last ten years, risk management in the banking industry has changed significantly. Regulatory measures and regulations that emerged in the wake of the financial meltdown of 2007-08 and the fines levied on banks triggered a wave of change in the risk function of banks. These regulatory measures include liquidity, enhanced and more demanding capital, improved standards for risk reporting, leverage and funding requirements (Mckinsey, 2015). In the wake of dynamism and complexities of the business environment; risk management in banks has drawn attention from regulatory bodies and management of banking institutions (Maghyereh and Awartani, 2014; Bunea, Lazarica and Petre, 2009). Significant developments have taken place in risk management at the global level in recent years in an attempt to improve risk management practices (Chortareas, Giradone and Ventouri, 2011; Al-Tamimi, H., 2008).

Therefore, the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision developed globally recognised Basel standards requiring banks to comply with those standards in order to cope with various kinds of risks. For this purpose, central banks and regulatory bodies in many countries have taken concrete steps towards implementing Basel accords to reinforce their respective risk management frameworks (Masood and Fry, 2012).

Bank of England (BoE) in the UK has enforced stringent risk management guidelines on banks and has required banking institutions to comply with the fundamental principles of risk

management regardless of their size and nature of operations. Thus, all banks have taken several steps to design, implement and review robust risk management frameworks to encounter different risks. Besides the Bank of England's guidelines on risk management, banks in the UK also using Basel accords depending on their risk portfolios.

Thorough research work has been undertaken in the current research to assess the effectiveness of the current practices of risk management followed in London banks within the context of LLOYDS and HSBC. This study has attempted to address two significant aspects of risk management in London banks. Firstly, current risk management practices of banks have been explored in this research. Secondly, the current work has determined the impact of key aspects of risk management on risk management practices followed by banks. Keeping in view the overall aim of the current study, this research has evaluated the effectiveness of current risk management practices adopted by HSBC and LLOYDS; this research has addressed the following objectives:

1. To determine the key risks faced by HSBC and LLOYDS.
2. To determine the current practices of risk management followed in London banks (LLOYDS and HSBC) and to explore the relationship between various aspects of risk management in order to manage risks, maximise opportunities and uphold economic stability
3. To investigate if there is any relationship between risk management and the amount of capital banks hold?
4. To evaluate the application of Basel III in London banks and to determine the impact of Basel III in managing risks.
5. To recommend a risk management framework in order to enhance the financial resilience of the banking sector.

This study has used mixed methods research design (see section 3.11) to achieve these objectives that have assisted this research to corroborate the findings of qualitative data analysis with quantitative data analysis which enabled the researcher to substantiate the findings. Mainly, quantitative research methods have been adopted in this study. However, a part of this study has also been undertaken with the help of qualitative research methodology in order to meet the research objectives accordingly. Next section puts the spotlight on various procedures and techniques for collecting and analysing data utilised in current research.

6.3 Overview of the Research

The current research has explored the risk management practices of HSBC and LLOYDS and determined the effect of various aspects of risk management on risk management practices. Both primary and secondary data has been collected to achieve the objectives of the research. This work comprises of a total of six chapters. In the first chapter, the background of the study with research questions, the aim and objectives of the research has been discussed. Research gap along with conceptual framework has also been discussed in detail. Chapter two sheds light on the literature review on risk management. In chapter three, research methodology has been discussed in detail along with the justification for research methodologies to be employed to meet the research objectives of the study.

Moreover, qualitative research undertaken is in the form of semi-structured interviews with bank managers and risk managers in banks. On the contrary, quantitative research is based on survey questionnaires distributed to banking professionals in London and secondary quantitative data (risk-weighted assets and amount of the capital banks hold) has been collected from annual reports of banks for period 2010-2019. Convenience sampling has been used after bearing into mind the aim and objectives of the research. Moreover, both semi-structured interviews and survey questionnaires are developed on the same perspective and are anticipated to achieve the same objectives of the study.

In chapter four, bearing into mind the literature review, research questions, aim and objectives of the research, this chapter has been divided into five sections. Part 1 explains the findings and results of interview data analysis. Part 2 sheds lights on the findings of questionnaire data that has been gathered through questionnaires sent to bank managers and risk managers in London. Part 3 sheds light on the findings of one research question undertaken to achieve the objective of the current study: To evaluate the application of Basel III in London banks and to determine the impact of Basel III in managing risks. Part 4 discusses the hypothesis development to determine the relationship between various aspects of risk management & risk management practices followed by HSBC and LLOYDS. In part 5, secondary quantitative data analysis has been discussed to explore the association between capital adequacy of banks and risk weighted assets (RWAs). Chapter 5 is the analysis and discussion chapter in which the findings of thematic analysis; descriptive and statistical analysis have been compared and corroborated with the literature review to substantiate the findings in order to achieve the aim of this research. Chapter six is the concluding chapter that aims to summarise the findings of all chapters.

6.4 Reflection of the Research Findings

As discussed in chapter one (section 1.2), risk management is a cornerstone of the modern banking industry. In the current volatile business environment, the banking industry is facing various interrelated risks including operational risk, market risk, liquidity risk, credit risk, interest rate risk, concentration risk, operational risk and foreign exchange risk. These risks are of paramount significance for banks as these risks may threaten their survival and performance and subsequently undermine consumer's confidence in the banking system. Furthermore, the recent financial downturn of 2007 and the collapse of big firms have emphasized the need for establishing a sound and resilient system of risk management in banks in order to absorb financial shocks.

It is worth pointing out here that this research fills the research gap (section 1.4) in research about risk management in HSBC and LLOYDS by investigating the opinions and perceptions of banking professional and statistical analysis towards the characteristics of risk management in banks from empirical evidence.

Thus, the current research has been conducted to address the research gap (see section 1.4) with regards to exploring the risk management practices followed in the London banks within the context of HSBC and LLOYDS and to evaluate their effectiveness.

For this purpose, a full dedicated study has been undertaken on HSBC and LLOYDS across London that offers a holistic overview of the risk management practices that have been explored and analysed by thematic, descriptive and statistical analyses. The results of the current research also reveal some key aspects of risk management that need to be improved for London banks after testing the hypothesis H01 with the help of multiple regression analysis.

Based on the findings in the current research, it is evident that capital risk, interest rate risk, credit risk, market risk, operational risk, liquidity risk, risk of a cyber attack, underwriting risk, model risk, and geopolitical risk are the most significant kinds of risks faced by HSBC and LLOYDS. The findings from both questionnaire and interview data analysis confirm that credit risks are the most important risks to both banks in London in the current business environment. Therefore, it can be concluded that all risks discussed in findings and analysis chapters are equally important. However, credit risk has been found the principal risk faced by banks in London.

Based on the findings reported in chapter five, section 5.3, a broad conclusion can be drawn that risk understanding, risk identification, risk assessment and analysis, risk monitoring and

controlling, managing operational risk, managing credit risk, managing market risk and managing operational risk are the key aspects of risk management followed by HSBC and LLOYDS. Descriptive analysis and thematic analysis show that these aspects of risk management have a statistically significant influence on risk management practices followed by London banks. London banks need to give more attention to improving these risk management variables in order to make their risk management systems more robust and resilient.

These findings also reinforce the homogeneity assumption of the institutional theory according to which regulatory pressures are exerted on banks in the form of obligations and direction (Hudin and Hamid, 2014; Collier and Woods, 2011). Based on the findings of this research, it can be summarised that different banks use different risk management strategies depending on their structure, size and nature of operations. Basel III is commonly used by HSBC and LLOYDS in order to absorb financial shocks.

The results of Pearson correlation and multiple regression analysis have shown that respondents from HSBC and LLOYDS have varying opinions on the suitability of Basel accords to HSBC and LLOYDS. According to these findings, not all provisions of Basel II and Basel III are significant to banks. Their applicability depends on the risk exposure of the bank and the likelihood of risks materialised. Basel III can play a remarkable role in stopping a financial crisis because the soundness of Basel III is mutually associated with stringent economic and regulatory reinforcements. Stringent regulations, enhanced emphasis on maintaining buffer capital and more significantly introduction of equity and tier1 capital may help banks in maintaining buffer capital with regards to their risk-weighted assets in order to absorb financial shocks.

Statistical and descriptive results also indicate that there is a somewhat positive relationship between capital adequacy of banks and risk management. However, capital adequacy of banks not only depends on risk management but also risk preferences of risk managers, bondholder, and shareholders, risk portfolio of banks and capital adequacy requirements of regulators play a leading role in exploring the capital needs of banks. Banks must maintain their capital levels after taking into their risk weighted assets and risk portfolios. There has been no unanimous agreement on the question of what kind of risk management framework should be established to deal with emerging risks and deal with any future crisis ahead. In addition, the findings assert that a more advanced and sophisticated risk management system is imperative for the UK Banking sector in this current business environment. According to these findings, various globally accepted risk management frameworks used in various

countries such as COSO framework, Sarbanes Oxley Act, and the UK good governance code can assist in developing a more a comprehensive and sophisticated risk management system.

6.5 Contribution of Research

The current study has made a contribution to the existing literature on risk management within the context of the London banks by exploring the current practices of risk management followed by banks and evaluating their effectiveness. This study helps in investigating whether the banks are following risk management guidelines recommended by the Bank of England and the Bank for International Settlements (BIS). The current research has facilitated in determining the relationship between various aspects of risk management and risk management practices which provides a holistic overview of risk management in London banks. It contributes to the knowledge by exploring what is the role of risk management in deciding the capital adequacy of banks and what is their relationship. Furthermore, the homogeneity assumption of institutional theory (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983) has been underpinned by the current research by focusing on the risk management practices in London banks with a particular focus on big banks such as HSBC and LLOYDS which makes a remarkable contribution to the current literature.

6.6 Research Limitations

Though, the current study has resulted in significant findings to add valuable contributions to the existing literature on risk management in the London banks by effectively testing the hypotheses, answering the research questions and thus achieving the aim and objectives of the current research. However, no research study can be completed without highlighting its limitations.

Like other research studies, during the course of execution of this research, the current study has also come across challenges and restrictions. The population of the current research is limited to only two banks in London such as LLOYDS and HSBC. Two large banks such as HSBC and LLOYDS have been chosen for this study. Bearing into mind time constraints, resources and accessibility to research participants for data collection; this research aims to assess the effectiveness of risk management practices in HSBC and LLOYDS across London instead of the whole UK. Another reason for undertaking research only on London banks with a specific focus on HSBC and LLOYDS is the scope and nature of the research study. It is impracticable and financially not possible to have access to all banks across the whole UK and time constraints to finish research study in prescribed time frame do not allow the researcher to choose banks across the whole UK.

For these reasons, the results of this research may not be generalized on these two types of banks in London. However, the mixed methodology used in this study and comparing and corroborating the findings of descriptive analysis, statistical analysis, thematic analysis with literature review and research questions have overcome this limitation and thus assisted this study to achieve the aim and objectives of the research.

The questionnaire in this research is limited to certain aspects of risk management as discussed in section 5.3.1 and this study has determined the relationship between these aspects and risk management in banks. More improved results can also be found by covering other aspects of risk management such as audit committee, board composition and size, management structure and quality in banks.

Another limitation of this research is about the secondary data analysis that is related to investigating the relationship between capital adequacy of banks and risk management. Statistical and descriptive analyses have been undertaken to determine the relationship as opposed to other capital adequacy measurement models which have also been employed in the current studies such as simulation with the help of @R (Risk software).

Inadequate time to complete this research and insufficient resources to have access to research participants for data collection, particularly from the UK banks, are other challenges that have been faced during the execution of this research.

6.7 Recommendations for Future Research

As highlighted in the research limitations (section 6.6) that various fields of risk management have been partly discussed in the current research that recommends some extensions for future study. Currently, this research has investigated risk management practices followed by two banks within the context of London only. Consequently, there is a prospect for future study to be extended to investigate risk management in big commercial banks across the whole UK to get a holistic synopsis of risk management in the UK banking sector. It may also facilitate future research to further evaluate the financial resilience of the UK banking industry and thus to appraise its capability to withstand future crisis ahead.

Furthermore, apart from exploring key aspects of risk management as discussed earlier future research can focus on determining other aspects of risk management such as audit committee, board composition and size, management structure and quality to get a comprehensive picture of risk management in the banks and to improve risk management in the UK banks.

The current research has employed statistical analysis and descriptive analysis to explore the association between capital adequacy of banks and risk management as opposed to other

capital adequacy estimation models which have also been utilised in the current studies such as simulation with the help of @R (Risk software). Therefore, future research can use simulation techniques with the help of @R (Risk software) to test the capital requirements of banks against the riskiness of their assets and risk portfolios.

6.8 Final Conclusion

This research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the current practices of risk management followed in London banks with a particular focus on LLOYDS and HSBC and to recommend a risk management framework for the UK banking industry to enhance its financial resilience. These results demonstrate that a sound risk management framework depends on various key factors. On the basis of the results, risk understanding, risk identification, risk assessment and analysis, risk monitoring and controlling, managing operational risk, managing credit risk, managing market risk and managing operational risk have been found the key aspects of risk management in HSBC and LLOYDS. Therefore, the effectiveness of a risk management system in banks depends on the usefulness and adequate understanding of all these aspects among all employees of banks. Moreover, banks need to pay attention towards developing a stringent risk management processes in order to identify, evaluate, respond and control various risks such as market risk, liquidity risk, capital risk and credit risk etc. In addition, banks should hold buffer capital after taking into account their risk-weighted assets and risk profiles. By considering the guidelines of the Bank of England on risk management, development of a sound system of risk management in banks is not only an effective practice to fulfil regulatory requirements but also a useful exercise to maximise the resilience of banking sector in the UK. Consequently, the results of the current study clearly endorse the assertion that an effective risk management system in banks assists in boosting the performance of banks. Furthermore, a more advanced and sophisticated risk management system can be developed after taking into account various globally used risk management frameworks in different countries and can be tailored to the circumstances of the UK banking sector.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: List of selected banks and their branches in London for this study

Serial No	HSBC	LLOYDS
	Locations	
1.	23 Ripple Road, Barking Essex, IG11 7NW	11 Station Parade, Barking IG11 8ED
2.	140 High Street, Barnet, Hertfordshire, EN5 5XW	218 Heathway, Dagenham RM10 8QS
3.	237 Broadway, Bexleyheath DA6 7EL	841 High Rd, North Finchley, London N12 8PX
4.	69 Park Royal Rd, Park Royal, London NW10 7JR	130 Broadway, Bexleyheath DA6 7DP
5.	184 High St, Bromley BR1 1HE	106 Kilburn High Rd, North Maida Vale, London NW6 4HY
6.	176 Camden High St, Camden Town, London NW1 8QL	6-8 Market Square, Bromley BR1 1NA
7.	9 Wellesley Rd, Croydon CR9 2AA	140 Camden High St, Camden Town, London NW1 0NG
8.	46 The Broadway, Ealing, London W5 5JR	137 N End, Croydon CR0 1TN
9.	1 The Town, Enfield EN2 6LD	13 Central Parade, New Addington, Croydon CR0 0JB
10.	275 Greenwich High Rd, Greenwich, London SE10 8NF	45 The Broadway, Ealing, London W5 5JU
11.	21 King St, London W6 0QF	1 Silver St, Enfield EN1 3EE
12.	312 Seven Sisters Rd, Finsbury Park, London N4 2AW	15 Blackheath Village, Kidbrooke, London SE3 9LH
13.	26-28 St Anns Road, Middlesex, Harrow HA1 1LA	19-20 Upper St, The Angel, London N1 0PJ
14.	173 High St, Hornchurch RM11 3YS	25 Gresham St, London EC2V 7HN
15.	28 High St, Uxbridge UB8 1JN	21-25 King St, Hammersmith, London W6 9HW
16.	127 High St, Hounslow TW3 1QP	417 North End Rd, Fulham, London SW6 1NS
17.	25 Islington High St, The Angel, London N1 9LJ	Wood Green Shopping City, 22-24, 149-153 High Rd, London N22 6EF
18.	92 Kensington High St, Kensington, London W8 4SH	37-39, South Mall, Edmonton Green Shopping Centre, Edmonton Green, London N9 0TZ
19.	103 Streatham Hill, Streatham, London SW2 4UE	286-288 Station Rd, Harrow HA1 2EB

20.	85 Lewisham High St, Lewisham, London SE13 6BE	1-3 Market Pl, Romford RM1 3AA
21.	5 Wimbledon Hill Rd, Wimbledon, London SW19 7NF	21-22 High St, Middlesex, Uxbridge UB8 1JD
22.	17 Boscawen St, Truro TR1 2QZ	High St, Hounslow TW3 1ES
23.	126 High Rd, Ilford IG1 1DA	19-20 Upper St, The Angel, London N1 0PJ
24.	67 George St, Richmond TW9 1HG	19-20 Upper St, The Angel, London N1 0PJ
25.	28 Borough High St, London SE1 1YB	33-33a King's Rd, Chelsea, London SW3 4LX
26.	75-77 High St, Sutton SM1 1DU	83 Clarence St, Kingston upon Thames KT1 1RE
27.	75 Whitechapel Rd, Shadwell, London E1 1DU	76 Kennington Rd, Lambeth, London SE11 6NL
28.	465 Bethnal Green Rd, London E2 9QW	120 Molesworth St, Lewisham High St, Lewisham, London SE13 6JG
29.	60 Fenchurch St, London EC3M 4BA	3 St George's Rd, Wimbledon, London SW19 4DR
30.	1-3, Bishopsgate, London EC2N 3AQ	60 Broadway, London E15 1NG
31.	192 Hoe St, Walthamstow, London E17 4QN	377 Eastern Ave, Ilford IG2 6LW
32.	73 Wandsworth High St, London SW18 2PT	19-21 The Quadrant, Richmond TW9 1BP
33.	333 Vauxhall Bridge Rd, Pimlico, London SW1V 1EJ	69-73 Borough High St, London SE1 1NQ
34.	5 Bank St, Jubilee Place, Canary Wharf, London E14 5NY	Unit 3, Park Pavillion, 40 Canada Square, Canary Wharf, London E14 5FW
35.	The Helicon, 1 South Pl, London EC2M 2UP	Forest Rd, Walthamstow, London E17 4PP
36.	100 Old Broad St, London EC2N 1BG	110-112 Putney High St, Putney, London SW15 1RG
37.	69 Pall Mall, St. James's, London SW1Y 5EY	98 Victoria St, Westminster, London SW1E 5JL

Appendix 2: Tables of Thematic Analysis and Descriptive Analysis

Table 4.2: focused coding number 1 for Q1

Liquidity Risk	
Interview 12	Banks in the UK may face liquidity issues specifically in terms of maintaining overnight liquidity and short term liquidity
Interview 17	The leverage or liquidity trade off for banks tend to be a double edged sword
Interview 19	Liquidity management is structurally different for many banks depending on their size and nature of operations
Interview 21	For many banks, liquidity is one of the most critical issue in current business environment

Table 4.3: focused coding number 2 for Q1

Asset Liability Management Risk	
Interview 25	Handling of asset liability maturity mismatch is a matter of concern for many banks

Table 4.3A: focused coding number 3 for Q1

Concentration Risk	
Interview 12	Uneven distribution of counterparties
Interview 14	Concentration risk tends to be a time bomb for banks that can bring down many banking institutions if investing heavily in one type of security, geographical area or in one industry.
Interview 17	High concentration risk made it vital for banks to sustain robust capitalisation.
Interview18	Risk of default

Table 4.4: focused coding number 4 for Q1

Market Risk	
Interview 8	Losses in on and off balance sheet positions
Interview 11	Market risk is a systemic risk
Interview 12	Market risk framework in banks
Interview 15	Market-risk modelling: Value at Risk (VaR)
Interview 19	Banks may be prone to different types of market risk

Table 4.6: focused coding number 1 for Q2

Risk management is about the development and implementation of a plan to manage risks
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Interview 8	Four steps of risk management to deal with banking risks such as identification and assessment of different risks, development and implementation of an action plan, review and reporting and follow up.
Interview 11	All staff especially risk managers in banks are responsible for risk management
Interview 18	Role of internal control system and corporate governance is critical to effective management of risks
Interview 21	Regulators require HSBC to adopt stress testing and formalise capital planning to weather future unpleasant economic events and counter banking risks.

Table 4.7: focused coding number 2 for Q2

Effective risk management plays a key role in the identification, assessment, evaluation and management of risks banks encounter.	
Interview 17	What risk management practices are followed in the bank depends on what types of risk are faced by the bank.
Interview 20	Effective risk management framework consists of risk management strategies and policies, organizational structure of bank, effective and efficient risk management processes, adequate internal controls system, appropriate information system and adequate process of internal capital adequacy assessment

Table 4.9: focused coding number 1 for Q3

May be used for the hedging purposes rather than for speculative trading activities	
Interview 8	Must be solely utilised for hedging purposes rather than speculation
Interview 9	Reducing the risk of adverse price fluctuations in an asset and taking an offset position in a related security.
Interview 17	Many underlying derivatives including futures, swaps, options and forward contracts are used by banks to hedge risks
Interview 20	Risk-Reward trade-off in hedging

Table 4.10: focused coding number 2 for Q3

In this current business environment especially after Brexit, HSBC and LLOYDS including other banks in the UK are using hedging to manage various kind of risks	
Interview 12	Utilising hedging tools puts HSBC and LLOYDS at competitive advantage
Interview 13	Both HSBC and LLOYDS are well equipped with resources to apply existing hedging techniques but still both banks need to do a lot in terms of hedging solutions.
Interview 17	It is a risk management strategy to offset losses in investment and help portfolio managers to mitigate their exposure to different kind of risks

Interview 21	There is increased demand for hedging products that the banks are seeking to develop and sell
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Table 4.12: focused coding number 1 for Q4

Risk managers in the bank and a centralised risk management function are responsible for identification and assessment of risk	
Interview 3	Risk perception plays a leading role in our decision making regarding risk management and development of internal control function in the bank
Interview 10	Risk handling of the bank determines how bank managers perceive and manage risks is reflected in their decision making
Interview 17	It is not a straightforward question to answer. However, how employees in HSBC manage risk depends on the risk management strategy, nature, size and banking structure of the bank.
Interview 23	Role of risk managers in LLOYDS is to oversee the activities of the bank that may pose threats, risks and incur losses and to determine the potential damage occurred as a result of these risks

Table 4.13: focused coding number 2 for Q4

Having a healthy banking environment in place ensures the robust managerial practice of risk assessment and risk management.	
Interview 8	Risk behaviour of bank managers is underpinned by the banking regulation, legislation, state policy on risk management and other intermediary organisations
Interview 17	A strong risk culture in the bank is essential for effective management of risks. Risk culture and management control are means of framing issues of risk through a mixture of formal and informal processes.
Interview 23	Risk handling by bank managers can be seen in the context of social constructionism. It means that bank managers act as agents on the behalf of shareholders to whom they assign authority and responsibility. Managers are also accountable to shareholders for actions they take and resources they use on their behalf.

Table 4.15: focused coding number 1 for Q5

The banks have established a risk policy on risk management and internal control.	
Interview 1	All staff members working in the bank play their overriding role in managing risk. However, risk managers are assigned clear responsibility and accountability for the process of risk management.
Interview 11	Training sessions, Continuous Professional Development (CPD) and performance appraisal etc
Interview 14	Risk managers in the bank have ultimate responsibility for risk management in the bank.

Interview 19	Risk management is a strategic business
Interview 21	HSBC has an effective independent risk management function under the supervision of a Chief Risk Officer with adequate resources, access, independence and stature to the board. Under the directions of independent risk management function, all employees working in the bank have responsibility to identify and assess risks.

Table 4.16: focused coding number 2 for Q5

Risk management is the integral part of induction and training of all staff in the bank enabling them to have a good understanding of risk management.	
Interview 7	Various initiatives and steps are taken to make employees aware of new developments in risk management and new risks emerging
Interview 9	All managers are required to be creative and thorough in their approach towards designing risk management strategies and solutions for the bank.
Interview 23	Banks embed a culture of risk awareness and risk understanding in induction of all staff members.

Table 4.18: focused coding number 1 for Q6

Basel accords are widely used risk management systems across the banking industry to manage various kinds of risks.	
Interview 4	After recent financial crisis of 2007-08 all banks in the UK are using Basel accords particularly Basel III to absorb financial shocks.
Interview 11	Basel accord is extensively used in HSBC to cope various types of risks. In addition, we have a clear policy document issued by the Bank of England (BoE) whose provisions on risk management and internal control we have to abide by for timely identification and assessment of risks.
Interview 12	In the light of bank's risk appetite and risk tolerance; bank defines the scope of various risks and determines the relationship with each other. Bank determines the impact of various risks with a particular focus on its capital and liquidity position. Based on the evaluation of the impact of assessed risks bank reports aggregate of risks to centralised department and then appropriate internal risk management action is determined to deal with risks.
Interview 19	Basel Accords (I, II, and III) are helping LLOYDS in managing liquidity risk, credit risk and operational risk. We are complying with guidelines issued by the UK government and Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) on risk management in order to make our bank resilient to any financial uncertainty.
Interview 22	I cannot explain full details of our risk management framework. What I illustrate that our bank has established a sound system of risk management enabling it deal with any unforeseen economic uncertainty.

Table 4.19: focused coding number 2 for Q6

Risk management framework consists of six components. These six components are risk identification, risk measurement, risk mitigation, risk reporting, risk monitoring and risk governance.	
Interview 4	A comprehensive risk management framework consists of eight key components enabling banks to redefine their risk management strategies and to determine the nature and scope of their internal control function.
Interview 18	A risk management framework has defined responsibilities for all staff and everyone is required to discharge their duties in the boundaries set by the framework.
Interview 20	A detailed analysis of key changes in current volatile business environment and technological developments especially in the UK may enable UK banks to stay alert to emerging risks and to redefine risk function accordingly.

Table 4.21: focused coding number 1 for Q7

Stringent corporate governance system in banks and guidance on effective risk management.	
Interview 3	A sound monitoring and follow up system in all branches of HSBC ensure that all employees are following risk management guidance on risk management.
Interview 14	Risk appetite and risk tolerance levels in HSBC to reduce risks to acceptable levels
Interview 18	Assessment and evaluation of risks are undertaken on daily basis. Aggregate of assessed risks are communicated to risk management department. Then various responses are designed and performed in response to the assessed risks
Interview 21	A tried and tested risk management system is working effectively in LLOYDS across London. We have a risk management framework that enables all staff working in the bank to identify possible risks in various areas of banking operations.

Table 4.22: Focused Coding Number 2 for Question 7

Risks prioritisation on the basis of their impact on the going concern status of banks and development of risk response strategies	
Interview 1	In HSBC, aim of risk management system is not only to eliminate all risks but also to reduce risks to a level that the bank is comfortable with its risk appetite and risk tolerance. Risks are prioritised depending on their impact on the going concern status of the bank. Risks response strategies are developed, performed and overseen by risk managers to ensure the effectiveness of risk management.
Interview 16	Communication of key risks and associated strategies to counter these risks is undertaken in a timely manner.
Interview 17	Rating 8 will be appropriate to give to our current risk management function with regards to evaluating its effectiveness

Interview 18	I believe our existing risk management system deserve rating of 7 keeping in mind emerging risks and financial innovation and technological developments.
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Table 4.24: focused coding number 1 for Q8

Basel accords particularly Basel II and Basel III are applied to banks in London	
Focussed Coding	
Interview 1	Poor risk management and corporate governance, overleveraging and inappropriate incentive structures
Interview 2	Strengthening the stability of banking system and achieving the degree of consistency between capital requirements of banks
Interview 13	Basel II and Basel III are useful standards for banking industry in the UK
Interview 24	Application of Basel accords is a matter of adjusting the standards according to the requirements of banks

Table 4.25: focused coding number 2 for Q8

Banks can use other standards too apart from Basel accords depending on types of risk they face and jurisdictions in which they operate	
Interview 3	The risk sharing characteristics necessitates the use of various capital rules
Interview 7	Capital adequacy e.g. buffer capital rules under Basel II and Basel III is a driving force for sound risk management
Interview 9	Risk management framework combined with Basel accords can make banking institutions more prudent and transparent
Interview 19	Basel II and potentially Basel III most likely targets conventional banks such as HSBC and LLOYDS offering them prudent approach and market discipline for better risk management.

Table 4.27: focused coding number 1 for Q9

More Capital	
Interview 3	Banks in the UK especially commercial banks hold more capital than usual
Interview 10	Nature of banking operations requires banks to maintain buffer capital anyway.
Interview12	Increased use of nonperforming loans in HSBC and LLOYDS and financial innovation lead them to have enough capital due to their exposure to various risks.
Interview 17	HSBC and LLOYDS are offering a wide range of financial products from insurance, mortgage and to investment businesses that require them to maintain more capital
Interviewe20	Capital requirements by Prudential Regulatory conduct Authority (PRA), Bank of England (BoE) and Basel II and III.

Table 4.28: focused coding number 2 for Q9

Less Capital	
Interview 1	Banking capital more likely depends on the size and nature of banking institution. Less amount of capital is acceptable in case of a small bank with simple products and business operations.
Interview 3	The risk sharing characteristics necessitates the use of various capital rules. The better risk sharing and adequate disclosure can lead to less capital to be held by banks.

Table 4.30: focused coding number 1 for Q10

Basel III may have significant impact on banks due to their business models	
Interview 1	Yes, Basel III may help the banking industry in enhancing its financial resilience because this new accord has potential to minimise the severity and probability of future financial crisis.
Interview 4	Tighter regulation and increased liquidity and capital requirements required by Basel III enhances the capability of banks to reduce risks they face enabling them to be more resilient in the case of any financial stress.
Interview 12	HSBC hold buffer capital and more liquidity to cope with financial challenges. Therefore, it may have minimal effect on HSBC
Interview 19	Leverage ratio introduced by Basel III brings system wide benefits by preventing the huge build up of debt across the banking sector during good times.

Table 4.31: Focused Coding Number 2 for Question 10

It is too early to judge until all details of Basel III come into force. However, most likely, it can help banks in enhancing their financial resilience	
Interview 4	It has introduced new measures such as stress testing, leverage ratio and capital ratio that is a requirement of the Bank of England (BoE) to use stress testing in order to measure banking capital with regards to their Risk Weighted Assets enabling the banks to increase their financial resilience.
Interview 6	I think Basel III has bigger impact on the banks because of their stringent measures on increased regulation and use of their business models
Interview 22	For the time being, extended implementation period of Basel III making its impact relatively irrelevant

Table 4.33: focused coding number 1 for Q11

Failures of Basel II need to be addressed and should ensure Basel III overcome those failures	
Interview 4	Basel II was absolutely failed to prevent recent financial meltdown of 2007-08
Interview 9	Basel II went wrong on various fronts such as liquidity, procyclicality and stress testing

Table 4.34: focused coding number 2 for Q11

The effectiveness of Basel III is linked to robust economic and regulatory reinforcements	
Interview 4	Basel III has potential to enhance financial resilience of the banks by requiring them to use stress testing and liquidity ratio. These measures may assist banks in determining their capital requirements and thus reduce systemic risk.
Interview 6	Basel III is a good standard for banks but it entails implementation problems
Interview 19	We cannot blame only Basel II for not preventing financial crisis, please blame the system that tends to be based on lack of morals and greed

Table 4.36: focused coding number 1 for Q12

Banks have shown strong resilience	
Interview 3	Our bank is resilient to any financial crisis because we are following leverage ratio and stress testing introduced by Basel III in order to maintain buffer capital in case of any worst case scenario
Interview 11	Stress testing with help of @RISK software to test capital requirements against Risk weighted Assets (RWA) is used in most of the UK banks
Interview 22	UK industry is more regulated than ever before and I think it has capability to absorb financial shocks in case of future financial crisis.

Table 4.37: focused coding number 2 for Q12

UK banking industry has adopted various regulatory measures	
Interview 1	Use of Net Stable Funding Ratio and the Liquidity Coverage Ratio in UK big banks like HSBC, Barclays and LLOYDS is a great step towards enhancing the financial resilience of the banks.
Interview 7	Quality of bank regulatory capital has improved with the passage of time
Interview 10	I cannot answer this question on the behalf of whole banking industry in the UK. However, UK banking industry has adopted various regulatory measures laid down by Basel Accords, Bank of England, intermediary institutions and other regulators after financial crisis of 2008.
Interview 20	UK banks are a part of global financial system. Therefore, they are not immune from the

	credit crisis.
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Table 4.39: focused coding number 1 for Q13

Enhanced Risk management and mitigation	
Interview 2	Enhance risk management procedures and risk culture
Interview 8	The banking industry demands more advanced risk management techniques
Interview 19	There is more room for improvement in risk management

Table 4.40: focused coding number 2 for Q13

There is no specific answer to this question. But a comprehensive framework on risk management covering key aspects on risk may be appropriate.	
Interview 6	UK Banking industry requires more advanced and sophisticated risk management system in order to deal with risks and challenges they may counter in this global world.
Interview 17	Various leading risk management frameworks adopted in various jurisdictions such as COSO framework, Sarbanes Oxley Act, and the UK good governance code can help in developing a more sophisticated and comprehensive risk management system.

Table 4.41: focused coding number 3 for Q13

Increased cost and extensive regulatory burden can stop banks from implementing risk management framework	
Interview 11	Regulatory burden, increase cost and adaptability of employees to new changes can restrict banks especially smaller banks from implementing new system.

Table 4.52 Risk faced by banks and their severity

		Statistics					
		Market Risk	Asset Liability Management Risk	Liquidity risk	Interest Rate Risk	Credit risk	Operational Risk
N	Valid	250	250	250	250	250	250
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 4.53

		Market Risk			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	101	40.4	40.4	40.4
	Yes	149	59.6	59.6	100.0

	Total	250	100.0	100.0	
--	-------	-----	-------	-------	--

Table 4.54

Asset Liability Management Risk					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	173	69.2	69.2	69.2
	Yes	77	30.8	30.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.55

Liquidity risk					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	218	87.2	87.2	87.2
	Yes	32	12.8	12.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.56

Interest Rate Risk					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	208	83.2	83.2	83.2
	Yes	42	16.8	16.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.57

Credit risk					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	208	83.2	83.2	83.2
	Yes	42	16.8	16.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.58

Operational Risk					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	208	83.2	83.2	83.2

	Yes	42	16.8	16.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.59

Market Risk					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Unimportant	12	4.8	4.8	4.8
	Neutral	18	7.2	7.2	12.0
	Important	32	12.8	12.8	27.2
	Very Important	182	72.8	72.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.60

Equity Risk					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Unimportant	30	12.0	12.0	12.0
	Important	137	54.8	54.8	66.8
	Very Important	83	33.2	33.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.61

Reputation Risk					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Unimportant	34	13.6	13.6	13.6
	Important	216	86.4	86.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.62

Off balance sheet Risk					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Unimportant	109	43.6	43.8	43.8
	Unimportant	140	56.0	56.2	100.0
	Total	249	99.6	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.4		

Total	250	100.0		
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Table 4.63

Asset Liability Management Risk					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Unimportant	19	7.6	7.6	7.6
	Unimportant	22	8.8	8.8	16.5
	Neutral	20	8.0	8.0	24.5
	Important	173	69.2	69.5	94.0
	Very Important	15	6.0	6.0	100.0
	Total	249	99.6	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.4		
Total		250	100.0		

Table 4.64

Liquidity Risk					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Important	79	31.6	31.6	31.6
	Very Important	171	68.4	68.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.65

Operational Risk					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Unimportant	75	30.0	30.0	30.0
	Neutral	20	8.0	8.0	38.0
	Important	108	43.2	43.2	81.2
	Very Important	47	18.8	18.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.66

Credit Risk					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Important	141	56.4	56.4	56.4

	Very Important	109	43.6	43.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Graphs (Descriptive Analysis)

Appendix 3: Request for Interview

Date

Dear Sir/Madam,

My name is Zahid Rasheed and I am currently a DBA student at the University of the West of Scotland, London, under the supervision and guidance of Dr. Hosein Piranfar. As part of the research of my thesis, I am undertaking a study on evaluating the effectiveness of risk management practices in the UK banks in particular since the 2009 financial crisis.

In order to meet the aim and objectives of this study, I endeavour to conduct interviews with bank managers, risk managers and other banking personnel who may be associated with the risk process. In this regard, I would like to solicit your assistance in obtaining your opinion of risk as a banking expert. I would be very grateful if you would agree to an interview to discuss a few issues relating to this topic.

Please be assured that you would not be asked nor required to disclose any sensitive information pertinent to your bank's operations or activities. This interview is solely to gain insight into what you think about risk and risk management in your bank. Your response will contribute to my research studies here at the UWS. The interview is expected to last for approximately 30-35 minutes; a list of the questions is attached.

The information obtained would be treated in the strictest of confidence as guided by the university's code of ethics for research studies. Complete anonymity would be maintained and no name of any person or the name of your bank or any institution would be mentioned in my research.

Thank you for your time, and I look forward to hearing from you.

Yours sincerely

ZAHID RASHEED

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 4: Interview Schedule

Date: _____

Interview Start Time: _____

Interview Finish Time: _____

Bank Name / Type: _____

Hello, Dear Sir\Madam, my name is ZAHID RASHEED and I am a DBA student at University of the West of Scotland in United Kingdom. As part of the research of my thesis, I am undertaking a study on evaluating the effectiveness of risk management practices in the UK banks.

I am thankful to you for agreeing to participate in my research study. Once again I assure you that all responses to this interview will be kept strictly confidential and used for academic research purposes only. I would appreciate your point of view regarding the preliminary research on risk management and hopeful that it will help me to refine, validate and add more detail in the analysis.

Gender: _____

Work Experience (YY: MM)

Overall: _____ **Risk Management:** _____

Appendix 5: Informed Consent Form for Survey Questionnaire

Research Title: Risk Management in the UK Banks

Researcher: Zahid Rasheed, DBA Student, University of the West of Scotland London,
United Kingdom

Contact Details: [REDACTED] Personal details withheld.

Research Purpose: This study intends to assess the effectiveness of current practices of risk management followed in the UK banks in order to develop a sound risk management framework to enhance the financial resilience of the banking sector. This study is based on some conceptual aspects of different risk management practices adopted by the banks and to what extent these efforts are successful in achieving their objectives in the UK.

What is required in participation?

I shall need your participation in the questionnaire survey. If you are willing then please complete this form and return it.

Your participation in this survey is voluntary and you can refuse to give answer for any question or even to withdraw your involvement at any point from this research project. All of your responses to this survey will be kept strictly confidential and will only be attributed to you with your prior permission.

Confidentiality will also be maintained by coding and storing all the questionnaires in such a way that it will be impossible to identify them directly with any individual. For this purpose, these questionnaires will be organized by numbers rather than by names.

Consent: (If you want to participate, please tick on the appropriate boxes below)

I have read all the above information

I am willing to participate in this research study

Participant's Signature: _____ Date: _____

Appendix 6: Survey Questionnaire

Part 1

- The purpose of part 1 is to obtain general information related to your institution and yourself as an anonymous participant in this study

Name: -----

Institution Name: _____

Gender: _____

Part II

- The section has been designed to obtain information about various aspects of risk management practices.
- Please read the questions carefully and tick () the selected choice clearly.

Risk Understanding

Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
1.	There is a general understanding of risk management across the bank	1	2	3	4	5
2.	There is an adequate system for understanding different risks used in the bank					
3.	Responsibility for understanding risk and risk management is clearly defined across the bank					
4.	Accountability for risk management and understanding of risk is defined in the banks					

Risk identification

Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree

5.	The bank conducts a systematic and detailed identification of risks it faces pertinent to its established aim and objectives.					
6.	Bank faces difficulties in prioritising risks					
7.	The bank knows its strengths and weaknesses of its risk management function in place					
8.	The banks has envisaged and established techniques for systematic identification of opportunities					
9.	It is very important for bank to implement the most widely accepted techniques for risk identification					

Risk Assessment and Analysis

Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
10.	The bank evaluates the probability of risks occurring					
11.	The bank uses quantitative methods of risk analysis					
12.	Qualitative analysis methods are also used by the bank to assess risks (e.g. high, moderate, low)					
13.	Assessment of bank to analysed risks includes cost- benefit assessment of addressing risks					
14.	The bank's response to analysed risks includes prioritization of risks and selection of those risks that require active management					
15.	The bank's response to analysed risks includes prioritization of risk treatments where there are resource constraints on risk treatment implementation					

16.	A computer based system is used by the bank to estimate the earnings and risk management variability.					
17.	The bank relies on the output of quantitative data with human judgment					

Risk Monitoring and Controlling

Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
18.	Monitoring the effectiveness of risk management is key component of management reporting process					
19.	The level of control by the bank is appropriate for the risks that it faces					
20.	The bank has adopted a standard reporting system about the risk management from bottom to top management					
21.	Reporting and communication processes within the bank support the effective management of risk.					
22.	The bank's response to risk includes an evaluation of the effectiveness of the existing controls and risk management responses					
23.	The bank's response to risk includes action plans in implementation decisions about identified risk					
24.	The bank effectively monitors the credit limit of everyone counterparty					
25.	The borrower's business performance is regularly observed by the bank following the extension of financing					

Managing Market Risk

Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
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26.	The market risk strategy is envisaged by the board of directors that is implemented by top management in the banks in the form of policies and procedures					
27.	Market risk exposure of bank is maintained at prudent levels and is in accordance with capital bank holds					
28.	The bank has a sound system of risk management in the form of policies, infrastructure and processes for managing market risk					
29.	Assessment of bank to analysed risks includes cost- benefit assessment of addressing risks					
30.	The bank uses various risk measurement methodologies to assess market risk in its various banking activities					

Managing Credit Risk

Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
31.	The credit risk strategy is envisaged by the board of directors that is implemented by top management in the banks in the form of policies and procedures					
32.	The bank adopts a credit risk system to assess the creditworthiness of customers across all its credit activities					
33.	The bank has a sound system of risk management in the form of policies, infrastructure and processes for managing credit risk					
34.	Credit portfolio is monitored by the					

	bank on day to day basis and takes action in case of any unpleasant credit events					
35.	A periodic report of credit risk is prepared by bank regularly					

Managing Operational Risk

Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
36.	Bank adopts a comprehensive set of policies, guidelines and policies for managing operational risk					
37.	All categories of operational risk are defined and contemplated by executive management and board of directors in the bank.					
38.	The bank ensures business continuity and contingency plans in the event of any business disruption in order to minimise losses and operate as a going concern.					
39.	Thorough operational risk management policy established by the top management of the bank transforms the strategic direction given by the board of directors					
40.	A periodic report of operational risk is prepared by bank regularly					

Managing Liquidity Risk

Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
41.	Bank adopts a comprehensive set of policies, guidelines and policies for managing liquidity risk					
42.	The bank has a sound system of risk management established by board of directors in the form of policies, infrastructure and processes for					

	managing market risk					
43.	Bank can reduce its liquidity losses by applying a robust system of liquidity risk management					
44.	A periodic report of operational risk is prepared by bank regularly					

Risk Management Practices

Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
45.	Executive management of the bank regularly reviews the performance of its operations in managing its risks					
46.	Bank has an effective system of receiving feedback on risk management strategies and its performance					
47.	Bank's strategy and policy ensure adequate training and induction of all employees in relation to risk management					
48.	Risk management processes and strategies are documented and appropriate guidance is provided to staff responsible for risk management					
49.	Bank needs to employ specialised people in its risk management department					
50.	Establishment of a sound risk management function is one of the main objectives of the bank.					
51.	Bearing into mind recent financial crisis of 2007-08, banks hold enough capital to absorb financial shocks if capital ratio to risk weighted assets (RWA) is equal to capital adequacy ratio set by Bank of England.					

52.	Current risk management practices adopted by the bank in current volatile business environment are sound and efficient.					
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Part III

- The third section is designed to obtain information about various risks, techniques and methods and techniques used by the banks in the UK to manage them.

53. Severity of risks facing big UK banks

Following are the main risks faced by big banks in the UK. Could you please identify the importance/ severity of following risks according to your own perception?

Risk	Very Important	Important	Neutral	Unimportant	Very Unimportant
Credit Risk					
Market Risk					
Operational Risk					
Liquidity Risk					
Asset Liability Management Risk					
Off balance sheet Risk					
Reputation Risk					
Equity Risk					
Interest rate Risk					
Technology risk					

54. Could you list below any other risks encountered by big banks in the UK in current business environment? Ranking in order of severity/importance?

- a.
- b.
- c.
- d.

55. Please indicate key methods used by banks for risk identification by banks

Sr No	Method	Yes	No
a.	Scenario Analysis		

b.	SWOT Analysis		
c.	Benchmarking		
d.	Audit		
e.	Risk Survey		
f.	Inspection by bank risk staff		
g.	Process Analysis		
h.	Internal communication (Periodical Reports and Risk Reports)		
	Any other (please specify)		

56. Please indicate key methods used by banks in the UK for measurement and analysis of risks.

Sr No	Method	Yes	No
a.	Gap Analysis		
b.	Credit Worthiness Analysis		
c.	Duration (Average of Life) Analysis		
d.	Sensitivity Analysis		
e.	Maturity Matching Analysis		
f.	Financial Statement Analysis		
g.	Statistical Models for Risk Measurement		
h.	Any other (please specify)		

57. Please indicate key techniques used by big banks in the UK for risk monitoring and controlling.

Sr No	Method	Yes	No
a.	Assets Diversification		
b.	Collateral Arrangement		
c.	Security Deposits		
d.	Reserves for Loan loss		
e.	Staff Supervision and Training		
f.	On balance sheet netting		
g.	Contingency Plans		
h.	Derivatives (i.e. Forwards, Futures, Options and Swaps)		
i.	Establishing Standards (e.g. Credit Limits)		
j.	Hedging		
	Any other (please specify)		

58. Please indicate key reports used by banks for risk reporting.

Sr No	Method	Yes	No
-------	--------	-----	----

a.	Report for Market Risk		
b.	Report for Operational Risk		
c.	Report for Interest Rate Risk		
d.	Report for Liquidity Risk		
e.	Report for Credit Risk		
f.	Report for Foreign Exchange Risk		
g.	Report for Country Risk		
h.	Any other (please specify)		

59. Which of the following methods are used by the banks in order to calculate minimum capital requirements?

- Basel II standards

 IFSB standards
 Other, please specify

 Don't know

60. Please mark appropriate options that are used by banks in order to manage risks under Basel Accords

Credit Risk

- Standardised approach

 Foundation IRB

 Advanced IRB
 Other, please specify

 Don't know

Market Risk

- Standardised approach

 Internal models approach
 Other, please specify

 Don't know

Operational Risk

- Basic indicator approach

 Advanced measurement approach
 Other, please specify

 Don't know

61. What is your opinion about the capital requirements of big banks in the UK in the light of recent financial crisis?

- Higher

 Same

 Lower

 Don't know

62. Please mark appropriate box in the following table

Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
a.	In the context of Basel Accords 111; increased capital requirement is effective in reducing risks					
b.	Basel 11 standards need to be reviewed after failing to prevent financial crisis					
c.	New Basel 111 regulatory standards may help banks in enhancing their financial resilience					
d.	Risk management processes and Stringent capital, liquidity and leverage standards recommended under Basel III may prevent another financial crisis from occurring.					

Thank You for your time and consideration

Appendix 7: Ethical Approval

28/11/2018

Dear Zahid Rasheed,

Your application 6225: Risk Management in the UK Banks , submission 4542, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean

Appendix 8: Reference letter for data collection: HSBC

Date 08 November 2018
Direct [REDACTED]
E-mail [REDACTED]
Our Ref LCJ

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

London Campus
235 Southwark Bridge Road
London
SE1 6NP
England, UK

Banner ID: [REDACTED]
Programme Code: [REDACTED]

TO HSBC

STUDENT STATUS LETTER

This is to confirm that the under noted postgraduate student is matriculated at this University for the current session.

[REDACTED]

Nationality:	Pakistani
Enrolment Status:	Enrolled
Attendance Mode:	Full Time
Programme Title:	DBA
Majoring in:	DBA
Year of programme student is enrolled in:	Pg Diploma Level 11 (SCQF level 12)
Qualification:	Doctor of Business Administration
Date Commenced Study:	08/08/2016
Average Attendance:	30 hours per week
Expected End Date of Programme:	09/08/2019

[REDACTED]

I trust this information is of assistance to you. All information provided is accurate and correct at the date given at the top of the letter.

Yours faithfully,

[REDACTED]

Nathan Ziel
Student Assistant

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 9: Reference letter for data collection: LLOYDS

Date 08 November 2018

Direct
E-mail

Our Ref LCJ

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

London Campus
235 Southwark Bridge Road
London
SE1 6NP
England, UK

TO LLOYDS

STUDENT STATUS LETTER

This is to confirm that the under noted postgraduate student is matriculated at this University for the current session.

Nationality: Pakistani
Enrolment Status: Enrolled
Attendance Mode: Full Time
Programme Title: DBA
Majoring in: DBA
Year of programme student is enrolled in: Pg Diploma Level 11 (SCQF level 12)
Qualification: Doctor of Business Administration
Date Commenced Study: 08/08/2016
Average Attendance: 30 hours per week
Expected End Date of Programme: 09/08/2019

I trust this information is of assistance to you. All information provided is accurate and correct at the date given at the top of the letter.

Nathan Ziel
Student Assistant

Personal details withheld.

